

EXPLORING ESOL LECTURER IDENTITIES THROUGH THE LENS OF
INTERSECTIONALITY: THE SCOTTISH COLLEGE CONTEXT.

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August, 2024

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the
requirements of the University of the West of
Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Abstract

This PhD thesis investigates the multifaceted identities of English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL) lecturers within the Scottish college context within an intersectional framework. The study addresses the ways in which different identity variables interact and intersect, and how certain identity characteristics are perceived within the profession creating unequal relations of power.

The study applies a qualitative methodology within a critical paradigm that involved nine in-depth interviews with ESOL lecturers and curriculum managers who were employed in colleges across Scotland. The findings are presented in two interrelated chapters. The first chapter employs thematic analysis to explore the identities of the lecturers and their intersections in order to identify unequal practices within Scottish ESOL departments. This chapter shows that the prevailing norm within these departments is largely comprised of white, British, native English-speaking, and heterosexual ESOL lecturers, who could be considered as 'standard'. In contrast, those who do not align with these characteristics are perceived as the 'other' in the profession, for example, lecturers who are from ethnic minorities, non-British or queer, leading to their discomfort, reluctance to pursue opportunities, and feelings of exclusion. The participants' opinions about the future of the Scottish ESOL profession in terms of the diversity of lecturers in the departments are explored.

The second findings chapter employs Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) to delve into the language that the participants of the study use during the interviews, and explores how power dynamics and the dominant discourse are embedded in language. By focusing on language and power, the study uncovers the reinforcement of dominant ideas and the potential to categorize certain identity characteristics as either 'standard' or 'other'. Both thematic and discursive analyses are essential in identifying instances of inequality linked to identity and professional role. In addition, both analyses demonstrate that even those considered privileged due to their perceived 'standard' ESOL teacher profile or positions of authority can experience disempowerment or invisibility within the profession

Given the increasing significance of ESOL education in Scotland, particularly in Further Education (FE) colleges, this study fills a gap in the limited research on ESOL lecturer identities. The study's intersectional framework not only explores the intricate identities of ESOL lecturers but also sheds light on potential unequal practices and aims to empower diverse identities within the profession. By addressing the complexities of identity and power relations in ESOL education, this research contributes to the evolving literature on the topic and offers insights into the rapidly expanding FE ESOL sector in Scotland. In addition, this study contributes to the current debates on language teacher identity and intersectionality that are being explored in different areas and encourages other scholars to explore the field of ESOL in Scotland as well as to employ the framework of intersectionality in English language education beyond this study.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude to my wonderful supervisors, Dr Margaret Allan and Dr Fernando León Solís and my advisor Dr Lisa McAuliffe for their invaluable guidance and support, and exceptional mentorship throughout my Ph.D. journey. Their expertise, encouragement, and constructive feedback have played a vital role in shaping this thesis and my overall growth as an academic. I am deeply grateful for their dedication, patience, and belief in my potential.

Of course, I would like to extend my appreciation to the participants of my research study. Their willingness to dedicate their time, share their experiences, and contribute to my research has been instrumental in the successful completion of this study. Their valuable insights and contributions have enriched the depth and breadth of this thesis, and I am sincerely grateful for their participation.

I would also like to express my gratitude to all my colleagues and peers who have provided support and many valuable discussions. I am extremely thankful for the knowledge exchange and the sense of community we have fostered in room J202, which has made this academic pursuit more rewarding.

In addition, I would like to express a special thank you to my loving husband, who has been a constant pillar of encouragement and support in this journey, particularly in times of COVID-19 lockdown. His love and belief in my abilities have sustained me during the challenging moments of this academic pursuit. I am eternally grateful for his patience when my topics of conversation revolved solely around ESOL and intersectionality, and my desk was filled with empty cups of coffee. I am also immensely thankful to my family for their unconditional love and support throughout this long journey. Their belief in my capabilities and their words of encouragement have given me the strength to persevere. Despite the distance, they have always been just a phone call away, ready to send words of encouragement. Special thank you to my mum, Lorraine Barrowcliffe, for providing an excellent example of what it means to be a great English teacher, mum and woman.

Lastly, I would like to express my gratitude to my two faithful companions, Manu and Amber, who have remained loyal underneath my desk throughout the whole journey. Their wagging tails, and their cuddles have provided solace and happiness during the stressful periods of my research and have forced me to take some rests. They have been a source of inspiration and a constant reminder to enjoy the simple pleasures of life.

To all those mentioned above, I cannot adequately express my appreciation for their encouragement and support. Their contributions have been immeasurable, and this thesis would not have been possible without them.

Thank you all from the bottom of my heart.

Paula Alcaraz Barrowcliffe.

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Glossary of key terms

Black: The term 'Black' is capitalized, as suggested by (Gerald (2020) and Collins and Bilge (2020) because it refers not to skin colour, but to a political term that acknowledges the cultural identity and shared experiences of systemic racism faced by people who are not considered white.

CDA: Critical Discourse Analysis.

CPD: Continual Professional development.

CRT: Critical Race Theory

EAL: English as an Additional Language. In Scotland, and in the context of this study, this term is used to refer to English language programmes delivered to speakers of other languages who are 16 or under (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019) .

EFL: English as a Foreign Language. In this study, EFL refers to English language programmes taught in countries where English is not the first or official language.

ELT: English language teaching. In this thesis, the term is employed as an umbrella term to refer to all the different context in which English language is taught as a second language.

ESOL: English for Speakers of Other Languages. In Scotland, and in the context of this study, this term is used to refer to English language programmes delivered to adults (16+) whose first language is not English.

LTI: Language Teacher Identity

L1: Speaker's first language

L2: Speaker's second language

NEST: Native English-speaking teachers.

NNEST: Non-native English-speaking teachers.

SCQF: Scottish Credit and Qualification Framework

TESOL: Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages. In this study, TESOL is used to refer to the global English language teaching profession.

white: Following Gerald's (2020) suggestion, this term is not capitalised as it does not reflect a shared identity, but a skin colour that has been traditionally linked to privilege.

Chapter 1 – Introduction

1.1 Introduction

The human is understood differentially depending on its race, the legibility of that race, its morphology, the recognizability of that morphology, its sex, the perceptual verifiability of that sex, its ethnicity, the categorical understanding of that ethnicity. Certain humans are recognized as less than human, and that form of qualified recognition does not lead to a viable life (Butler, 2004, p. 2)

In the above quotation Butler summarises how certain identity characteristics are perceived differently by society and, as a result, these perceptions can have a negative impact on a person's life. In a context such as ESOL education in Scotland, where students come from a large variety of countries, and for a variety of reasons, and lecturers are exposed on a daily basis to a large variety of people, the way in which different identity characteristics are perceived deserves to be explored. This thesis focuses on exploring the identity of ESOL lecturers working in Scottish colleges through an intersectional lens (Crenshaw, 1989) to uncover any unequal practices stemming from how their identities are perceived within the ESOL profession. Additionally, it investigates the perspectives of ESOL college lecturers in Scotland on the future of the profession, particularly regarding the potential for greater diversity among lecturers. As I will develop in the rationale, the focus of this study responds to the recent interest in language teacher identity (LTI) research (Barkhuizen, 2017) and the exploration of power dynamics and hierarchies within the staff in the department and the broader college sector.

1.2 Structure of the thesis

The thesis is structured around eight chapters; each focuses on a particular area of the study, and together, serve the purpose of exploring the research questions that are presented in section 1.5 of this chapter, and discussed in the last chapter.

This first chapter is an introduction to the thesis where I explore the significance of the study and my rationale for focusing on this particular area, and where I introduce the research questions and aims of the study. In addition, in this chapter I scrutinize my own positionality as the researcher, as a former ESOL lecturer, and as a professional actively involved in the English language teaching profession. I also reflect on my own identity and its effects on my positionality in this study. Altogether, this chapter presents the focus of the study, addresses any potential bias, and gives the reader an understanding of the perspective of this study.

The second chapter provides the context for the study, exploring the background of TESOL as a global profession, ESOL education in Scotland, and the genealogy of intersectionality. It

also serves to locate the study within the particular setting in which the research questions are explored.

The third chapter is a review of the literature central to the areas of interest for this study. This includes an analysis and discussion of the literature around power, language teacher identity, English language varieties in ELT, and current debates regarding ESOL education in Scotland. This body of knowledge informs and supports discussion of the findings of the study.

Chapter 4 focuses on an exploration of the theoretical framework employed in this study: intersectionality. The chapter offers a discussion around the definition of intersectionality, its main criticisms and a defence of the reasons why this framework is suitable for the purpose of this study. Lastly, it sets out a detailed discussion of how the framework is adopted for this particular piece of research.

The fifth chapter of the thesis explores the methodology that underpins the study. The chapter offers a discussion around the research paradigm of the study, the ontology and epistemology and the way in which the study is situated and designed taking into account ethical considerations and limitations. This chapter is key to understanding how the data collection and subsequent analyses of the findings have been put into practice.

Chapters 6 and 7 comprise the findings of the study. The data has been analysed from two perspectives; chapter 6 provides a discussion of the findings from a thematic analysis of the interviews with participants. In this first analysis I identify key themes, and ideas related to diversity, the perception of ESOL lecturers' identities in the profession, and the implications this has in the ESOL departments and in the wider college sector. Chapter 7 presents a discussion of the findings from the perspective of a critical discourse analysis where I explore the language in relation to power structures, and how it helps to create, maintain and challenge situations of perceived inequality and privilege in the college ESOL departments in Scotland. Although they are presented separately to enhance clarity in the discussion, both chapters need to be read as complementary, rather than independently. Both chapters are interlinked, each complementing and enriching the other by examining lecturer identities, power structures, and the participants' sense of belonging to and 'otherness' in the profession from different perspectives. This dual approach enables a more comprehensive and nuanced exploration of the research questions and, collectively, offers a more robust understanding of the findings of the study.

The final chapter concludes the study by summarizing the preceding chapters and discussing the research questions in light of the study's findings. It addresses the study's limitations and offers reflections on what could have been done differently. Additionally, the chapter explores the implications of the research, provides recommendations, and suggests directions for future research.

1.3 Rationale

In this short excerpt, Lawrence and Nagashima (2019 p.52) describe how their personal identity cannot be detached from their professional practice as English language teachers; quite the reverse, as it seems to have shaped their professional selves:

It appears evident that the intersectionality of who we are as individuals, in terms of the context-driven perception of gender, sexuality, race, and linguistic status, has had a direct and profound impact on our careers as language teachers.

They also describe identity as 'intersectional' in the way that it refers not only to one identity characteristic, but to the combination of gender, sexuality, race, and linguistic status as parts of a whole. These two concepts, the importance of teacher identity, and identity as intersectional, are at the forefront of this study.

As I will explore and develop further in the next two chapters, identity and the perception of certain identity characteristics within the profession have been an important focal point in English language education research. As Lindahl and Yazan (2019) argue this topic is central to the teachers' practice inside the classroom:

how teachers' and teacher educators' practice and ongoing learning is informed by their identities; their learning and practice involves negotiation, enactment, and (trans)formation of identities, and their professional identities are complexly intertwined and intersected with their other social identities (Lindahl and Yazan, 2019, p. 2).

In the past, many studies have explored identity by focusing on one identity characteristic (Kubota and Lin, 2006; Kamhi-Stein, 2016; Neena, 2019) or a combination of two or more factors (Amin, 1997; Hume, 2013). These studies have identified that there are certain identity features that seem to be privileged by recruiters, students and some colleagues in the profession. For example, being a native speaker of English (Ruecker and Ives, 2015; Holliday, 2018), being white (Kubota and Lin, 2006; Ruecker and Ives, 2015), or being associated with heteronormativity (Moore, 2020) seem to be the preferred characteristics in the global TESOL profession, while other characteristics are perceived as 'inferior'. These perceptions may have an impact on hiring practices (Selvi, 2010; Mahboob and Golden, 2013; Jenkins, 2017), or the way teachers are perceived by students (Neena, 2019; Wright, 2024) or by other members of the profession (Basurto-Santos and Sánchez-Menéndez, 2018).

These studies have been helpful in shedding light on the issues surrounding certain discriminatory practices in ELT. However, by focusing on identity characteristics in isolation they fail to address the complexity of how certain identity characteristics interplay and influence our own experience of reality creating unique situations of oppression and privilege (Collins and Bilge, 2020) in the profession. With reference to Lawrence and Nagashima's (2019) excerpt at the beginning of this section, it is evident that if our identity can be considered as intersectional, the issues related to how identity is discussed in the profession should be explored from an intersectional perspective.

Although intersectionality did not emerge in the field of language education – I will come back to this in chapter 2 – it has been successfully employed in different contexts in the discipline (Romero, 2017; Lawrence and Nagashima, 2019; Haynes *et al.*, 2020; Maddamsetti, 2020). In fact, there seems to be a move to expand the framework to new contexts (Carbado *et al.*, 2013; Leckie and Buser De, 2020) such as the exploration of ESOL lecturers' identities in Scottish colleges, as a way to address perceived inequalities that have been traditionally overlooked, and to bring a consideration of new perspectives to the profession, ultimately aiming to transform it, and contribute positively to fairer practices.

There has been a steep increase in demand for ESOL provision in Scotland over the last decades, particularly in the college sector, where the majority of classes are offered (Stella, 2010; Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019). This increase has occurred as a consequence of migration. However, research in this area has started to emerge relatively recently (Allan, 2015; Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019; Brown, 2020, 2021; Stella and MacDougall, 2021; Stella and Kay, 2023), and to date, the identity of ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges and its effects on the profession have not been explored. Thus, it is now the right time to address this topic as the field of ESOL education in Scotland continues to grow (Stella and Kay, 2023), and as a consequence, there will be a greater demand for ESOL lecturers in colleges.

I believe that this is a particularly important topic due to the existing and perceived power relations between teachers and students, as well as among ESOL practitioners which are often 'hidden' or 'unspoken' (Pennycook, 2020; Brown and Bicknell, 2021). In addition, identifying whether the FE ESOL sector in Scotland mirrors the global ELT industry in what is considered to be a perception of the 'ideal' teacher of English (Amin, 1997; Selvi, 2010; Appleby, 2016) may be beneficial in order to prompt reflection on the hiring criteria, the teaching methods and their influence on the profession. It can also serve to identify the power relations that continue to support the global TESOL profession and the Scottish college sector, and to identify, and indeed discuss and raise awareness of possible solutions for these issues.

1.4 Significance of the study

This study seeks to examine how the various identity characteristics of ESOL lecturers interact and intersect, as well as how they are perceived within ESOL departments and the broader college sector. In addition, it aims to explore how these interactions may contribute to situations of privilege and discrimination, whether intentional or unintentional.

This exploration will lead to an understanding of whether there are any areas of identity that are valued more than others in the profession, and what impact this might have for the lecturers, for the students, and for the sector more generally in terms of potentially influencing the curriculum or teaching practices.

In addition, the study seeks to gain insights into the perceptions of college ESOL lecturers in Scotland regarding the future of the profession in terms of the diversity of staff in their departments. As a result, the study will identify possible ways in which ESOL departments and the colleges as institutions could implement changes to enhance diversity in the body of lecturers that teach in Scottish ESOL departments.

Ultimately, the study aims to make a contribution to knowledge through engaging with current debates around intersectionality in education (Shelton, Flynn and Grosland, 2018; Leckie and Buser De, 2020; Maddamsetti, 2020), ESOL education in Scotland (Allan, 2015; Brown, 2021), and the discourses regarding unequal practices in the broader TESOL profession (Davis and Skilton-Sylvester, 2004; Appleby, 2016; Basurto-Santos and Sánchez-Menéndez, 2018; García Ponce, 2020).

1.5 Research questions and aims.

Following the reasons discussed in the rationale, and in order to make the contributions to knowledge described in the significance of the study, the thesis aims to address the following research questions, which have been selected and informed by a review of relevant literature, and the researcher's positionality:

1. In what ways do the different identity variables of ESOL lecturers in the Scottish college context interact and intersect?
2. Are ESOL lecturers in Scotland subject to unequal practices on account of perceptions around their identity (gender, race, sexuality, accent, country of origin etc...)?
3. What are the ESOL lecturers' perceptions regarding the future of ESOL departments in Scottish Colleges in terms of staff diversity?

1.6 Positionality: my place in the study.

According to Bukamal (2022, p.328) "*positionality*¹ is the term given to [the researcher's] biography - a biography that pays particular attention to the context that creates the researcher's identity, an identity that will affect the way that the social world is seen and understood". In other words, it serves to 'locate' the researcher's position in the research from a personal and socio-political perspective (Holmes and Darwin, 2020). This exploration of the self is common practice in interpretivist studies, but it is particularly relevant in studies related to intersectionality and the exploration of identity (Bukamal, 2022). This reflective activity enables the researcher to identify any perceived positions on the parts of power, and to reflect on the possible impact their identity might have on the participants' responses and on the analysis of the data.

It is worth starting this section by acknowledging the fact that there is never an 'outsider' position from which to analyse the world (Lykke, 2010). On the contrary, the researcher is always involved and responsible for the production of knowledge and, as a consequence, subjectivity is always part of one's knowledge: "the researcher cannot give an objective depiction of the world 'out there' but produces a story, of which she or he is part" (Lykke, 2010, p. 5). In this particular study, I consider myself as an 'insider', not only because of my

¹ Italics in original.

involvement in the production of knowledge as mentioned above, but also because I am, and have been, directly involved in the English language profession in different contexts throughout all my life. This no doubt has helped to shape me as a researcher, as an educator, and as human being, and of course, it has helped to bring this thesis to life.

1.6.1 Identity dilemmas and English language education.

I was born into a Spanish-English bilingual household at a period of time when English in Spain was being taught as the first foreign language in most primary and secondary schools, with the clear aim of contributing to a multicultural and plurilingual Europe (Villacañas-de-Castro, 2017). This means that like in other EFL contexts (Gray and Block, 2014), the Spanish EFL context has been influenced by what could be considered as neoliberal ideologies and linguistic imperialism specifically in relation to language education (Phillipson, 1992; Villacañas-de-Castro, 2017), which have inevitably shaped my own perceptions of English language education, at least at the early stages of my career, where the industry demanded ‘native’ speaker teachers only, on some occasions even over qualifications or experience.

I started to learn English at home in Spain, with my Scottish mum and her family, acquiring their local accent and expressions. It was not until I started primary school in Spain that I realized that the variety of English that I was being taught in class was *different* to the one I was learning at home. At that age, I was not able to identify the reasons for this, but I was very aware that there was something *wrong* with it, and my English teacher in primary school insisted that in class, I should speak the *type* of English that I was being taught by her. That was the first time I came across the idea that, apparently, some varieties were *better* than others, or at least, that was how some people perceived it.

In my hometown in Spain, my mum had her own language school where she worked as an EFL teacher, and I used to spend a significant amount of time in her school doing my homework or playing with other children. While I was around, I could hear how my mum changed her ‘*home English*’ for her ‘*teacher English*’, which is far less Scottish, and more *standard*. This reinforced my perceptions of some varieties being *better* than others, and so at this early stage in my life, I believed this to be true.

As I grew older, I developed an interest in becoming an EFL teacher myself; so, while I was studying for my English language degree in Spain, I started to teach some English classes in different public schools. At this stage, I started to perceive that, as Llurda and Mocanu (2024, p.325) point out, “in Spain, we can find instances of native-speakerism deeply rooted in the discourses around language learning and teaching” (Llurda and Mocanu, 2024, p. 324) and native English speaker teachers seemed to be perceived as superior in the profession:

Spanish context still privileges so-called ‘native speakers’, who are endowed with an aura of magnificence, and by the same token it projects a bias against those who are perceived as ‘non-native’ speakers.

This had a significant impact on my identity and the way in which I was perceived by students and hiring managers. As a bilingual/bicultural English language teacher, I was sometimes

privileged for being ‘white, bilingual, native speaker of English’ in aspects such as job offers or *credibility*, while on other occasions, I was not perceived as *completely* British and therefore, my abilities as an English teacher were questioned.

After a few years working in the EFL sector in Spain, I moved to Scotland to continue my education and develop my career in the ELT profession. In the Scottish ESOL context, English language education is predominantly taught to migrants to support their social integration (The Scottish Government, 2007) and, therefore, the initial aim is different to the aim of EFL learners in Spain; however, the perceptions related to my own identity as a teacher seemed to be quite similar. My first experience working in ESOL in Scotland was in community settings, where some students seemed to perceive Scottish-born teachers differently to other teachers; students were able to relate to some of the experiences of the teachers who were not Scottish, which led to perceive them as ‘aspirational’ in the sense that those teachers had been able to learn English ‘successfully’, which is what these students were aiming for. However, Scottish teachers were perceived as points of reference for local expressions, and accent. In this context, I was perceived as a teacher who, like them, was a migrant, allowing them to relate to some of my experiences, while also being closely connected to Scottish culture.

While I was working as an ESOL tutor in the community, I was also studying for my MEd TESOL qualification and, as part of the course, we were introduced to the ideas of native-speakerism, language ideologies, and racism in the field of TESOL. In addition, my dissertation for this programme focused on perceptions of gender hierarchies in TESOL. These ideas resonated with my own experiences in the English language profession, both as a learner and as a teacher, and therefore, I started to develop an interest in the exploration of perceived discriminatory practices in TESOL, and the ways in which they may affect the profession. Additionally, it seemed reasonable to explore identity from a framework that enabled me to understand how different identity characteristics interplay, and the different types of power structures related to identity that existed in the context I was immersed in; I realised this framework was intersectionality.

I decided to locate this research within the college sector in Scotland as it is where the majority of ESOL classes are being delivered in Scotland (Stella and Kay, 2023). This setting not only reflects the central role colleges play in ESOL education in Scotland, but it also means that the findings from this study have the potential to influence practice and policy on a larger scale.

Initially, I approached this study from the perspective of someone who was familiar with parts of the ESOL sector in Scotland, but did not have first-hand experience in Scottish colleges particularly. However, after the data collection, and while I was working in the analysis of the data, I started to work, first, as a lecturer in Higher Education, and then, also as an ESOL lecturer in a college in Scotland. Consequently, my perspective changed significantly, from situating myself outside the ESOL college context but close to the research topic, to being fully immersed in the same context as my participants. This shift, as a consequence, came with a re-negotiation of my own identity in the research, which I will explore further in the final reflections of the thesis, and that enabled me to explore the data from a different angle. From my new insider perspective, I was able to understand the framework and the power relations that are embedded in the Further Education system in practical terms and explore my own

role and identity as a practitioner in the ESOL profession who is mainly perceived by staff and students as white, bilingual, Spanish, and heterosexual. However, my identity, as with many other people's identity, is much more complex and the way in which one's identity is perceived in a certain context is not always how we understand our own identity.

1.6.2 Perceptions of identity, power, and privilege in ELT/ESOL.

Throughout my career as an English language educator, I have mainly been perceived as a white, young, woman. On certain occasions this has put me in a situation of presumed privilege because for certain roles such as teaching younger learners, women seem to be preferred (Wright, 2024). However, in other contexts, being perceived as a *young woman* was also linked to connotations of being 'inexperienced', despite my qualifications and expertise.

This part of my identity sometimes intersected with being perceived as Spanish in a context where 'native' speakers seem to be preferred by students and, as a consequence, this had an impact on the *credibility* I had from students, compared to other teachers who were perceived as 'native'. Colleagues (both 'native', and 'non-native') have always been very supportive in such instances, however, these experiences in the classroom have no doubt influenced my practice as I have often felt the need to put in extra effort to demonstrate to students and colleagues that I *deserved* to be there.

On other occasions, the perception of my own identity has put me in a position of privilege. While working in Spain, for example, being bilingual since childhood, gave me an advantage over other teachers in terms of employment opportunities; while in Scotland, students perceived me as a migrant and someone who they could relate to. I also have experiences of being in a privileged position in the profession, particularly as an ESOL lecturer in a Scottish college, which is exactly the context of this study. For example, being perceived by staff and students as heterosexual in a field where heteronormativity is deeply embedded in the materials, curricula and pedagogies (Kaiser, 2017) gave me the power to 'hide' my bisexuality in certain contexts as I am very aware that the discussion of sexuality in the ESOL classroom "may clash with the cultural and religious sensibilities of learners" (Stella and MacDougall, 2021, p. 375) and thus exposing my own identity to this discussion, could potentially result in a negative reaction from students and influence their perception of me. At the same time, I was aware that this masking behaviour contributes to the invisibility of queer voices in ESOL (Baynham, 2021) as it helps to maintain the hegemonic structure that is currently present in the profession, as will be discussed in the following chapters.

In this section, my intention was to acknowledge my position of both privilege and disadvantage within the profession by providing relevant personal examples of how the perception of identity and how certain related discourses are perceived in the profession play an important role in the dynamic and fluid nature of power.

1.7 Conclusion

This first chapter has provided an overview of the structure of this thesis, and a reflection of the rationale and the significance of the study. In addition, it has clearly stated the research questions and aims that will guide the rest of the study. Lastly, it has offered an exploration of my positionality and my identity. Each of the chapters that follow will be dedicated to a different part of the research; the next chapter includes a discussion of the genealogy of intersectionality as well as a detailed description of the context of English language education in general, and ESOL in Scotland in particular.

Chapter 2 - Context

2.1 Introduction

The study focuses on exploring the identities of ESOL lecturers working in Scottish colleges through an intersectional lens, aiming to investigate potential discriminatory practices in the profession based on the lecturers' self-described identities. The current chapter aims to set the context in which this study is located. It starts with an exploration of the genealogy of intersectionality in order to understand the origins of the theory that serves as the theoretical framework for this research. Then, I will discuss the previous debates about discrimination in TESOL in relation to the perception of teachers' identity characteristics in the profession. This aims to offer an insight into the global situation of the profession and to explore in which ways the particular context of this study may be influenced by the global TESOL field. The chapter will continue situating English as the current global language, and providing an exploration of how this has shaped the global TESOL profession. Lastly, the chapter will contextualize ESOL education in Scotland, where the study is situated.

2.2. Intersectionality: historical background

Despite many efforts to trace its origins (Davis, 2008; Carastathis, 2016; Al-Faham, Davis and Ernst, 2019; Collins and Bilge, 2020), "intersectionality's history cannot be neatly organized in time periods or geographic locations" (Collins and Bilge, 2020, p. 72) because it does not come from a single, linear strand of history. Instead, intersectionality developed as an overarching term that emerged from the need to address the different types of oppression that Black women have been experiencing throughout history (Crenshaw, 1989; Carastathis, 2016; Collins and Bilge, 2020). Thus, I will explore the historical background of intersectionality directly through the work of key women activists who have challenged embedded power structures and social inequalities in their own fields.

The term 'intersectionality' was not coined by Crenshaw until 1989, however, it would not have been possible for Crenshaw (1989) to do so without the work of many Black Women in America who had previously raised, denounced and challenged interlocking issues of gender, racial and social oppressions in their communities (Lykke, 2010; Carastathis, 2016; Collins and Bilge, 2020). Before the term was introduced, these interlocking, or intersecting oppressions were referred to in many ways, for example as *multiple* or *simultaneous* discrimination (Sordo-Ruz, 2019), double jeopardy, or matrix of domination (Collins, 1990), and although all these concepts are not "interchangeable" (Carastathis, 2016, p. 26) because they use different approaches to explore identity and power, they all represent the need for a term that helped to address the struggles that Black women were facing at different moments in history in the United States.

2.2.1 The roots of intersectionality

The 19th Century seems to be the earliest point in history where most scholars (Carastathis, 2016; Haynes *et al.*, 2020; Collins and Bilge, 2020) note the beginnings of discussions around intersectionality, although it was not yet described as such, as explained above. As an example, in 1832, the African American Maria Stewart publicly acknowledged the double-discrimination of race and gender that Black American women were suffering at the time (Cheryl, 2006). Some years later, in 1851, Sojourner Truth delivered a speech which can be described as one of the most influential works in Black feminism (hooks, 2001; Collins, 2007; Carastathis, 2016; Haynes *et al.*, 2020; Collins and Bilge, 2020) as she was one of the first women to denounce publicly the invisibility and marginalisation that Black slave women were experiencing at the time in America. In her speech “Ain’t I a woman?” (National Park service, 2017) Truth highlighted how the perceived oppressions of race, class and gender are interwoven throughout society and leave Black American women outside socio-political spaces (Haynes *et al.*, 2020). She explained how society did not consider her as a ‘real’ woman as, to others, her perceived identity and femininity differed from those of a white woman. She also drew attention to how the abolitionist movements focused exclusively on Black men’s rights, noting how her own identity fell through the cracks² of the discourses around both women’s rights, and anti-slavery movements (Crenshaw, 1989; Haynes *et al.*, 2020). Truth’s speech and the ideas it explored were central in enabling Crenshaw (1989) to develop the intersectionality framework in 1989. In fact, they form the core of Crenshaw’s seminal paper ‘Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics’, where she asks the question “*ain’t we women*³?” (Crenshaw, 1989, p. 152) to address the place of Black feminism in America. These ideas could be understood as the beginnings of the development of what Crenshaw later named as ‘intersectionality’ (Crenshaw, 1989). Both Truth and Crenshaw focus on highlighting how the experiences of Black women are markedly different from those of Black men and white women and expose how the power structures that are interwoven in society render them invisible. As Carastathis (2016, p.16) argues, this is evidence of the “long history of struggle” that has been affecting Black women communities for centuries, and which created a real need for a term that encompassed these experiences.

In the 1960s and until the 1980s, the “core ideas” (Collins and Bilge, 2020 p.73) of intersectionality were starting to form due to the fervent social activism which aimed to tackle the ideas of colonialism, racism, heterosexism and workers’ rights in the United States at the time (ibid.). African American women activists were aware that their jobs, education, and healthcare were ‘falling through the cracks’ of the current system and that existing activist movements were not fully addressing their issues (Collins and Bilge, 2020). This developed into heterogeneous Black feminist movements and then into political organizations, not as a reaction to mainstream white feminism, but as a necessity to address the struggles that were directly affecting individuals and their communities (Carastathis, 2016). These new Black feminist movements formed by Black, indigenous, Chicana and other groups of marginalized women in America (Collins, 1990, 2015) had their own struggles within their own particular communities and differed from the focus of other types of activism. However, all these groups

² ‘To fall through the cracks’ is an expression used by Crenshaw on different occasions throughout her work (see: *The Urgency of Intersectionality*, 2016) to describe the gaps that traditional systems do not address, and to justify the need for an intersectional framework.

³ Italics in the original paper.

were united and interconnected because they understood the similarities between the oppressions (Collins and Bilge, 2020; Collins *et al.*, 2021). In this sense, intersectionality became a conversation “among disparate ideas and people” (Collins *et al.*, 2021, p. 692) that involved different political movements which, together, aimed to address traditional ‘blind spots’⁴ and question structures of power.

As these Black feminist movements started to become active, they also began to develop “intersectional sensitivities” (Collins and Bilge, 2020, p. 74) when they realized that the social movements that were active at the time, such as anti-racist movements and workers’ unions, were only focusing on one type of oppression (race, class...) and pursued “mono-categorical solutions” (Collins, 2015 p.8) that failed to address the entirety of the discrimination they were experiencing. Black women realised that they needed a different approach to challenge all the collection of oppressions which were affecting them (Collins, 1990). In this context, the first discussions of intersectionality that started to emerge provided a new analytical perspective from which it became possible to address such social matters within the same movement, enabling them to make connections and attempt to tackle the breadth of all oppressions simultaneously (Collins, 2015; Collins and Bilge, 2020).

During the 1970s and 1980s, the goal of Black feminism in the US was to empower Black women through a critical analysis of how different systems of oppression framed their realities and struggles. In order to achieve this, Black feminist activists took their activism to other discursive areas of society such as poetry, edited volumes, creative venues and community spaces (Collins, 2015; Collins and Bilge, 2020). Black Women started to use the discourse they had learned in political spaces to continue highlighting and addressing social inequalities in their own communities, which meant that these issues soon became a discussion among the wider public, and not just among political activists (Collins and Bilge, 2020). As a result, social movements led by Black women gained some power in US society, enabling these movements to transform some areas of society, including schools, healthcare, housing rights and higher education (Collins and Bilge, 2020).

However, it is important to note that intersectionality is not only rooted in Black feminism, but it also emerged from the field of Critical Race Theory (CRT) as a tool to explore issues of racial oppression in combination with gender (Carbado *et al.*, 2013; Smooth, 2013; Kayi-Aydar, Varghese and Vitanova, 2022). CRT is a “potentially fluid” (Dixson and Rousseau Anderson, 2018, p. 122) concept and, like intersectionality, it can be understood in many ways. In general terms it can be defined as a theory that addresses racism as a structural phenomenon (Dixson and Rousseau Anderson, 2018). The work of legal scholars such as Crenshaw (1989) in the 1980s was clearly rooted in CRT, but Crenshaw (1989) soon realised that there was a need for a different framework that addressed multiple oppressions simultaneously. In her 1989 paper, Crenshaw (1989) criticized CRT as a lens that only focused on the male mainstream voices of race oppression and left both non-mainstream male, and women’s voices, unnoticed, and as a result, she coined the term ‘intersectionality’, a term which will be discussed and its meaning explored in a later section of this chapter. Others such as Choo and Ferree (2010) also criticised

⁴ In her crossroads metaphor, Crenshaw, (1989) uses the concept of blind spots to illustrate how women who fall into different categories of oppression are often invisible.

CRT for its exclusive focus on race, and the way in which it fails to notice its interactions with other identity and social factors such as class, gender, or country of origin which may result in obscuring other oppressions that intersect with the characteristic of 'race'. Given their shared history, CRT and intersectionality have many commonalities, including their emphasis on social transformation and the challenge to power hierarchies and social constructs (Choo and Ferree, 2010; Kayi-Aydar, 2019; Collins and Bilge, 2020). As a result, this new intersectional discourse not only created a new perspective from which to challenge perceived structures of power in the United States but also initiated connections with other social justice movements across the world (Collins, 2015).

2.2.2 'Intersectionality' enters the academy

As Collins (2015, p.9) explained, Black feminist activism "change[d] in location but not necessarily its substance" moving from political and social spaces into the academy. One of the main criticisms aimed at universities and colleges was that traditionally, Black women were excluded from these institutions, or if they managed to enter them, they were discriminated against (Collins and Bilge, 2020). In this climate of activism, higher education institutions and colleges in the United States responded to these movements by hiring people who had been historically excluded: African Americans, Latino women, working class white women, and indigenous women. This became a key moment for intersectionality as theory and politics were starting to construct a "synergy" (Collins and Bilge, 2020, p.80) that enriched the discussions related to power and oppressions inside and outside academic institutions. Those women who were engaged in social activism were finally *inside* the institutions, working or studying in colleges and universities at different levels as students, professors, administrative staff and instructors. This enabled them to transform and shape the profession using intersectionality as a form of critical theory and praxis (Collins and Bilge, 2020). New university courses arose directly from political and social discussions related to intersectional identities, inequalities and social struggles, and developed into a field of study that was originally known as 'Race, class and gender studies'(ibid.). However, academics in this field had to fight against much criticism in order for it to be considered an area deserving of academic recognition (ibid). For this reason, the encompassing term of 'Race class and gender studies' later transformed into 'Intersectionality' as a broader term which to encompass all identity characteristics and enabled academics to establish a common framework from which to develop and expand the field. From this moment, intersectionality was considered a field of study, an analytical lens, and a political movement (Davis, 2008; Collins, 2015; Collins and Bilge, 2020).

2.3 Kimberlé Crenshaw's intersectionality

As a result of decades of Black feminist activism fighting to address intersecting systems of oppressions within different communities (for example African American, Indigenous and Latino women), each with their own struggles but supporting each other to attempt to make transformative changes in society, Crenshaw (1989) finally coined the term 'intersectionality' as an umbrella term to describe the framework from which to explore the struggles of those who are "multiply burdened"(Crenshaw, 1989, p. 140). Crenshaw's (1989) seminal paper

mentioned above 'Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics' is situated in the American court system and highlights how the American legal system uses a single-axis approach that does not fully address the experiences of many Black American women. This perspective considers gender and race as two mutually exclusive categories and each of which focuses only on the experiences of the "most privileged group members" (ibid.p.140). For example, in the case of gender discrimination, it focuses mainly on white, middle-class women, in the case of race, only on black men. This means that any other subgroups are ignored, and Black women are "theoretically erased" (Crenshaw, 1989, p.139).

In order to address the issue of the single-axis approach, Crenshaw developed the Intersectionality framework that understands and posits identity categories not as mutually exclusive, but rather as interacting with one another creating complex experiences. Crenshaw believed that by shifting from a single-axis approach to an intersectional framework, new forms of oppression that have been traditionally overlooked would be made visible:

Without frames that allow us to see how social problems impact all members of a targeted group, many will fall through the cracks of our movements, left to suffer in virtual isolation (The Urgency of Intersectionality, 2016, min. 4:21).

It is important to note that Crenshaw's intersectionality framework does not suggest *just* exploring different forms of discrimination simultaneously but finding how they operate together creating a new layer of oppression (Crenshaw, 2016, Sordo-Ruz, 2019). In order to understand this, Levon (2015) offers an insightful explanation of the term:

The difference between an interaction and an intersection is that in the case of the former, there is a necessary assumption of independence between the categories in question (Levon, 2015, p. 298).

Since it was coined, the term has "traveled from its original context" (Carastathis, 2016, p. 69) of political intervention in the United States, to different fields of study and geographical locations. It has evolved and developed globally and "[...] is very much in use these days, but is employed in a variety of ways by different social actors" (Collins and Bilge, 2020, p. 220). It has a place in many fields such as education (Leckie and Buser De, 2020), health (Lett, Dowshen and Baker, 2020), and social policy (APS Group Scotland, 2022) as a lens through which to examine power, oppression, and perceptions of privilege, not only to explore challenges related to class, gender and race but also to focus on related intersecting identity factors such as disabilities, sexual orientation, religion, nation, age, ethnicity and other identity categories (Carbado *et al.*, 2013; Collins *et al.*, 2021). However, Carastathis (2016) denounces how there is a lack of engagement with the term that can lead to an unintentional distortion of Crenshaw's framework. In order to avoid this, and help scholars to engage critically with the framework, she suggests a close reading of Crenshaw's metaphors of intersectionality as discussed below.

2.3.1 Crenshaw's metaphors of intersectionality

The first metaphor that I will explore in this section (although the second one provided by Crenshaw) is the metaphor of the basement which is presented in 'Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist theory and Antiracist Politics' (Crenshaw, 1989). This metaphor has been used extensively in intersectional scholarship (Haynes *et al.*, 2020; Collins and Bilge, 2020) to provide a visual image of the framework. It reads as follows:

Imagine a basement which contains all people who are disadvantaged on the basis of race, sex, class, sexual preference, age and/or physical ability. These people are stacked-feet standing on shoulders-with those on the bottom being disadvantaged by the full array of factors, up to the very top, where the heads of all those disadvantaged by a singular factor brush up against the ceiling. Their ceiling is actually the floor above which only those who are *not* disadvantaged in any way reside. In efforts to correct some aspects of domination, those above the ceiling admit from the basement only those who can say that "but for" the ceiling, they too would be in the upper room. A hatch is developed through which those placed immediately below can crawl. Yet this hatch is generally available only to those who, due to the singularity of their burden and their otherwise privileged position relative to those below, are in the position to crawl through. Those who are multiply-burdened are generally left below unless they can somehow pull themselves into the groups that are permitted to squeeze through the hatch (Crenshaw, 1989, pp. 151–152).

This metaphor represents a hierarchical society, with clear relations of power. The more 'disadvantaged factors' one has, the lower they are in the basement. However, as Carastathis (2016, p. 73) highlights, the metaphor also shows that those who are at the bottom have a "revolutionary potential" to liberate others. The emancipation of the people at the bottom of the basement means that all other groups are also free, which suggests the power of self-emancipation (*ibid.*).

In the second metaphor, the representation of intersectionality as a crossroad is used to problematize the single-axis approach that was used in the American court system and that I have illustrated in the previous section:

Consider an analogy to traffic in an intersection, coming and going in all four directions. Discrimination, like traffic through an intersection, may flow in one direction, and it may flow in another. If an accident happens in an intersection, it can be caused by cars traveling from any number of directions and, sometimes, from all of them. Similarly, if a Black woman is harmed because she is in the intersection, her injury could result from sex discrimination or race discrimination (Crenshaw, 1989, p. 149).

One of the main differences in the way the two metaphors are represented is that in the basement metaphor, there is a clear hierarchy within the oppressed. Those who are affected by one factor seem to be higher or 'less oppressed' than those who are affected by many factors, who are positioned at the bottom of the basement (Carastathis, 2016). This hierarchical view of oppressions does not consider individual contexts; for example, certain

type of oppressions may be more problematic in one context than in another which would imply that two individuals affected by the same number of factors may be positioned at different levels in the basement as one would be more disadvantaged than another, or even play different roles at a time, as Collins (1990, p. 556) puts it:

Depending on the context, an individual may be an oppressor, a member of an oppressed group, or simultaneously oppressor and oppressed.

The basement metaphor, therefore, was created as a way to provide a visual representation of the American court system at the time, and although it has been useful to explain the specific issue that Crenshaw was aiming to describe, it is not a perfect representation of intersectionality as a whole (Crenshaw, 1991). In contrast, the crossroads metaphor puts all the oppressions at the same level, emphasizes the connection between all of them, and brings to the fore the uniqueness of individual experiences which depend on personal and contextual circumstances. To continue with the same metaphor, the injury from the car accident will be unique for each individual depending on how many cars are involved, the speed, or the place of the collision.

One of the major criticisms of this metaphor (Dhamoon, 2011; Rodó-Zárate and Jorba, 2022) is that it does not capture the dynamic and interconnected nature of intersections, in the sense that each oppression cannot be understood independently from the others. The metaphor seems to suggest an additive model of oppressions, rather than representing oppressions that “mutually constitute each other” (Carbado *et al.*, 2013, p. 307). Another criticism of this representation of intersectionality is that it does not fully capture the dynamic nature of power (Dhamoon, 2011). While the basement metaphor does represent the possibility of moving up and down the basement, the crossroads are represented as fixed, implying that an individual is always affected by the same factors, and that this situation cannot be altered.

Despite their drawbacks both metaphors have been useful to describe intersectionality in different ways; while the basement metaphor is helpful to provide a visual representation of how oppressions relate to an overarching system of power, the crossroads metaphor represents oppression at the level of the individual. However, neither of them fully captures all the nuances of intersectionality and how the relationship between different identity factors may vary depending on the context (Crenshaw, 1991; Dhamoon, 2011; Carastathis, 2016). Indeed, Dhamoon (2011) argues that despite being useful at times, these metaphors might limit our ability to analyse power relations and identity categories.

Understanding these metaphors and the way in which Crenshaw conceptualises intersectionality have been key to developing the theoretical framework of this study which is explored in chapter 4. The basement metaphor enabled me to understand the dynamic nature of the inequality experienced by ESOL lecturers working in the Scottish FE sector, not only within their own departments but at an institutional level; this metaphor is useful in this particular context to illustrate how ESOL lecturers’ identities are not static or one-dimensional but are constantly negotiated within the intersecting power dynamics which exist at departmental and institutional level. However, as will be explored in chapter 4, in this study identity characteristics are understood from a non-hierarchical approach. Therefore, this

metaphor has been complemented by the crossroads metaphor which offers an opportunity to focus on the specific circumstances of each participant and to reflect on their individual experiences in the profession. In this sense, the crossroads metaphor has been helpful to understand how different identity characteristics and the way they are perceived in the profession affect individuals in different ways creating situations of privilege and disadvantage. However, it is worth noting that, as I will explore in chapter 4, this study understands power relations as dynamic which cannot be adequately captured by the crossroad metaphor, and for that, Hill Collins conceptualization of identity characteristics has been called upon.

2.4 Patricia Hill Collins and the matrix of domination

Although Crenshaw (1989) coined the term 'Intersectionality', Collins (1990) is also considered as one of the "mothers of Intersectionality" (Freeman, 2019, p. 4) and therefore, her work needs to be discussed in this chapter.

Both Crenshaw (1989) and Collins (1990) reject a single-axis approach to studying discrimination and suggest models that explore different sources of oppression simultaneously. The main difference is the way in which they conceptualise oppressions. As I explored in the previous section, Crenshaw's crossroad metaphor represents oppressions as additive; on the contrary, Collins (1990, p. 554) proposes "a paradigm shift that rejects additive approaches to oppressions" in favour of an analysis that focuses on how the different variables interconnect, or interlock. For Collins, there is no one source of oppression from which to start the analysis, to which other types of oppression would be added. For her, all types of oppression are understood under "one overarching structure of domination" (Collins, 1990, p. 554).

In her view, additive models are limiting as they are "firmly rooted" (Collins, 1990, p. 556) in dichotomous views that come from "Eurocentric, masculinist thought" (ibid.). In this sense one must be, for example, either white or non-white, male or female, and it does not allow people outside these parameters to 'exist' as they do not fit into this model. Therefore, she suggests a new paradigm that focuses on how the different factors interlock, and that will enable the "creat[ion of] possibilities for new paradigms" (ibid.) and focus on other types of oppressions outside gender and race such as class, sexual orientation, age, or religion that affect all groups that have been labelled as 'The Other' throughout history.

It is also worth exploring the way in which Collins (2000) conceptualises identity variables in a non-hierarchical way. In her view, all identity factors should be considered at the same level and there is no one single factor of identity that should be considered as more important than another in the analysis as they all belong to the same matrix of oppressions. In the present study Collins' (2000) approach helped me to understand how identity variables interplay and mutually shape each other. Using this flexible approach, I was able to observe and explore how identity variables interconnected in the participants' experiences without imposing preconceived notions about the relationship between different identity characteristics. As a result, I was able to identify and explore new intersections in the ways that power functions within the ESOL college sector.

2.5 Previous debates on discrimination in TESOL

In the context of ESOL, any literature surrounding discriminatory practices is limited. Therefore, this section will situate the field of ESOL and any related discrimination within the broader global TESOL context in order to explore common discriminatory practices that may occur in different contexts where English is taught as a foreign (EFL) or additional (EAL) language. Many scholars in the field have acknowledged that discrimination in TESOL is an “extensive phenomenon” (Basurto-Santos and Sánchez-Menéndez, 2018, p. 34) that is “alive and well” (Jenkins, 2017, p. 374) and that is experienced by teachers both inside and outside the workplace (Varghese *et al.*, 2005). Hume (2013) believes that the first step to overcome any situation of oppression or discrimination in a particular society should be its acknowledgement; therefore, discrimination in ELT has been at the centre of many research papers from the last decades. As a result, this issue has been examined from a variety of perspectives, such as hiring practices (Selvi, 2010; Jenkins, 2017; Tatar, 2019), job advertisements (Mahboob and Golden, 2013; Ruecker and Ives, 2015), textbooks and classroom materials (Ansary and Babaii, 2003; Nelson, 2019), and identity (Varghese *et al.*, 2005; Kubota and Lin, 2006; Glodjo, 2017). This body of work has helped to identify common discriminatory practices that occur in the TESOL field related to different identity characteristics such as gender (Florent and Walter, 1989; Davis and Skilton-Sylvester, 2004; Norton and Pavlenko, 2004; Alansari, 2022), ethnicity (Kubota and Lin, 2006), class (Gray and Block, 2014; Vandrlick, 2014; Glodjo, 2017), and sexuality (Hume, 2013; Gray and Cooke, 2019).

In the field of TESOL, women educators seem to be more prevalent than men, yet a smaller percentage of women hold positions of power and influence in the profession (Florent and Walter, 1989, Where are the Women in ELT?, 2015, Norton, 2019), which has resulted in a significant gender gap that has impacted the field in many ways. In terms of the production of the most influential language learning theories, it seems that “female theorists were less visible than male theorists, despite the predominance of female scholars in our field” (Norton, 2019 p.301). In addition, the presence and visibility of women as conference speakers appears to be less common than that of men, although it seems to be gradually shifting towards a more equal balance between men and women (Prentis and Mayne, 2015) thanks to the work of certain organizations that work to promote equality in the profession (see: Mayne and Prentis, no date). It is worth noting that the analysis of the literature understands women as a homogeneous group where all the people represented in this category share a feature of identity and does not consider differences among women. However, studies that employ an intersectional framework understand women as a heterogeneous group which varies in age, ethnicity, sexual orientation, professional experience, and mother tongue among other factors acknowledging that the experiences and representation of women in a particular society can vary according to the combination of their identity factors and their perception in that community (Collins and Bilge, 2020).

In a similar way, the profession has been described as a promoter of heteronormativity and middle class western-centred ideology that undervalues people who do not fit into these categories (Hume, 2013, Glodjo, 2017). In addition, it has been noted that the profession seems to favour teachers who are white, leaving people of colour at a disadvantage with

regard to employment (Ruecker and Ives, 2015). This debate is very often linked to the native/nonnative English speaker dichotomy, wherein whiteness is not only associated with provenance but also with having a particular accent that recruiters seem to favour (Ruecker and Ives, 2015; Richardson, 2016). In TESOL, having the 'native speaker' label has been considered, in many cases, an advantage as many job offers openly state that teaching qualifications are not needed because first language speakers of English are often perceived as language experts (Llurda, 2015). However, this 'native speaker' label is not just a matter of accent or English variety; it has traditionally been associated with other identity variables such as ethnicity, class and nationality (Ruecker & Ives, 2014). Scholars such as Holliday (2018) and Jenkins (2017), however, have criticized the extensive focus given to this dichotomy as it oversimplifies the complex and multifaceted identity of TESOL teachers and labels members of the profession into fixed groups, which, according to Holliday (2017) are just a social construct "underpinned by an ideology" (n.p) that describes people who are "[labelled] as 'non-native speakers' as culturally deficient" (n.p). It is also worth noting that, although this preference for 'native' speakers is extended throughout the profession it seems to be reinforced in a stronger manner in outer-circle contexts by non-white NNESTs (ibid.)

The different forms of perceived privilege and exclusion with reference to specific identity variables seem to be shaping the profession in a way that constructs the 'ideal' English language teacher as "young, white, enthusiastic native-speaker of English from a very stable list of inner-circle countries" (Ruecker & Ives, 2014 p.733). This ideology seems to favour teachers who fit into this homogeneous and narrow profile based on identity characteristics, rather than competent professionals with relevant qualifications and professional experience (Ruecker & Ives, 2014). From an intersectional approach, in a global profession such as TESOL this should be challenged in order to promote the multiple and dynamic identities of TESOL professionals and achieve equal opportunities for all teachers regardless of how their identity is perceived.

Employing an intersectional approach to explore, specifically, the identity of lecturers and the dynamics of power to which they are subject in college ESOL departments in Scotland can be a tool to identify any perceived discriminatory practices in this sector. This can serve to challenge current perceptions related to ESOL lecturer identities in Scotland, as distinct to the global TESOL context. In addition, it can contribute to foster a more inclusive profession that aligns with policies such as the Equality Act (2010) which aim to promote equality and fairness throughout Scotland.

2.6 The spread of English and TESOL as a global profession. What does 'English as a Global Language' really mean?

This question was previously explored by Crystal (2003) who explains that for a language to have a global status it does not necessarily need to be spoken by every single person in the world or be recognized as the official language in every country, but rather the language should have a special status around the globe. He explains that this special status does not depend on the number of L1 speakers of a language, but in the way in which the language is used around the world. It can be used, in some countries, as the language for official communication in areas such as politics, education, science and media; in others, it can be

recognized as the second official language or the first option in foreign language learning in schools. In short, the global status of a language has very little to do with the number of L1 speakers of English, but rather with the power of those speakers:

Language has no independence existence [...]. Language exists only in the brains and mouths and ears and hands and eyes of its users. When they succeed, on the international stage, their language succeeds. When they fail, their language fails (Crystal, 2003, p. 7).

English has certainly obtained the global status in the last decades as “there has never been in the past a language spoken more widely in the world than English is today” (Melitz, 2016, p. 583); it is used for political international communication, education, and science. According to the data discussed by Melitz (2016), Chinese is the language with the highest number of speakers; however, English is the language with more ‘nonnative’ than ‘native’ speakers, that is more L2 than L1 speakers, and is the only language that is spread all over the five continents, although the use of English in all areas is not standard, nor unified across the world. The global spread of English was aided by those who saw an interest in promoting the English language and also by those who also found value in learning and acquiring the language (Pennycook, 2020). Such perceived value can be attributed to the impact of colonial exploitation, or contemporary needs promoted by neoliberalism and the discourses of globalization (Brown, 2020; Pennycook, 2020) such as trade, popular culture, travel, technology, communication and religion (Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Melitz, 2016; Pennycook, 2020).

In some contexts, such as communication in airline control towers or between sea vessels where communication needs to be fast and efficient, the use of translators can cost lives. Therefore, in order to pursue a faster way of communication in these contexts, there are forms of English such as ‘airspeak’ which has been adopted by over one hundred and eighty countries following the recommendations of the International Civil Aviation Organization whereas ‘seaspeak’ is used by the International Marine Organization (Melitz, 2016). On other occasions, although the use of translators does not seem to put anyone at risk, it can be prohibitively expensive for some international organizations which have a large number of members who speak different languages. For example, large international political organizations tend to use only a limited number of languages, English being, in most cases, the preferred language (ibid.). In private international organizations, information about their working languages is less accessible, but Crystal (2003) estimated that in 1995-1996, 85% of these organizations used English as the language for communication, and in European contexts the number rises to 99% of the organizations. However, as discussed earlier, English has not just one single variety; these changes depending on its users and their needs; Llorca (2004 p.316) terms as “Euro-English” the variety of English used for international communication within the European countries in order to differentiate it from those spoken in the United Kingdom or other dominant English-speaking countries.

Just as in international trade and politics, in science there has also been an increased use of the English language, especially after the end of World War II (Graddol, 2000). Nowadays, most scholars choose to publish their work in English rather than in their own language in

order to have international recognition and make their work available to a broader audience (Sekhar Rao, 2018).

In education, English language has, too, that special status described by Crystal (2003). It is, of course, a requirement for international students choosing to study university courses in anglophone countries to have a certain level of English, but even universities in countries where English is not the first language expect students to have certain command of the language. As an example, Universitat de Barcelona (n.d.) in Spain, states that the final honours degree dissertation can be entirely in English or, that at least students should provide a summary in English:

Cada centro define cómo debe ser el trabajo de fin de grado; en algún caso se puede exigir que esté redactado íntegramente en inglés y que la exposición oral sea también en esta lengua. En todos los casos, sin embargo, es obligatorio un resumen escrito en lengua inglesa (*Universitat de Barcelona: Exigencias y requisitos lingüísticos.*, no date).

Each school sets the rules for the final dissertation; in some cases, students may be required to write it and present it orally entirely in English. In all cases, however, all students are required to submit a written summary of their dissertation in English. [Own translation]

In addition, English is being taught as one of the major foreign languages in many bilingual programmes in schools across the globe as parents have an interest in preparing their children for a “context of growing globalization, internationalism, global trade, multinational corporations, and transnational employment” (Wright and Baker, 2017, p. 6).

These situations exemplify the special status of English as a global language as it is, in many cases, the preferred language of communication in international contexts all over the world. In 2004, Llorca proposed the term ‘English as an International language’ to describe the new varieties of English that emerged from the usage of the language internationally, highlighting the difference between this and the regional varieties spoken in anglophone contexts. Likewise, the global spread of English has also led to a discussion about the ownership of English, as some scholars believe that English should be owned and changed by all its users, not only by ‘native speakers’, as explained by Lin (2006) in this extract:

English should not be exclusively owned by the English-speaking British, Americans, Australians or Canadians. English in its many diverse ways, in its many rich accents, should be accessible and should belong to anyone who wants it. English should also allow itself to be enriched, expanded, and hybridized by people living in different parts of the world. (Lin, 2006 p.78)

Norton (1997) explains that the beliefs about the discussion around ownership of English may affect the learners’ identity in the classroom and, as a consequence, their language development; if learners perceive that English language does not belong to them as much as it belongs to the ‘native’ speakers, they may feel less confident in using the language as they may never get to own it. This shows the need for teachers to understand the value of all

English language teachers, regardless of their L1, as it these ideas may be reflected in the students, and as a consequence, impact their identity.

The need for international communication has resulted in an exponential increase in the demand to learn English over the last years (The British Council, 2013; Alansari, 2022) and “globalization is seen as a driver for the boom in the ELT industry” (Alansari, 2022, p. 143). This has consequently led to a growth in the demand for English language teachers and has affected the TESOL profession in many ways. English language courses are now delivered all over the world in a variety of formats such as online, face to face and as blended learning, to different group sizes or individuals in order to fulfil the different demands of the learners (ibid.). In addition, it has put in contact people of different cultures which has intensified the need to adapt the profession to become more culturally sensitive, and aware of the different social relationships than can develop within the classroom context and beyond (Norton, 1997, Llurda, 2004, Kumaravadivelu, 2006, Yurtsever and Özel, 2021). As the profession diversifies, and the number of English learners with very different language needs, and diverse backgrounds increases, the teaching body should also become more diverse in order to meet the profession’s evolving demands. Many scholars (Norton, 1997; Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Winchester, 2013; Alansari, 2022) have argued how, in certain contexts, culture and values are transmitted through language, and therefore, when teaching English language there are certain values and cultural aspects that are often associated with the language. For this reason, having a diverse teaching body will prevent the language and the ELT profession from being influenced by only a narrow profile of teachers, and will help the profession to adapt to the multiple backgrounds of English learners, not only culturally and socially (Norton, 1997), but in all their identity dimensions.

This section has placed the TESOL profession and the status of the English language into context in order to provide a description of the current situation at a global level. However, ESOL education in Scotland is a particular area and aims to fulfil a specific function for the nation and for its learners. Therefore, the following section will be dedicated to a discussion of the context of ESOL education in Scotland.

2.7 ESOL education in Scotland.

English for Speakers of Other Languages (ESOL) is the term used to describe English language education for people who are migrants to “English-dominant countries” (Simpson, 2020, p. 177). This branch of TESOL is, perhaps, the one with “the closest link to the consequences of migration and globalization processes” (ibid., p.179). The current focus of ESOL education is to provide linguistic support for migrants’ social and economic integration in the host community enabling them to participate fully in the new community and offering language progression to different routes to work and study (Highton *et al.*, 2019). For this *integration* to occur successfully, migrants not only need to be proficient in the dominant language of the host country, which in Scotland is English, they also need to “learn about [its] existing structures, systems and institutions” (Brown, 2021, p. 868) with the support of the host country. For this reason, some ESOL providers in the UK offer other cultural activities alongside

their English language provision, for example, discussions on British culture, visiting the local library or understanding the local public transport (Highton *et al.*, 2019). In order to be *included*, newcomers to an English-dominant country have the right to have access to English language education, and the host country should ensure that everyone can enter those courses, and that there is progression beyond those courses. However, on some occasions, migrants may find obstacles in accessing those ESOL courses, often due to the long waiting lists (Highton *et al.*, 2019, Simpson, 2020).

The policy for ESOL courses related to funding, the structure of the courses, and the selection of eligible students depends on each country (Simpson, 2020), therefore, this section will be located within the Scottish context and cannot be generalized to other countries which are regulated by different ESOL policies. Education Scotland (n.d. n.p.) is “a Scottish Government executive agency charged with supporting quality and improvement in Scottish education” and is responsible for ESOL policies, providing support and implementing the National ESOL Strategy (The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015). As Allan (2015) points out, the research done around ESOL education in the Scottish context is limited, and she suggests consulting studies framed within the English ESOL context for guidance, such as the work done by Cooke and Simpson (2010). However, while the English ESOL context “[shares] much with the Scottish experience, [it] fails to connect with the issue of the relations of governance and power, perceived or otherwise, within this specific context” (Allan, 2015, p. 19). Therefore, as this study is contextualized within the Scottish framework, it seems pertinent to dedicate this section to describing and explaining how ESOL education is implemented in Scotland.

The 2019 GLIMER study undertaken by Meer, Peace and Hill (2019) provides a detailed analysis of the differences between ESOL in the UK, with a focus on the English context, and in the Scottish context. Firstly, it is explained that the governance of ESOL in the United Kingdom belongs to the Education brief of each nation, which means that the Scottish regulations for ESOL education in terms of delivery, governance and policy differ from those for England and the other nations within the UK. However, the powers concerning immigration, security and border remain subjected to the UK legislation (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019). With regard to the funding provided for the delivery of ESOL classes, Scotland seems to be better funded than England, as the funding for Scotland has “remained consistent since 2012” (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019 p.6). In the Further Education context in particular, each college in Scotland gets an amount of funding allocated by the Scottish Further and Higher Education Funding Council (SFC) and it is the responsibility of each individual college to decide how much of it goes directly into ESOL provision (Stella and Kay, 2023). In addition, asylum seekers, refugees or EU migrants to Scotland have free access to ESOL classes from the first day they enter the country, while in England they have to be residents of the UK for six months before having access to ESOL education, at which point they need to pay half of their fees for ESOL tuition (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019).

Since the 1970s, when ESOL in Scotland was just delivered in community-based contexts, the demand for ESOL classes has significantly increased. As a result, apart from these community ESOL classes, Further Education institutions have been offering accredited ESOL courses for over 30 years (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019). In addition, during the last two decades, the Scottish framework for ESOL education has been in constant development aiming to adapt to

the changing situations that the country has been facing in terms of migration and its associated language needs.

Two main migratory events marked the beginning of a demographic change in Scotland which directly impacted ESOL education policies: in 1999 asylum seekers and refugees were distributed around the Scottish central belt; five years later, in 2004, Scotland welcomed new migrants from Eastern Europe after new countries accessed the European Union (Allan, 2015; Brown, 2017). These among other factors aroused concern about equal opportunities for employment in Scottish colleges and highlighted the urge to provide an inclusive education for all learners, taking into account the language needs of migrant learners (ibid.). The 2004 events had a clear impact on the ESOL provision in Glasgow, where “college and community ESOL providers increased their capacity, and new community and third sector ESOL providers appeared in the city” (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019 p.7). This increased demand for ESOL classes in Glasgow was also reflected in the rest of Scotland, and as a consequence, the Scottish government provided more funding for ESOL provision across the country (Brown, 2017). Finally, in 2007, ‘The Adult ESOL strategy for Scotland’ (The Scottish Government, 2007) was the first government policy “to influence directly ESOL learning and teaching in Scotland” (Allan, 2015, p. 30). This policy and the additional funding provided for ESOL in Scotland implied that the quality and quantity of ESOL provision improved (Stella and Kay, 2023). More recently, The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland (2015) published a new ESOL strategy which acknowledged that the delivery of ESOL education is a “key factor to the successful integration of those coming to live in Scotland” (p.4), aspiring to support the language and communication skills of people whose first language is not English in order to allow them to “contribute [...] economically, culturally and socially” (ibid. p.4) in society. This ESOL policy focused on second language development, but also encouraged students to critically engage with current power structures to positively transform Scottish society (Brown, 2017). The intention of this policy was to help ESOL learners to become more prepared to fully participate in all aspects of society (Brown, 2017). However, Brown (2017) argues that the implementation of the Adult ESOL strategy in the FE sector seems to clash with the policies which are at the heart of the Developing the Young Workforce (DYW) (The Scottish Government, 2014) document which focuses on the development of practical skills in the FE sector, that, though well-intentioned, ultimately lead to employability among young people (Brown, 2017). At the same time, there was a change in the funding allocation for ESOL that prioritized accredited courses over non-accredited courses (Stella and Kay, 2023). In this climate, the challenge for ESOL curriculum managers working in Scottish colleges was to find a practical way to negotiate the Adult ESOL strategy and the aims proposed by DYW document; as a consequence of this, there was an increase in the number of ESOL accredited courses, and more full-time ESOL courses offered by the FE sector in Scotland (Brown, 2017).

At the moment, ESOL provision in Scotland is offered either in community settings, delivered by local authorities or third sector organisations, or in Further Education institution, where the majority of ESOL delivery takes place in Scotland. Generally speaking, non-accredited classes for lower levels are offered in community settings, while colleges offer accredited courses that lead to SQA qualifications and facilitate progression to further studies or

employment (Stella and Kay, 2023). Scottish colleges deliver courses ranging from SCQF level 2 to level 6, as well as other courses on ESOL for Employability at SCQF levels 4 and 5 (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019; Stella and Kay, 2023). However, on some occasions colleges also offer non-accredited classes, and community providers have recently started offering accredited courses (Stella and Kay, 2023). In certain instances, ESOL learners can attend other courses that help them develop other skills that are required for certain types of employment, for example ICT or Problem solving (Education Scotland, 2016). This has proven to have a positive impact on children, young people and adults, enabling them to build social relationships, have access to learning in other fields outside ESOL and have broader employment opportunities (Allan, 2015; Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019; Education Scotland, 2023). According to Brown (2019), however, the fact that most ESOL classes are provided by the Scottish FE sector which is bound by the focus on practical skills and employability as promoted by DWY, may hinder the fulfilment of the emancipatory goals of the Adult ESOL strategy. In his study, Brown (2019) discusses the focus on ESOL accredited courses, and the little autonomy practitioners and learners have to influence the curriculum as the main limiting factors for learner emancipation.

The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland (2015, p. 6), explain the importance of developing English language skills as follows:

These language skills are central to giving people a democratic voice and supporting them to contribute to the society in which they live.

However, Allan's (2015) analysis of the discourse of these policies suggests that despite the Scottish government's intentions to design an inclusive policy for all teachers and learners, the 2007 policy does not seem to take completely into account the unique circumstances of migrant students in Scotland.

The ESOL context in Scotland has significantly changed since the launch of the first ESOL policy in 2007; the demand for ESOL classes has grown considerably due to an increased number of people coming from non-English speaking countries (The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015). According to The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland (2015), the largest number of people from European countries come from Poland, Germany, France and Spain, although this may be different now as in 2023, nearly 23,000 people from Ukraine arrived in Scotland, fleeing the war (Scottish Refugee Council, 2023). The largest number of migrants from outside Europe come from China, India and Pakistan. This implies that the ESOL learners are not only very varied in age and level of education, but also come from very different backgrounds: some are refugees, asylum seekers or migrants looking to work or study in the country (ibid.); however, it seems that in the FE context, most ESOL learners are European and white (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019). This diversity in the students' backgrounds implies that their reasons for learning English vary from person to person. According to The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland (2015), some of the most common reasons for ESOL learners to learn English is to reduce their isolation, to find opportunities for employment, and to be able to communicate effectively within their communities. For beginner ESOL learners, there is an additional reason to learn English: the need to be independent in the host country. Some of those students are dependent on interpreters,

friends or their own children to help them with medical encounters or other endeavours, therefore learning the language will give them more freedom and independency in their lives (Simpson, 2020). This diversity in ESOL learners should be taken into account by their teachers who should tailor their pedagogy to such specific learners, considering techniques such as translanguaging that take into account the multilingual context of the students (Simpson, 2020). These considerations seem vital in contributing to the learners' engagement with the language inside and outside of the classroom and facilitating English communication and social integration of the learner in the host country (Norton, 1997, Simpson, 2020).

In 2021, the Scottish government announced plans to incorporate ESOL education within a wider adult learning strategy, dismissing the Adult ESOL strategy that was introduced in 2007 (Brown and Sheridan, 2024). According to the results provided in Brown and Sheridan's (2024) study, most ESOL practitioners consulted seem to believe that this would have negative effects for Scottish ESOL education, as it would fail to take into account the particular needs of ESOL learners in Scotland. While some of their participants acknowledged that the Adult ESOL policy had its flaws, they agreed that this strategy was useful in raising the profile of ESOL education in Scotland, and gave the sector a sense of purpose, direction and worth (ibid). This incorporation of ESOL into the wider Adult Learning strategy, however, is likely to have a significant impact on the future of ESOL education in Scotland. Stella and Kay (2023) highlight that subsuming the ESOL policy into a broader Adult Learning strategy might reduce the prominence of ESOL education in Scotland at policy level, and raise concerns over the possible underrepresentation of the needs of ESOL learners in Scotland.

This section has explored the nature of ESOL in Scotland, the variety of learners and the different strategies that underpin ESOL education and the FE sector. This has allowed me to further explore and understand the place of ESOL in Scotland and the in the FE sector in particular.

2.8 Conclusion

Carastathis (2016) states that engaging with the political origins of intersectionality is essential for anyone who would like to engage in intersectional studies in order to avoid misusing the term. Therefore, it seemed pertinent to start the contextualization of this study by situating intersectionality in its political origins. I will explore how it has been operationalised in this study in chapter 4.

In addition, the chapter has offered a summary of the major debates about discriminatory practices in TESOL in relation to the way teacher identity characteristics are perceived in the profession. This was followed by a discussion of the status of English as a global language and its impact on the TESOL profession as a whole. Lastly, the chapter has provided an overview of the current context of ESOL education in Scotland in relation to the type of settings where ESOL is delivered and has highted the development of the sector throughout the years. This is essential to understand the participants' discussions around ESOL lecturer identities that will be presented in chapters 6 and 7. In addition, this chapter has introduced some of the key ideas that will be discussed in the following chapter.

Chapter 3 - Literature Review

3.1 Introduction

This review of the literature focuses on four key areas which are related to the study of lecturers' identity and intersectional discriminatory practices within the field of ELT and more specifically, ESOL education in Scotland. The first section in this chapter discusses power and the way in which it helps to shape certain relationships. This topic rightly underpins the study, and therefore, it has been placed at the beginning. Then, I introduce the literature around language teacher identity, which helps to understand how the way in which language teachers negotiate their identity affect the learning environment. Then, I explore the discussions around perceived discriminatory practices in the global TESOL context, to finalise the chapter discussing the uniqueness of ESOL education and its perceived power structures and mechanisms. Together, all the different sections of this chapter aim to situate this study within the existing literature and help to support the findings presented in chapters 6 and 7.

3.2 Power

Pennycook (2020, p. 26) claims "that English language teaching is inextricably bound up with multiple power relationships". Others such as Smooth (2013) and Collins (2015) believe that understanding power relations and inequality is key to understand research on intersectionality; thus, it seems reasonable to start this first section reviewing the literature around issues of power in general and how these power relations are reproduced within the global TESOL context, generating inequalities and issues of discrimination in the profession. This would help to set a starting point to explore power relations in Scottish ESOL education in the college sector.

Power cannot be seen as fixed, nor unidirectional; instead, it is dynamic, shifting and bound to change over time (Smooth, 2013; Appleby, 2016). The context dictates who is privileged and who is marginalised at any given time; these power relations change through time and geographic location (ibid.); if the context changes, the power relations in the society might also change. Collins and Bilge (2020, p.225) describe power "as a relationship rather than a static entity", which is able to change depending on how these relationships are created and reproduced; this implies that individuals can be both privileged and oppressed at the same time depending on different variables and contexts, and the subject position that they occupy (Fairclough, 1989). For example, in the case of TESOL teachers, a white western woman can potentially be considered privileged in the profession for being white and sharing the western values but can be potentially unwittingly discriminated against because of her gender. In addition, not all individuals or institutions are aware of their position of advantage or disadvantage and in what ways they are benefiting or being negatively affected by the current structural system (ibid.). Therefore, research on privilege and discrimination should be conscious and careful in not blaming outright the oppressor group for any imbalance of power, which they may not be aware of.

3.2.1 Foucault: mechanisms of power

In order to explore the effects and mechanisms of power and its relationship to knowledge and education, I will start this section by exploring the work of Foucault through the lenses of different scholars. According to Powell (2015, p.403) the Foucauldian understanding of the relationship between power and knowledge is that “knowledge shapes what action is possible and what power is exercised, those actions also shape the creation of new knowledge and what is thereby given credence”. Therefore, there is a mutual support between power and knowledge that works as a “productive network” (Foucault and Gordon, 1980, p.119) influencing and reproducing what is considered to be ‘the Truth’. This means that certain professional discourses that are considered powerful and rooted in knowledge have the potential to shape and define the profession in a particular way; people who hold influential roles in a particular field may be able to shape certain areas of a profession through their discourse. In TESOL, this discourse may affect aspects such as hiring practices, teaching content, classroom practices, and classroom materials. This is clearly elucidated in the work of Allan (2015), who explains how in the Scottish College ESOL context, lecturers have to shape their professional and classroom practices negotiating the rules that are set within their own context:

All the staff within a college setting have to negotiate, and perhaps even accede to, overt and covert rules, discourses of both the classroom and of the college itself, but they also have to adopt the expected behaviour involved in being a staff member in a Scottish college which has been learnt, or subsumed [...] from a variety of factors, situations and more established colleagues (Allan, 2015, p. 152)

Thus, power hierarchies within the institutions of education can be, on some occasions, obvious for staff and students, but they can also be covert or hidden “without being less invasive or powerful” (ibid., p.85). These power relations within the context of education “can affect practice on a daily basis” (ibid., p.153) and ultimately have an impact on students’ identity negotiation and language development. Therefore, it is important to understand how these power structures work to shape the profession and the individuals involved in it in order to identify, understand, and ultimately address, any unfair practices that may be embedded within the profession.

Powell (2015) explains how Foucauldian tools for thinking can be divided into two categories that interact and co-exist to help “professions to examine, calculate and classify the groups that governments and institutions regulate, discipline and divide” (ibid., p.408). The first tool for thinking is the archaeology of knowledge, which refers to the analysis of statements and the power of discourse to choose one statement over another, for a certain purpose or context. The preference for one statement rather than another is not static, but rather is subject to change depending on its context; sometimes a certain idea is the norm and accepted as ‘Truth’ for a certain period of time and, then it is replaced by another one (Foucault, 1980). In TESOL, this tool may help to explain how the discourse has influenced the profession and its power structures to favour some teachers’ identity characteristics over others, as evidenced in the previous chapter. However, the concept of archaeology of knowledge helps to explain that this perceived preference for a certain profile of teachers

could change if the circumstances change. According to Powell (2015) this consideration of the discourse could contribute to the unveiling of close inter-relationships within particular discourses and institutions; for example, it could serve to identify and explain the reasons why some institutions require teachers who are perceived as 'native speakers', or consider applications from candidates who hold passports from only a limited number of countries (Ruecker and Ives, 2015).

Powell (2015) discusses genealogy as the Foucauldian second tool for thinking, which is, in essence, the practical discussion of archaeology. For Foucault and Gordon (1980, p.117) genealogy is a "form of history that can account for the constitution of knowledges, [and] discourses" without even making reference to any particular subject, field or event, but that is simply embedded and accepted in history. This tool for thinking, according to Powell (2015), can be manifested in two ways: first, through classification practices that determine what is considered an object of knowledge, or 'Truth,' and what is not. This idea takes into consideration that the 'Truth' is not fixed but rather it depends on each society's beliefs, and it is constructed through multiple ways of exercising power and constraint (Foucault, 1980). In addition, according to Foucault, this idea of 'Truth' in a particular society is not created by just one single event, but rather it is shaped by all the different events that influence society:

It's not a matter of locating everything on one level, that of the event, but of realising that there are actually a whole order of levels of different types of events differing in amplitude, chronological breadth, and capacity to produce effects (Foucault, 1980 p.114)

This theory implies that the perceived preference for certain teachers' characteristics over others that is present in the ELT profession may be based on a socially constructed idea that favours certain aspects of teachers such as gender, nativeness, and age in or for a particular context.

The second way in which genealogy can be manifested is through divisive practices which consist of 'othering' some behaviours and normalizing others aiming to maintain cultural order. In the wide TESOL profession this tool is perceived in many ways, not only affecting educators, but the profession as a whole. Considering the acronym of 'TESOL' itself, there is already a division between the teachers and the 'others'; the powerful and the powerless (Pennycook, 2020). This is precisely what Amin (1997) explains when describing the situation of immigrant ESOL learners in Canada; she points out that those learners are defined as 'other' and considered inferior by the society until they acquire a certain level of English. Simpson (2020) also discusses how in some ESOL contexts, acquiring a competent level of English is perceived as being successful. In his view, society believes that by the acquisition of English, migrants will transform from being considered the 'others' to being successful members of the community. Therefore, competence in the English language is transformed into power, or lack of it, within ESOL communities.

There are other examples of dividing practices in the profession. For example, the NNES/NNEST dichotomy serves to perpetuate a division between what is considered the 'Truth', the NESTs, and the 'other', the NNESTs, or the white and non-white English language teacher division discussed by scholars such as Motha (2006) and Gerald (2020). These

practices serve the purpose of giving more credence to one group and leaving the 'others' in a position of perceived disadvantage. As Powell (2015) explains, these two practices, classification and dividing, work together helping professions to "examine, calculate and classify the groups that governments and institutions regulate, discipline and divide" (ibid. p.408) and ultimately shape the profession around these power mechanisms.

All in all, understanding how Foucauldian tools for thinking operate within the profession provides this study with a broader perspective of how power shapes and develops in the field, and will help to acknowledge, understand, and explain any situation of inequality or discrimination that might be encountered.

3.2.2 Freire: power and oppression

In a thesis investigating power and education from an intersectional perspective, it seems reasonable to discuss the work of Freire (2000), which Collins and Bilge (2020 p.190) have described as "a core text for intersectionality". Freire (2000) describes oppression as:

Any situation in which "A" objectively exploits "B" or hinders his and her pursuit of self-affirmation as a responsible person is one of oppression. Such situation itself constitutes violence, even when sweetened by false generosity [...] Never in history has violence been initiated by the oppressed. [...] Violence is initiated by those who oppress, who exploit, who fail to recognize others as persons- not by those who are oppressed, exploited and unrecognized (Freire, 2000, p. 55).

This definition of oppression can be applied to any context or situation where unequal power and injustice are being analysed, yet the term 'oppression' has been described as "bold and direct" (Collins and Bilge, 2020 p.191) and it may be considered an exaggeration by some. However, the realities that Freire (2000) described can be applied to the context of this study and therefore his own terms will be employed to discuss this idea. In the context of ESOL professionals, the fact that some employers hinder the career path or the opportunity for employment of some teachers and have a perceived preference for others based on their identity characteristics could be potentially understood as a form of oppression, and as a consequence as violence (ibid.), although they may not be aware that they are causing this. A key element of Freire's (2000) understanding of power in education is that any situation of oppression is not fixed, but it has the ability to change if the oppressed acknowledge their own reality, as he explains in the following section:

In order for the oppressed to be able to wage the struggle for their liberation, they must perceive reality of oppression not as a closed world from which there is no exit, but as a limiting situation which they can transform (Freire, 2000, p. 49).

Yet, Freire (2000) believes that the oppressed cannot achieve this without the solidarity and support of the oppressing group. This means that those who have the power to transform the profession should do so, in order to reconstruct the current reality and support the oppressed group. This has already been suggested by Richardson (2016) who publicly asked employers to analyse, understand and explain the situation of discrimination in the profession and revise

their hiring criteria in order to make it more inclusive. However, providing that this is a common goal in the profession, ensuring unanimity on hiring practices globally across the sector is a huge task that will take time and that needs as many people as possible involved working towards this change.

Freire (2000) also argues that not all oppressors perceive their position of privilege and understand how it may affect others; instead, some believe that those who are in a perceived less privileged position are there by their own means because they are “incompetent or lazy” (p.59) and are seen as “potential enemies who must be watched” (p.59). On the other hand, if the oppressors are not willing to negotiate their position of power, or are not predisposed to re-evaluate their place in the profession, the oppressed might, in some cases, be able to challenge power hierarchies without the support and solidarity of the people in power - as it has happened with certain historically disadvantaged groups such as women, the LGBTQ+ community, poor people, or Black people, who have fought “for emancipation from the dominance of those historically privileged in the Western Culture” (St. Pierre, 2000 p.489).

In his discussion around power relations between the oppressed and the oppressors, Freire (2000) also discusses the “irresistible attraction” (ibid., p.63) that the oppressed group feel towards the oppressors and their desire to imitate them “at any cost” (ibid., p.63). This leads to their own “self-depreciation [...] which derives from their internalization of the opinion the oppressors hold of them” (ibid., p.63) and that results in their own perception of themselves as unfit. This resembles the skin whitening beauty treatments that some non-white people go through in an attempt to imitate what is considered the ‘Western beauty’, associated with whiteness, and that can have terrible consequences for their health (Li *et al.*, 2008). In a similar way, some NNEST students and teachers try to mimic the way NEST speak (Llurda, 2015) as the NESTs’ ‘native’ or ‘neutral’ accent is considered “beautiful”. Even though this does not seem to have atrocious consequences for their physical health, it may have a negative impact on the L2 English speaker teachers’ self-perception and can lead to that self-depreciation mentioned by Freire (2000), and that scholars such as Llurda (2015), and Richardson (2016) have already identified in the profession.

3.2.3. Collins & Bilge: The domains of power, and intersectionality

More recently, Collins and Bilge (2020) have also discussed the issue of power within an intersectional perspective. According to them, power is structured around four different domains, each of which is concerned with a certain aspect of society and that combined serve to shape the status quo and organize society.

First, they describe the *structural domain*, which refers to social institutions such as health, education, job market, and housing, which interact influencing the country’s social structure. Second, they refer to the *cultural domain of power*, which emphasizes the ideas and culture that are valued by the institution in power. In the context of TESOL, this domain of power can be used to analyse which idea or ideas of ‘Truth’ are being promoted through the materials and digital content frequently used in the classroom. For example, major institutions in the profession have traditionally been known for choosing accents such as Received Pronunciation (RP) or General American (GA) as the ‘correct model’ for students (Monfared and Khatib,

2018), and for creating curriculum content around a very specific idea of what is considered to be the 'British Culture' (Gray and Block, 2014). Since the material of large TESOL institutions is being used globally, "it is important to ask what cultural messages concerning race, gender, class, sexuality, and similar categories are being broadcast to this vast global audience" (Collins and Bilge, 2020 p.10). This question is addressed by Brown and Nanguy (2021) in the Scottish ESOL context. In their study, they analyse two examples of global coursebooks frequently used in the classroom to teach ESOL in colleges and community learning spaces in Scotland, to explore how the nine identity characteristics that are protected under the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010) are portrayed in these books, and to what extent they serve as an aid to facilitate discussions around these characteristics, or if, on the contrary, these characteristics are silenced or invisible. The study concludes that, in the coursebooks, there is a perceived "invisibility" (Brown and Nanguy, 2021, p. 58) of people who have one or more of the protected characteristics, which denies students the opportunity to learn meaningful language to express their own views on different identities. This is an example of Collins and Bilge's (2020) *cultural domain* used in the ESOL Scottish context.

The third domain of power that they (ibid.) describe in their book is the *disciplinary domain* which is concerned with how rules and regulations are applied across a society vis-à-vis the different identity factors such as ethnicity, age, race, gender and class among others. According to them, every individual is "disciplined" (ibid., p.12) to 'fit' into the current status quo that organizes the society they live in. This discipline is not applied using "overt pressure, but by ongoing disciplinary pressure" (ibid., p.12). For Foucault (1995) this type of disciplinary power has a "great power of diffusion" (ibid., p.139) through small acts, apparently innocent, that serve as a form of coercion in society. In the TESOL context, this domain could serve to explain the different hiring requirements for native and nonnative teachers, or the acceptance of the idea that perceives native teachers as 'better' teachers (Jenkins, 2017; Tatar, 2019). Lastly, Collins and Bilge (2020) discuss the *interpersonal domain* to refer to how each individual experiences the interaction of the other three domains and how they shape their identity and their social interaction with others. Each individual is biased by their own perceptions as members of different social groups, and this can influence the way everyone perceives their sense of privilege and oppression. In TESOL, perhaps some teachers may not realize their position of privilege derived from their belonging to certain social groups, but they might acknowledge their position of oppression for belonging to other not so privileged groups. For example, a Black male teacher from the UK, may understand their situation of oppression for being Black but fail to realize their potential privilege for being male and from a Western country. Using an intersectional analysis will help to shed some light in issues of power and oppression within the context of ESOL Further Education in Scotland, in a way that has not been explored in the past.

3.3 Language teacher identity (LTI)

Gray and Morton (2018, p. 2) define identity as a "superordinate term" that encompasses all aspects of what we do and who we are, both as individuals and as members of various communities. This identity shapes how we position ourselves in different situations and influences the way in which others perceive us. In the teaching context, teacher identity is constructed and negotiated in relation to the learners, personal and professional experiences, and the teaching context (ibid.) but it is also "inseparable" (Yazan and Lindahl, 2020, p. 2) from other identity categories such as ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, class, religion or

nationality. Thus, language teacher identities should be explored from an intersectional framework as all these categories are interdependent and subject to change within a particular context (Norton and De Costa, 2018).

For scholars such as Varghese *et al.* (2005), Winchester (2013), and Yazan and Lindahl (2020) language teachers' negotiation of their own identity is an essential part of the learning process in language education, because the teacher's role in the classroom is not neutral; it has the potential to influence students' language development, motivation and investment in education, as well as shaping the learning atmosphere of the classroom. This means that the way in which teachers present themselves to and engage with the students, as well as the way they negotiate aspects of their own identity such as race, gender, social status and sexual orientation can have an impact on the learners' identity formation. In addition, Schissel and Stephens (2020) believe that teachers' critical awareness of how their identity influences their teaching is the starting point to understand the complex identities of the students and is "pivotal" (Schissel and Stephens, 2020, p. 144) in preparing them to identify and challenge any perceived oppression that minority groups in the profession might face. Thus, in this study where the focus is on the exploration of ESOL lecturers' identity in Scottish colleges, the literature around teacher identity, and particularly language teacher identity (LTI) is central to the whole thesis.

According to Kayi-Aydar (2019), the topic of language teacher identity in research is relatively recent and has gained more attention in the last decade. This recent interest in language teacher identity has led to varied views and interpretations of this concept, or as Barkhuizen (2017, p.3) puts it "composite understandings" of it. Therefore, the next sub-section explores the different ways in which scholars understand LTI, and the factors that influence teachers' identity negotiation.

3.3.1 Factors that influence teachers' identity negotiation

The literature underscores a widespread understanding that language teacher identity is dynamic and constantly evolving (Norton, 1997; Varghese *et al.*, 2005; Barkhuizen, 2017; Yazan, 2017; Kayi-Aydar, 2019; Dimitrieska, 2024). For Yazan and Lindahl (2020) the dynamic nature of LTI means that teachers' identity negotiation is a continuous process that enables them to understand how to "become teachers, grow as teachers, and exercise their practices situated in sociohistorical, cultural and political contexts" (Yazan and Lindahl, 2020, p.1). This construction and negotiation of their identity is influenced by their past, present and (imagined) future experiences as practitioners, as members of different communities, for example, an institution or a class, and as citizens in a specific city. Dimitrieska (2024) also understands LTI as shifting and dynamic and believes that the way in which it needs to be negotiated across different contexts and is influenced by various factors makes the LTI unique for each individual, and for each particular situation. Barkhuizen (2017) emphasizes that teachers' identities shift as they adapt to new contexts, situations, and objectives, but they also change in response to the different roles and relationships a teacher navigates within and outside the classroom. For instance, a teacher may present their identity differently when interacting with colleagues than when engaging directly with students. Therefore, due to this changing nature, for him, "LTIs are not something teachers possess, like an object, but rather something they do or perform" (Barkhuizen, 2017, p.6). This notion of language teacher

identity as performative and dynamic is also explored in the work of Kennedy (2020), who discusses with the participants of her study the idea of having a teaching 'persona' that is different from the identity of that teacher outside the classroom. However, in the end, her participants discard this idea and, instead, they believe that rather than having a static 'persona', teachers decide which parts of their identity they want to 'emphasize' more in the classroom in order to connect with the learners. This particular negotiation of identity is influenced by both the context and the learners' needs. This view is an example of the considerations of LTI in relation to learners and the potential impact (either positive or negative) that the teachers' identity might have on students which I discuss in the next subsection. Lastly, with regard to the dynamic nature of teachers' identities, Barkhuizen (2017) argues that such changes in a person's LTI can be as a result of a short-term encounter or may occur over a longer period of time as a consequence of different experiences.

The literature suggests that there are different factors that influence this negotiation or 'performance' of LTIs; these factors include cognitive, social, emotional and contextual causes. Barkhuizen (2017) views LTIs as cognitive constructs in the sense they are shaped by the teachers' professional knowledge of theories and pedagogies as well as by their experiences inside the classroom; that is, what the teacher knows about the students' and their experiences. Similarly, Dimitrieska (2024) also perceives that the cognitive abilities of the teacher, and their professional experience, influences LTIs. However, she believes that this professional knowledge intersects with the teachers' personal identities, and the development of these identities through time. This notion is shared by Yazan and Lindahl (2020) who consider LTIs as a continued negotiation process at the intersection between the personal and professional identities of the teachers; that is, their professional knowledge and experience intersect with other parts of their identity, such as teachers' own ideas, biases or values. Similarly, Kennedy (2020) suggests that the teachers' I-positions, that is, the different roles that a teacher 'performs' in order to negotiate their identity in a particular context, are based on their own beliefs and their prior experiences inside the classroom.

Social interactions, whether occurring locally within teachers' institutions, or globally in broader professional discussions, also have the potential to influence teachers' identity negotiation (Barkhuizen, 2017; Kennedy, 2020; Yazan and Lindahl, 2020). Barkhuizen (2017) illustrates this by describing how interactions with students, colleagues, or staff in an educational institution often require teachers to engage in identity negotiation in order to 'perform' their identity in a way that is suitable for a specific context. This negotiation of identity can result in teachers perceiving themselves as part of a community, or as an outsider in this particular context; while their sense of belonging may enhance participation in a specific community, lack of belonging may cause detachment from that context (ibid.). In addition, Barkhuizen (2017) believes that there is an interconnectivity between the 'outside', the social context, and the 'inside', the teacher's own beliefs, emotions, and ideas and both influence LTIs simultaneously. This belief is also shared by Kennedy (2020, p.47) who describes identity negotiation "at the intersection between the individual and the social space". This 'individual' or 'inside' space is also influenced by personal emotions, as highlighted by Barkhuizen (2017). Teachers' emotions, self-perceptions, and internal experiences contribute significantly to the shaping of their professional identities; for example, feelings of success or frustrations may influence teachers' own perceptions about themselves and, subsequently,

influence their practice. The work of Yazan and Lindahl (2020) also explores language teacher identity as linked to emotions capturing long-term and short-term tensions. These emotional dynamics influence how teachers experience their professional roles and navigate challenges within the classroom, with other members of staff or at a broader institutional level. Long-term tensions may arise from previous experiences inside or outside the classroom or professional or institutional demands, while short-term tensions can appear as a result of immediate classroom interactions. Understanding how emotions have the potential to influence the way in which identity is presented in professional settings are evidence of the complexities of LTI in practice.

It is also worth considering language as a factor that influences teachers' identity negotiation as "identity constructs and is constructed through language" (Norton, 1997, p. 419). In the same way that the role of the teacher in the classroom is not neutral, as discussed earlier, language is not either, especially within the contexts of multiculturalism and globalization. According to Norton (2019 p.301)

the concept of 'language' is not only a linguistic system of words and sentences, but also a social practice in which identities and desires are negotiated in the context of complex and often unequal social relationships.

Therefore, language cannot be detached from the social background, nor from its users and their culture, as it contains "traces of the cultural contexts in which it has been used" (Kramsch and Zhu, 2019, p. 39). The global presence of English is not just a reflection of linguistic dominance but also an embodiment of certain perceptions of cultural representations. As such, when people engage with English, they are often interacting with the cultural 'baggage' it carries, including images of modernity, consumerism, and Western ideals. This intertwining of language with social identity and culture means that the way in which teachers and learners engage with the English language also has the potential to influence the way in which identity is negotiated in the classroom and more widely.

As discussed above, the construction and negotiation of teachers' identity may serve to enhance teachers' sense of belonging in their community (e.g. school, classroom, or country). However, it can also create tensions, conflict, and resistance within their own individual selves as it could be understood as an act of distance from oneself (Barkhuizen, 2017; Gray and Morton, 2018; Kennedy, 2020). Varghese *et al.* (2005) argue that such conflicts may arise when there is a discrepancy between how a teacher perceives themselves, and how others perceive them. Varghese *et al.* (2005) conceptualise LTIs as multiple and fluid, meaning that an individual can occupy different roles within the profession. For instance, an English language teacher might simultaneously be the head of department and a student in another department. In such case, the teacher must constantly negotiate how and when to 'perform' each role depending on the specific context. The negotiation may generate a sense of conflict between the teacher's self-perception, and the way they are perceived by other members of staff or students. According to Yazan and Lindahl (2020) conflict may also be generated by structural constraints and customary classroom practices. This idea is developed further by Gray and Morton (2018) who explain how the reality of most teachers is that they are working

for education systems that are heavily perceived as businesses and, therefore, their construction and negotiation of identity might be influenced by the interests of the market. This is particularly relevant in the context of English as a global language, discussed in the previous chapter, where there is a current demand for English language teaching and learning. As a result of these tensions, teachers might experience a conflict between their professional knowledge and the structural and institutional interests; for example, if their understanding of effective practices, or educational theories clash with institutional policies or interests of the institution or the society in which it is based. Thus, language teacher identity and the way it is negotiated can create harmony, or sense of belonging, or tensions which may influence the experiences of language learners. For this reason, in the following section, I explore how teacher identity negotiation may influence English language learners.

3.3.2 Language teacher identity (LTI): influence on learners.

In a context such as ESOL in Scotland where learners come from a wide range of countries and educational backgrounds, and the student body is multilingual in nature, students and teachers may not always share a common linguistic or cultural background. In order to provide the best possible experience for learners, Schissel and Stephens (2020) recommend that teachers develop an understanding of the way in which their own multiple identities converge or diverge from the students'. This may influence teachers' practice in a positive way and enhance student engagement. A similar notion is discussed in the work of Kennedy (2020) who states that:

Understanding that your everyday personality might not be what your students need is really insightful. It's not a positive or a negative thing; it's just being aware (Kennedy, 2020, p. 54)

If a teacher can develop an awareness of their own identity traits which may enhance the connection with the students, the teacher might have the ability to 'emphasize' those aspects of their identity over others (ibid.). Scholars such as Varghese et al. (2005), and Winchester (2013) believe that learning about students' backgrounds and their language needs may help the teacher to negotiate their own identity in a way that facilitates students' identity negotiation in the target language, which can result in improved communication and the use of relevant classroom materials to develop and enhance language learning. This can be especially significant in multilingual classes or in contexts where educators teach in a different country from that in which they are from, as they will need to understand and adapt to different rules of communication (Winchester, 2013).

In addition, scholars such as Yazan and Lindahl (2020) point out that teachers with a strong sense of their own identity are often more sensitive to issues of diversity and inclusion in the classroom. These teachers can create environments that are welcoming to students from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds, which can enhance learners' sense of belonging and confidence and, thus, enhance their language development. By modelling inclusivity, teachers can encourage students to embrace their own identities, resulting in better social and academic outcomes, and improved participation in classroom activities. However, when teachers fail to acknowledge learners' diverse identities, it can lead to feelings of alienation or

exclusion among students, which can potentially have a negative impact on learning. An awareness of these issues is vital to good practice and has relevance for this study because, as will be seen in the findings chapters, teachers who have a strong sense of identity are the ones expected to introduce diversity in the profession.

Norton and De Costa (2018) identified the role of the language teacher in the classroom as a role model for students; for example, students tend to imitate the way the teacher uses the language, and they are perceived as a figure of authority within the classroom. For this reason, in their view, the way in which teacher identity is performed in the classroom can influence how learners perceive their own linguistic and cultural identities. For instance, a teacher who embraces multilingualism and cultural diversity can inspire learners to develop a positive view of their own linguistic and cultural heritage. Conversely, if a teacher is not sensitive to the learners' multiple identities, learners may feel excluded or less confident in expressing their identity.

Thus, the literature suggests that exploring LTI can have positive impact on the learning experience for teachers and learners, can foster better communication practices and address diverse identities in the classroom. That is the reason why scholars such as Kennedy (2020), Schissel and Stephens (2020), and Dimitrieska (2024) are critical of English language teacher training programmes that do not seem to offer space to reflect and explore teacher identity construction and negotiation. They believe that these practices should be included as part of pre-service English language teacher courses, and in fact, at all stages of a teacher's career. This idea is also supported by Banegas, Beltrán-Palanques and Salas (2023), who encourage all teachers and teacher educators to engage in identity reflection as a beneficial practice for staff and students. In addition, they believe that this practice can encourage criticality in the language programmes.

Overall, this section has examined the literature on language teacher identity negotiation, highlighting the various factors that influence teachers' identities and the potential impact their identity performances may have on students and their language learning experiences. The following section will explore how different aspects of teachers' identities such as race, ethnicity, English language varieties, culture, social class, and gender, are perceived within the profession.

3.4 Exploring unequal practices in TESOL: practitioners' identities

As discussed in the previous chapter, English language is now considered a global language that enables international communication and has become part of the popular culture and of many education systems all over the world (Crystal, 2003, Melitz, 2016). However, Pennycook (2020) points out that ELT provides possibilities for many, but also creates barriers for others:

Rather than the bland terms in which English is often understood – as a neutral medium of international communication, a language that holds out the social and economic development of all those who learnt it, a language of equal opportunity, a language that the world needs in order to be able to communicate – we need to understand that it is also an exclusionary class dialect, favouring particular people,

cultures, forms of knowledge and possibilities of development; it is a language which creates barriers as well as it presents possibilities (Pennycook, 2020, p. 26).

English as a global language has resulted in TESOL as a worldwide profession that embraces people from very diverse backgrounds and values from all over the world. As a result, this enables professional debates between teachers who have varied professional experiences and work in a variety of teaching contexts (Kubota and Lin, 2006). This has generated an interest from a great number of scholars (Kumaravadivelu, 2006; Appleby, 2013; Lawrence and Nagashima, 2019; Maddamsetti, 2020) who have focused on analysing the identity of teachers in the profession and pointing out the perceived preference for very specific teacher characteristics which are largely white, middle class and 'native speakers' of English. The influence and perception of English language teachers' identities in the profession has been explored in various forms and from perspectives which include analysing hiring practices (Jenkins, 2017), job advertisements (Mahboob and Golden, 2013), and the content of textbooks (Ansary and Babaii, 2003; Gray and Block, 2014). Most studies seem to agree that the identity characteristics of individual candidates in terms of race, age, gender, sexual identity, nationality, and personality among other factors can potentially play a decisive role in hiring practices (Kubota and Lin, 2006) and the overall reputation of the profession (Nash, 2008). Appleby (2016), however, argues that most of this research focuses on disadvantaged groups and, as a result, there is very little research about the perceived privileged groups and the ethical dilemmas that they can potentially encounter for being in such a position. In addition, she points out the potential lack of awareness of the perceived privileged groups and the limitations in acknowledging and exploring the ways in which they may be benefiting from the current system.

3.4.1 Race, ethnicity and the concept of 'native speakerism' in ELT

According to Motha (2006) discussing race in English language teaching is "inevitabl[e]" (p.496) because the global spread of English has been historically linked to the international political power of English and whiteness, as it has been previously discussed by scholars such as Kumaravadivelu (2006) and Crystal (2003). For Motha (2006) this whiteness in ELT "echoes colonial patterns of domination [and] affirms Eurocentric values" (p.498) with regard to students and teachers of different backgrounds. On the discussion about racism in TESOL, the work of Kubota and Lin (2006) has been prominent, introducing the idea that racism is very much present and visible in various ways in the profession to the extent that it helps to shape and determine power relations:

The idea of race, racialization, and racism are factors that shape social, cultural, and political dimensions of language teaching and learning. English language teaching entails complex relations of power fuelled by differences created by racialization (Kubota and Lin, 2006, p.488).

They also describe how races are not biologically determined, but rather a social construct used to legitimize and perpetuate divisions between humans, and as a construct, they are dynamic and able to adapt to particular historical and geographical contexts. From this perspective, the concept of 'ethnicity' is also an abstraction.

This could be considered an example of use of the second Foucauldian tool for thinking (genealogy), explained in section 3.2.1, that uses 'othering' as a mechanism to control and exercise power; therefore the construct of race legitimizes divisions between people and creates a notion of 'Truth', where in some situations and for some people, certain races are preferred over others, as it is perceived in some contexts of the TESOL profession (Kubota and Lin, 2006, Lin, 2006, Mahboob, 2009, Gerald, 2020).

On the other hand, although the concept of race is socially constructed, it is also necessary to address the experiences of non-white people. This allows the identification, challenge, and, ultimately, eradication of the unequal power relations that exist among races in different contexts. Without addressing the category of 'race', particular behaviours or policies that have a negative impact on non-white people may be overlooked or ignored, as it happened in Brazil, when the government eradicated the concept of race:

This erasure of "blackness" as a political category allowed discriminatory practices to occur in areas of education and employment against people of visible African descent because there were neither officially recognised terms of describing racial discrimination nor official remedies for it (Collins and Bilge, 2020 p.26)

Therefore, in the field of TESOL, it seems essential to acknowledge the concept of race, not as a tool to create divisions between people, but as a term to frame particular struggles that affect non-white professionals and that may be otherwise overlooked.

Racism in TESOL can be considered an element of a bigger issue that is present in every other aspect of society, permeating personal relations, and even in institutions and public bodies (ibid.) resulting in terrible incidents such as the murder of Stephen Lawrence in the United Kingdom in 1993 (MacPherson, 1999), which in itself led to a public inquiry and a subsequent recognition of institutional racism within the police. A more recent example of this is the violent police incident in the United States, which resulted in George Floyd's death, and which led to a wave of collective anger which has become palpable in many anti-racist campaigns in the United States and beyond (BBC, 2020). These examples show that institutional racism is not exclusively associated with a single country, culture or historical moment, but rather it has been endemic in many areas of society for decades and yet, it has still not been eradicated.

In TESOL, racism has been closely explored in relation to different identity characteristics such as teachers' first language and the belief that NESTs are "the ideal teacher of English" (Llurda, 2020, p. 51). This, according to many (Kubota and Lin, 2006, Mahboob and Golden, 2013, Holliday, 2014), has a direct influence on the hiring practices of different institutions. Llurda (2015) also believes that native speakerism is a form of racism in TESOL and a term intended to 'other' and segregate the 'natives' from the 'non-natives':

"Race is, in fact, a key element of the discussion of native and non-native teachers, as discriminatory practices are often associated with practices of segregation of "the other", the foreigner, the stranger who does not belong to [...] the native community and such discriminatory practices are conveniently disguised as common sense" (Llurda, 2015, p. 107).

This is closely related to the idea of NEST being not only language instructors, but “ambassadors” (Llurda, 2004 p.319) of the so-called English culture. Holliday (2018) develops further this idea and describes native speakerism as a “neo-racist ideology” (ibid., p.1) that intends to promote the idea of native speakers and Western values as an aspirational model for the learners. This, according to Lawrence and Nagashima (2019), makes the white native speaker teacher a commodity that is, in some cases, considered more valuable than qualifications and experience; this not only undervalues the qualifications of native speaker teachers but also excludes from the profession the majority of the teaching body just because their first language is not English (Varghese et al., 2005, Richardson, 2016). Appleby (2013) offers examples of this in the Japanese context, showing how having English as an L1 but no related qualifications or experience was not an obstacle for employment for the participants in his study, as long as they had enthusiasm and an outgoing personality.

This native speaker privilege not only affects hiring practices but also seems to play an important role in defining teachers’ self-perception (Llurda, 2015; Maddamsetti, 2020). In a study carried out by Bailey and Evison (2020), the findings suggest that although all participants considered themselves committed to the profession, the NESTs tried to show dedication by distancing themselves from the “backpacker” (ibid. p.8) English language teacher, while the NNESTs displayed commitment by demonstrating their linguistic competence in the field. On this topic, Llurda (2015, p.108) posits that some NNEST teachers “suffer a specific type of self-hatred [...] consisting of in secretly admiring the native speaker and denying themselves the legitimacy of being considered rightful language users and teachers”. This idea could serve as an explanation of why, according to Floris and Renandya (2020) many NNEST prefer to hire NEST for their own schools or departments. To address this situation, many scholars (Mahboob and Golden, 2013; Llurda, 2015; Richardson, 2016) are demanding a paradigm shift where English is taught in a bilingual or plurilingual context and professionals are employed based on their suitability to the job rather than on their first language. In addition, there are online platforms such as ‘TEFL Equity Advocates’ founded by Kiczkowiak (n.d.) which also aim to tackle native speakerism in English language teaching. This, however, has not been explored in relation to ESOL particularly where English is taught in countries where English is the dominant language, rather than a foreign language.

3.4.2 English varieties in ELT

The debate around native speakerism goes beyond the teachers’ first language; there seems to be a variety of English that is perceived as more valuable than others, which is known as “Standard English” (Fairclough, 1989 p.57). Decades ago, Fairclough (1989) discussed the role of the ‘Standardization of English’ as a valuable political, economic and cultural tool for the capitalist system of the West. This ‘Standard English’ started as a social dialect used by merchants in London and developed into what mainstream English coursebooks teach today - at the expense of other social dialects which were considered “*vulgar, slovenly, low [or] barbarous*” (Fairclough, 1989 p.57) - and has always been associated with the capitalist system and the middle class or *bourgeoisie* (ibid.), national unity, Anglocentric values and whiteness (Fairclough, 1989; Motha, 2006; R Fithriani, 2018; Pennycook, 2020).

This preference for the 'Standard' variety of English is now reflected in mainstream English classrooms. Many students are exposed to Received Pronunciation (RP) or General American (GA) varieties through their coursebooks so, as explained by Monfared and Khatib (2018), students are not only expected to learn English, but to learn these particular varieties as the 'correct' pronunciation for L2 English speakers, which implies that any deviation from these two inner circle pronunciation models (Kachru, 1992) is perceived as worse or less valid. This concept of 'Standard English' therefore seems to devalue any other variety of English that "deviat[es] from [it] in terms of phonology, lexis, pragmatics, grammar, and communication styles" (Fithriani, 2018, p.741) and, therefore, teachers who speak other varieties may be considered less valuable in the profession (Modiano, 2001). The studies referred to, however, are based on countries where English is taught as a foreign language, so this may be different in Scottish ESOL education as in Scotland English is the dominant language and the varieties spoken in this region deviate from the so-called 'Standard' variety.

Motha (2006) also explores the relation between English variety and skin colour and argues that in the same way that white teachers are perceived to be "more legitimate than English teachers of color" (Motha, 2006, p. 499), those who speak a mainstream variety are perceived to be more legitimate teachers of the language. As an example, she (ibid.) shares her own experiences related to her linguistic background, explaining that although she has Sri-Lankan origins, she has learned English in Australia and the US, and therefore the variety of English she speaks is considered privileged because it is associated with whiteness: "I speak a form of English associated with Whiteness, although I am not White" (ibid.p.499).

In opposition to the construct of 'Standard English', Kachru (1992) posits a new list of standard varieties based on what he described as a model of World Englishes, the varieties of which are distributed around three concentric circles based on social, geographical and historical parameters. In short, the term 'World Englishes' encompasses "any of the varieties [of English] that have emerged in postcolonial and other international contexts" (Motha, 2006 p.508) and gives value to the local varieties of English that deviate from the 'Standard' (Llurda, 2020). This model has received a lot of criticism by scholars such as Graddol, 1997 p.10) who states that:

One of the drawbacks of this terminology is the way it locates the 'native speakers' and native speaking countries at the centre of the global use of English and, by implication, the source of models of correctness, the best teachers and English-language.

In addition, Motha (2006) believes that Kachru's (1992) classification of Englishes contributes to the devaluation of people of colour in the profession and to the Anglicization of the varieties of English that are spoken by people outside the 'white mainstream' variety. Pennycook (2020) is also very critical of Kachru's (1992) model of World Englishes on the grounds that it is related to power and classism, as it only focuses on the varieties of English spoken by the upper class of each country. This model, as Pennycook (2020) argues, leaves other varieties spoken by people of other social classes unnoticed, which creates a division between colonial and postcolonial English, and it does not tackle issues of power and inequalities.

This discussion is particularly relevant in the context ESOL education in Scotland, an inner-circle country with accents that generally differ from RP and GA, and varieties of English that deviate from the so called 'Standard English'. In this context, Scottish practitioners who may be considered 'native' do not speak the 'Standard' variety.

3.4.3 White-skin privilege and its associated 'prestige'

A related aspect of racism in TESOL is the perceived white skin privilege, which also seems to have an impact on the hiring practices and the schools' perceived prestige associated with Whiteness and nativeness (Kubota and Lin, 2006; Mahboob and Golden, 2013). This is very clearly explained by Lin (2006) who narrates her own story as a racialized woman in TESOL. She describes how she has perceived that some schools prefer to have white skinned teachers as head of departments, as this is used in some cases as symbols of prestige that help to boost the school or departmental image. On the topic of whiteness, Mahboob (2009) argues that schools seem to prefer native speakers in the believe that they are better teachers, and those native speakers are always imagined as white. He (ibid.) analyses different job advertisements and finds out that unlike the explicit requirement for teachers to be native speakers of English, whiteness is not explicitly stated in the job descriptions, but it is considered "an unmarked feature of being an ESL teacher" (p.34).

This apparent bias towards white professionals is what Gerald (2020, p.44) refers to as "hegemonic whiteness [that] controls our institutions, our curricula and our pedagogy ", an unfair situation that makes him call all members of the profession to work together to counteract and eradicate it. Both Richardson (2016) and Gerald (2020) show that some schools justify their preference for a certain type of teacher that is native and white as an answer to their customers' preferences. Richardson (2016) suggests educating the customers about their choices and the "unrealistic expectations" of being taught by native speakers of English only. Richardson (2016) also makes clear that it is the employers and teachers themselves who need to challenge these discriminatory choices in order to see a change in customers' preferences. In addition, Motha (2006) believes that, in order to overcome any form of racism in the profession, "ESOL practitioners should have an explicit consciousness of the implications of their practice" (ibid., p.514) in a broader context and adapt their teaching and materials accordingly.

3.3.4 Culture

According to Atkinson (1999, p. 625), "except for language, learning, and teaching, there is perhaps no more important concept in the field of TESOL than culture". Although the academic discussion of culture in Applied Linguistics and TESOL only started during the 1990s, when globalization began to emerge, it has become a widely discussed issue in the field of ELT by scholars such as Atkinson (1999), Kubota and Lin (2006), Morgan (2007) and Kramsch and Zhu (2019). For Kubota and Lin (2006) culture is just a more "benign and acceptable" (p.476) term that has replaced what was previously known as racial difference, but that it serves the same purpose: divide people into groups by their experiences in order to exclude or privilege certain groups of people. In the ELT context, Morgan (2007) believes that discussions about cultural differences can become a form of disguising and legitimizing "systematic inequalities

connected to race, class, sexual orientation, or gender relations in society.” (p.1042). As an example, he describes how the ELT methods and techniques that teachers learn in their teacher training courses have been discussed and learned from a specific culture and set of beliefs and can be a “potential form of cultural politics when exported across settings” (p.1043).

This preference for a particular way of teaching techniques that are set in Western, middle-class values and culture may explain the perceived predilection in the profession for teacher candidates who are from a cultural background and have personalities that are associated with the western culture (Appleby, 2016).

Kramersch and Zhu (2019, p.45) refer to the notion of culture in ELT as “denationalised, deterritorialised, decontextualised and associated with language use in real and online environments” across people of different backgrounds and identity characteristics. The online environment and social media have influenced the way people communicate and think of language and relationships, as well as the concept of culture as homogeneous across a particular country or region. Kramersch and Zhu (2019) wonder how this new concept of culture can be introduced into the ELT classroom taking into account the new tools, and the new perceptions of culture across the virtual environment.

3.4.5 Social class in ELT

Social class seems to have been an aspect of identity and source of inequalities in ELT that despite its “tangible effects in language classrooms, [...] often remain[s] hidden behind discourse of other very important inequalities” (Glodjo, 2017, p. 343). Therefore, scholars such as Vandrick (2014) and Glodjo (2017) urge researchers to include a class lens in their research in order to make more visible the different manifestations of class that contribute to reinforcing and reproducing privilege in ELT in the profession; this section will analyse the relevant literature on class in ELT and how it affects teachers’ identity and its implications for teaching and learning.

Unlike other aspects of identity such as ethnicity, class is not fixed but rather dynamic (ibid.) which makes it more challenging to define and explore. The definitions of class have been very diverse throughout history and applied in different ways in society. However, in simple terms, Vandrick (2014, p.86) describes social class as “an amorphous term” but one that is generally understood as a way to rank people hierarchically in a society in terms of “their social, economic, occupational, and educational statuses” (ibid.). There seems to be certain consensus in the need to include a social class lens to explore different aspects of English language education such as the students, the educators, and the relationship between them across levels, countries, and institutions, as suggested by Vandrick (2014, pp. 89–90):

The effects of social class status are not abstract but strongly affect the lived experiences of participants in second-language education. Social class status can cause great disadvantage or grant great privilege. Because it has such concrete consequences, it is important that those involved in language education, whether

teaching language, preparing language educators, or carrying out research on language education, consider addressing social class in their teaching and research.

As part of the identity characteristics explored in this study, social class will be studied from the participants' perceptions, taking into account its intersections with other identity variables such as gender, first language, or ethnicity, among others. The understanding of class in this study is taken from the participants' discussions, and will be explored in chapter 6.

3.3.6 Gender in ELT

Gender has also been identified as a common discriminatory factor in the field which positions women educators "unfavourably in the gender and racial hierarchies operating within the TESOL profession" (Appleby, 2013 p.124). Studies on gender in TESOL, SLA and Applied Linguistics have shifted from understanding gender as an individual factor, to examine it as part of a wider discourse that changes according to the political, historical and economic context (Norton and Pavlenko, 2004). Florent and Walter (1989, p.180) described sexism as "an unconscious bias, expressed and reinforced by the language people learn from childhood on" and that develops to change people's thoughts, attitudes, and behaviours. In relation to sexism and language, Hume (2013, p. 20) also believes that linguistic choices influence the way "we organise and think about the world" and that this is shown in language teaching. Therefore, sexist practices in the society are linked to the language that people use, and it evolves with society and reproduced by language teaching.

Davis and Skilton-Sylvester (2004) explain that although the context changes throughout the years "sexist practices may persist and become institutionalized because they benefit those who hold power" (ibid, p.383). This suggests that sexism, like racism, is part of a greater discourse that is endemic in society in many forms and has the power to influence hiring practices and the perceptions on the status of women in the profession (Neena, 2019). Today, the digital world in general, and social media in particular, provide resources to make sexism visible and easier to denounce in all its forms (McLean, 2020). This has led to projects such as 'Everyday Sexism' (Bates, no date) where people can share their own experiences related to sexism. In TESOL there are also online organizations such as 'Women of Color In ELT' (2023) and 'Gender Equality ELT' (Mayne and Prentis, no date), fighting for equal opportunities in the profession and supporting women working in ELT in different ways.

The gender imbalance in English language teaching has been acknowledged in the United Kingdom at least since 1986 when the group 'Women in TEFL' was founded. This group aimed to support and empower women working in ELT and offered training to enable them access to management positions (Florent and Walter, 1989). There is, however, limited scholarly literature about this topic, although it has been discussed by ELT professionals in many blog posts (Butler, 2010; Thornbury, 2017; Bruzzano, 2021). In 2015, Prentis and Mayne addressed this issue in their IATEFL session Where are the Women in ELT? (Prentis and Mayne, 2015) and more recently scholars such as Sullivan and Kimura (2020) have also discussed it; they all agree on the lack of women in positions of power in English language teaching, even though women outnumber men in the profession. According to Sullivan and Kimura (2020, p.70) this is explained because employers "[favour] male employees over female" and they offer men

more opportunities to progress in their careers, which leads to a lack of women role models in the ELT profession.

In addition to issues of power and representation of women in English language teaching, the perceived gender imbalance seems to generate, in some cases, a gender pay gap that affects women more than men. Sullivan and Kimura (2020), for example, show how in the Japanese context women dominate in part-time employment while men in this field are usually full-time teachers; they relate this situation to a hiring criterion that favours men and leaves childcare responsibilities to women in most of the cases. As has been discussed above, the academic literature on the topic of gender imbalance in TESOL is scarce, therefore there is not enough data to compare the Japanese context to the British context.

All in all, this perceived preference for certain accents, gender or even race or provenance that seems to be present in TESOL as a global profession, does not only impact the career development opportunities for professionals who are non-white, non-male, non-middle class and non-native speakers of English. It also creates a wealth gap between those who have the 'preferred' identity characteristics and those who do not. Bearing in mind that traditionally the TESOL industry has been targeted towards middle-class learners and teachers, this focus on a very homogeneous model of teachers, creates an even wider wealth gap in the industry allowing only certain people to have access to certain roles and to progress in their careers. According to Collins and Bilge (2020) the wealth gap has been traditionally analysed through the lenses of gender or race, but not through an intersectional framework that takes into account all identity factors that interplay with power. Therefore, this thesis will explore different identity characteristics of ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges and how their identities are perceived in the profession, shaping power relations in the profession, and impacting the individuals involved.

This section of the literature review has attempted to illustrate and discuss the main discriminatory practices that scholars have observed within the TESOL field. The discussion around the multiple factors that interplay in teachers' identity and any potential privilege or oppressive practices that are perceived in the profession can help both researchers and practitioners to reshape and redesign classroom practices in order to benefit teachers and learners of the English language (Glodjo, 2017). Hume (2013, p.11) believes that "silencing diversity issues is a central aspect of discriminatory practices" that affects the profession in many ways. In order to overcome this state of affairs and enhance the overall reputation of the profession, scholars have proposed encouraging diversity in schools and departments, by modifying the hiring criteria and discussing issues of discrimination in teaching training courses (Richardson, 2016), as well as by enhancing visibility of minority groups in ELT (Vandrick, 2014). In addition, making the profession more diverse and eliminating any identity privilege should have an impact on the learning environment as it may help to develop more meaningful education contexts that are culturally relevant for students and that lead into a more effective learning (Yurtsever and Özel, 2021).

3.5 The uniqueness of ESOL education.

As explored in the previous section, the TESOL profession has no geographical limits; it has expanded across countries and continents. As such, the profession is not homogeneous, but rather it has taken many forms in order to fulfil the demands of the different learners and institutions (Llurda, 2004). In some contexts, where English is not the first language spoken by most of the people living in a country or community, English is taught as an international (Llurda, 2004) or foreign language in schools and universities to allow communication between different countries (Wright and Baker, 2017). However, in the case of Scotland or other dominant English-speaking countries such as Australia, Canada or the United States, the English language courses are designed mainly for migrants who speak languages other than English in order to “become more effective contributors to society” (Allan, 2015 p.4) by enhancing their employability skills or enabling access to Further Education (The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015). This implies that the context of ESOL teachers and learners in English speaking countries is inherently different from other contexts where English is taught to enable global communication rather than for social integration in the community. Therefore, it should be explored from a different perspective, but of course, bearing in mind that it is still part of, and affected by, the huge global profession. This section intends to explore the (limited) literature around ESOL and discrimination in general, but particularly in the Scottish context where this study is located.

The work of Simpson (2020) is a good starting point to understand the common characteristics of ESOL education in general, the nature of ESOL students and their needs as well as the general requirements for host countries to provide quality ESOL education for migrants. Although the policies for ESOL education, the funding and the pedagogic practices vary from country to country, Simpson (2020) notes that there are some common characteristics among ESOL learners in most of the “English-dominant countries” (ibid., p.177). For example, the reasons for migrants to leave their home country, according to him are, escaping war, poverty, fear of prosecution or shortage of labours in certain sectors; this seems to correlate with the reasons described by Allan (2015) and stated in the policy created by the Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland (2015) for the Scottish ESOL context. In addition, Simpson (2020) explains that the main motivations for ESOL learners to learn the dominant language of their host country are the need to find employment and their need to socialise and be independent in their community; these reasons are very similar to the ones described for the ESOL students living in Scotland (Allan, 2015). However, not only the ESOL learners have an interest on learning the language, the British Government (Courtney, 2017) and The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland (2015) believe that by providing ESOL education for migrants, the learners will be able to contribute to the economic system of the country and will no longer be perceived as a “threat” (Courtney, 2017, p.26) or as a “drain on the economy” (ibid., p.27).

In addition, Simpson (2020) highlights the diverse educational backgrounds of ESOL learners, and the multiple languages spoken in the classroom which also seems to be the case for ESOL students in Scotland (Allan, 2015, The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015). However, Simpson (2020) perceives a general lack of support of multilingualism within the

ESOL classroom and suggests that there should be a transformation in ESOL practices in a way that supports students' cultural and linguistic backgrounds. Diversity in ESOL classrooms goes beyond country of origin of the learners and their first language; within the ESOL classroom, there are, generally different levels of literacy and education (Simpson, 2020), although this is not usually the case in FE classes, where students are organised in groups according to their level. This cultural and linguistic diversity in education has already been acknowledged and addressed in Scotland in 2015 with the genesis of the National Framework for Languages (NFfL), which was created by the Language Group of the Scottish Council of Deans of Education (SCDE) aiming to support and promote cultural and linguistic diversity in education (National Framework for Languages, n.d.). In addition, the Scottish government have implemented the 1+2 languages approach from P1 onwards to support plurilingualism and diversity in the country:

The Scottish Government's policy, Language Learning in Scotland: A 1+2 Approach is aimed at ensuring that every child has the opportunity to learn a modern language from Primary 1 onwards. Additionally, each child should have the right to learn a second modern language from P5 onwards. The policy should be fully implemented across the country by August 2021. Language learning is an entitlement for all from P1 to S3 (The Scottish Government, 2012, p. 1)

Although this approach does not address ESOL learners in Scotland in particular, it shows the continued focus on promoting and encouraging cultural and linguistic diversity and awareness throughout the country, by advocating not only for the children's appreciation of the role of foreign languages but also the teachers' and parents' support for their second language learning. This alone may encourage institutions and individuals to value and support ESOL learners in a way that facilitates their inclusion within the Scottish community, by understanding the challenges of learning a new language and the value of multilingualism. In addition, the NFfL highlights the role of the teacher as key to "ensur[e that] young people develop a positive attitude and enthusiasm towards language, language learning and other cultures" (National Framework for Languages, n.d.,n.p.). Although the NFfL puts its emphasis on the important role of teachers at early levels of education, this may also impact the linguistic and cultural perception of students and teachers at higher levels and, ultimately, permeate the whole discourse in Scottish education.

3.5.1 'Othering' as a mechanism of power in ESOL

Brons (2015, p.70) describes 'othering' as follows:

Othering is the simultaneous construction of the self or in-group and the other or out-group in mutual and unequal opposition through identification of some desirable characteristic that the self/in-group has, and the other/out-group lacks and/or some undesirable characteristic that the other/out-group has and the self/in-group lacks.

Othering thus sets up a superior self/in-group in contrast to an inferior other/out-group, but this superiority/inferiority is nearly always left implicit.

This social construct is a dividing practice that has been used to explain control mechanisms in societies in order to exercise power towards what is considered the difference. In the British context, this is “crucial in understanding where inequalities in the multicultural UK are generated and the negative impact they have on ethnic minority groups” (Courtney, 2017, p.29). This section will be dedicated to understanding ‘othering’ mechanisms within the peculiarities of ESOL education.

In terms of power relations in ESOL, Motha (2006), Courtney (2017) and Simpson (2020) describe a similar situation in two different contexts, Canada and the United Kingdom. In these two countries learning English is a pre-requisite to be successful, and it is assumed that once the learners acquire certain level of competency of the English language, they shift from being considered the ‘others’ to being considered part of the community. According to Simpson (2020) a nationalist monolingual ideology reinforces this idea of ‘othering’ by promoting “the importance of a standard language as a unifying ‘glue’ for a nation” (p.181) and oversees multilingualism and multicultural identities within the country. Courtney (2017) explains that, in the UK context, this British nationalist vision implies that “the critical factor in validating ‘Britishness’ is possessing a command of the nation's dominant language and having a knowledge of selective aspects of culture” (p.27); in other words, the only way for immigrants to be accepted as members of the host community is to assimilate both the language and the culture of the host country. Thus, using Brons' (2015) definition, the in-group (considered ‘superior’ in ESOL) is understood as those who have English as an L1, or are as close as possible to that model, while the out-group or ‘other’ are those who speak other languages and do not master a good level of English (and are considered ‘inferior’ in the profession). This may apply to ESOL learners, or lecturers whose first language is not English.

The aforementioned suppression of diversity and multilingualism has a direct impact on classroom practices, which may not recognise the students’ multilingual backgrounds and may ignore the use of pedagogical practices such as translanguaging that enhance multilingualism in the classroom. In her study, Courtney (2017) explores from the ESOL tutors’ perspective, the learners’ feelings towards ESOL education in the UK and describes the pressure that many UK migrants feel to “prove themselves their value in the new community” (ibid., p.26) by demonstrating a ‘good’ level of English or their commitment to achieve it. In addition, the findings of her study (ibid.) suggest that it is not only the society who perceives the learners as “deficient” (ibid., p.33) but she also argues that some ESOL tutors emphasize the learners’ lack of ability in certain skills rather than their knowledge of their previous experience and their proficiency in their first language, comparing their literacy skills to children and infantilizing behaviours. This emphasizes a model of deficiency that highlights the learners’ inability to speak English, rather than highlighting the skills that they do have, and this has detrimental effects on the profession and on the learners, affecting policy, curriculum, and the students’ sense of self and learning expectations (ibid.)

The focus of this section has been mainly on understanding 'otherness' among learners and among teachers and learners. The literature about othering practices among ESOL practitioners, especially in the Scottish context, is scarce; therefore, this study aims to contribute to fill this gap in research by investigating 'otherness' among ESOL practitioners in Scotland with a focus on Further Education.

3.6 Conclusion

Understanding the key areas that underpin this study has served to locate the study within the global context of TESOL and its current power tensions, as well as to localise the study within the Scottish ESOL context, the nature, goals and expectations of this branch of English language teaching. In addition, understanding the literature around power and how different scholars understand its different levels will be essential to guide and support both the thematic and discursive analyses in this study.

The next chapter will explore the ways in which the framework of intersectionality, firstly used by Crenshaw (1989) has been understood and shaped to serve the purposes of this particular study.

Chapter 4 - Theoretical framework: Framing intersectionality

4.1. Introduction

Grant and Osanloo (2014) compare the theoretical framework of a thesis to the blueprint for a house: the architect (or researcher) needs to create a basic structure that serves as a guide from which the rest of the house (or thesis) will be supported and developed. Thus, this chapter will be dedicated to developing an understanding of the key theories and concepts that underpin the whole study. In addition, this chapter will serve to position the research within a particular philosophical, epistemological and ontological framework; this will help the reader to understand the perspective from which this research has been conducted.

The theoretical framework of a study derives from an existing theory that has already been used, proven and accepted within the research community; however, each researcher makes a “unique application of the selected theory” (Grant and Osanloo, 2014 p.16) to fit their own investigation context and needs. As discussed in the context chapter, this study is rooted in the framework of intersectionality (Crenshaw, 1989) taking its common tenets as a starting point to define the framework but adapting it to the specific characteristics of this study.

One of the major criticisms of intersectionality theory is its ambiguity and its lack of defined methodology (Nash, 2008). However, this is precisely what makes the theory so versatile and adaptable to different research contexts. In fact, scholars such as Carbado et al. (2013) believe that although the framework was firstly discussed in legal studies, “there is no a priori place for intersectionality” (ibid., p.305) and they invite scholars and other professionals outside academia to use the intersectionality framework to analyse power structures and discrimination within any field and context. In fact, Tefera, Powers and Fischman (2018, p.8) consider intersectionality a “research imperative for education researchers” that will serve to interrogate epistemological ideas that have been rooted in the field for a long time, and contribute with new ideas, questions and concepts that have been, perhaps, unquestioned in the past.

The versatile and flexible nature of the theory also implies that I should provide a clear explanation of how the theory is understood in this particular study, and how it is employed to investigate the research questions. In order to do so, this chapter starts by defining the common tenets of intersectionality and a discussion of how this framework is operationalized in this particular thesis. Then, I introduce a discussion around methodological complexities in intersectionality that will help to set the basis for the methodology chapter. The next section of this chapter discusses the main criticisms of intersectionality, as well as a defence of the framework, and, lastly, I discuss the research possibilities of using the framework of intersectionality within education and TESOL particularly.

4.2 Conceptualising intersectionality

Despite the ambiguity of the term and the different interpretations of it, there is no doubt that most scholars in this field agree on some common characteristics which define

'Intersectionality'. Collins and Bilge (2020 p.2) provide a working definition that describes common tenets that are accepted by most scholars:

Intersectionality investigates how intersecting power relations influence social relations across diverse societies as well as individual experiences in everyday life. As an analytical tool, intersectionality views categories of race, class, gender, sexuality, class, nation, ability, ethnicity, and age - among others - as interrelated and mutually shaping one another. Intersectionality is a way of understanding and explaining complexity in the world, in people, and in human experiences.

Taking this definition as a starting point, this section will discuss six tenets of intersectionality that should be present in every intersectional study (Dhamoon, 2011; Collins and Bilge, 2020). This will help me to explore the reasons why I have chosen 'Intersectionality' as the theoretical framework of this study, and how it is understood as a theoretical and analytical framework for this particular thesis.

Tenet 1: Intersectionality is dynamic in nature.

There is consensus about the dynamic nature of intersectionality which enables the framework to expand geographically, and across time, extending its boundaries to different fields and subfields (Carbado et al., 2013) including Higher Education (Harris and Patton, 2019) and English language teaching (Kayi-Aydar, Varghese and Vitanova, 2022). Carbado et.al. (2013) consider intersectionality as a work-in-progress which is "never done, never exhausted" (p.304) and is able to be discussed within any field, even the ones that have never been considered in relation to this framework. As Dhamoon (2011) explains, Intersectionality, as an analytical approach, can move beyond its original scope of Black Women, to be applied to study other social groups, their relations and contexts. Similarly, Romero (2017) sees the dynamic and interdisciplinary nature of this theory as an opportunity for researchers to consider broader possibilities in the field of language education and explore further questions related to unexplored issues. In this study, I am taking this opportunity to explore ESOL college lecturers' identities from an intersectional perspective, aiming to identify issues related to identity and power relations in the profession that have been previously overlooked.

Tenet 2: Intersectionality can be applied generally, but it is context specific.

Although as seen above, intersectionality can be applied to different fields, Levon (2015) explains that the findings of a particular intersectional analysis are the result of very specific conditions and, therefore, it is impossible to generalise the way in which identity variables intersect. In short, in intersectional studies, understanding the context is essential for applying this framework to explore and analyse power relations (Collins and Bilge, 2020). This view implies that different research studies will identify and examine a unique view of the explored topic, providing new contributions to the field. However, there are shared structural practices that emerge from similar power structures (Smooth, 2013); a clear example of this is seen in the origins of intersectionality, when different Black feminist groups from a variety of contexts, such as Chicana, Black American, or Latino women were experiencing discriminatory practices

in America that seemed to arise from a wider power structure (Carastathis, 2016; Collins and Bilge, 2020).

Tenet 3: 'Relationality' of identity factors

Following Dhamoon's (2011) recommendation relating the considerations one should have when implementing intersectionality as the analytical framework for a particular study, it is important to consider the way the different identity factors interplay. This is what Collins and Bilge (2020, p. 33) referred to as "relationality". The concept has also been referred to as 'coalition', 'interaction', or 'dialog' among other terms (ibid.). Terminology, however, seems to be "less important" (ibid.) than understanding the emphasis of intersectionality on how different identity factors are understood as interconnected (rather than in isolation) and that this perspective can bring new possibilities to explore identity and power relations (ibid.). For example, by focusing only on exploring racial discrimination in isolation, there is a possibility of missing how discrimination is also affected by one's gender or class identities.

This relationality of factors also assumes that each identity factor can be perceived and experienced differently by each person. Rather than regarding people as an "undifferentiated mass of individuals" (Collins and Bilge, 2020 p.19), the intersectionality approach enables researchers to explore identity as multifaceted and unique to each individual (Smooth, 2013). Similarly, Levon (2015) understands identity as multifaceted and dynamic and claims that the interaction of all the variables constitutes the uniqueness of each person's identity; therefore, he agrees with Crenshaw (1989), Romero (2017) and Lykke's (2010) approach to using an intersectional analysis that understands identity variables as mutually constituting each other.

Tenet 4: 'Identity factors are changeable and socially constructed.'

Another important conceptualization when defining intersectionality is the way in which categories may be perceived and discussed within particular contexts. The work of Walby, Armstrong and Strid (2012) clearly describes the debate between perceiving categories as static or fluid in intersectional studies. On the one hand, authors such as McCall (2005) believe that by using static, well defined macrocategories to explore intersectionality, inequalities can be studied across different groups. On the other hand, other authors (Collins and Bilge, 2020) believe in taking a more fluid approach which interprets categories as changeable, and socially constructed. To resolve this dilemma, Walby, Armstrong and Strid (2012) propose understanding identity categories as social constructs which, over time have become more static due to their acceptance by social institutions. In their view, these constructs are reproduced by education institutions. However, these categories can change gradually, or suddenly, if there is a change in the social context (Smooth, 2013; Collins and Bilge, 2020). As Smooth (2013, p.23) puts it:

[The categories'] social and political meanings often change in different historical contexts, and are contested and restructured both at the level of the individual (what

it means to me and my experiences) and at the societal level (what it means to society and social systems).

In short, categories can be perceived as mostly static in the way they are understood in a particular context and historical time, but fluid as they are context and history dependent.

Tenet 5: Commitment to social justice and transformative practice

Scholars such as Crenshaw (1989), Davis (2008), Carbado et.al. (2013), Collins (2015) and, more recently, Lawrence and Nagashima (2019) and Maddamsetti (2019) highlight the power for social change and transformative practice that an intersectional analysis can offer. They agree on understanding intersectionality as an approach that aims to re-evaluate and challenge the current power dynamics pursuing an alternative discourse, asking new questions and ultimately aiming for social transformation. The importance of applying an intersectional analysis to research within the Higher Education context aiming for social change and social transformation is explained by Harris and Patton (2019 p.349) as follows:

It is important to explore how scholars do intersectionality in higher education because intersectional analyses have the power to transform knowledge, transform society and transform higher education.

However, in their study (ibid.) they criticize how the term ‘intersectionality’ has been used increasingly in Higher Education research in an oversimplistic way without further exploration of the term, but just to “express scholars familiarity with the (popularity of the) theory, without having to engage in intersectional efforts” (Harris and Patton, 2019, p. 359). This practice may, they think, devaluate the complexities of the framework and its fundamental aim of social transformation.

Within the group of scholars who engage with the approach taken by Harris and Patton (2019) in their understanding of intersectionality, it is clear that their ultimate goal is to create new perspectives on their topic aiming to change the narrative about exclusion and power hierarchies and transform the current system (Davis, 2008, Carbado et al., 2013, Collins, 2015, Lawrence and Nagashima, 2019, Maddamsetti, 2019). This is what Harris and Patton (2019 p.354) refer to as “doing intersectionality”; a complex process that involves citation practices, exploration of the *herstory*⁵ of the theory and making educated decisions about the people and the subject that are going to be analysed, as well as the methodology.

Tenet 6: Complexity

The last tenet of intersectionality is its complexity. Implementing an intersectional analysis in any study is “difficult” (Collins and Bilge, 2020, p. 34) due the “multifaceted” (ibid) and ambiguous nature (Davis, 2008) of this framework. This is because:

⁵ Herstory in original (Harris and Patton, 2019)

intersectionality aims to understand and analyse the complexity in the world, [and therefore,] it requires intricate strategies to do so (Collins and Bilge, 2020, p. 34).

Carastathis (2016) also describes the ever-expanding complexity of intersectionality explaining how exploring some interactions may uncover new power structures within a particular context that would need to be explored further. In a similar way, McCall (2005, p. 1772) refers to the complexity of intersectionality explaining that it “mirror[s] the complexity of social life” and how humans interact with each other and within the community. In an attempt to understand this complexity, and the different methodologies that scholars have employed to apply intersectionality into their studies, McCall's (2005) work has been used as a point of reference for many researchers (Davis, 2008; Stella, 2010; Collins and Bilge, 2020), and of course, it has also influenced this study. I will explore McCall's (2005) paper ‘The Complexity of Intersectionality’ in more detail in section 4.3 of this chapter.

4.2.1 The place of ‘Intersectionality’ in this study

In this study, intersectionality has been operationalised following the basic tenets described above; however, due to the vagueness and ambiguity of the framework (Davis, 2008), I will use this section to explore in more depth the ways in which intersectionality informs and was applied in this particular context.

I have taken the opportunity to use the dynamic nature of intersectionality to take the framework outside its original space of Black American feminism to explore the identities of ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges. As I will discuss in Section 4.6, intersectionality has been applied in a variety of studies which focus on areas related to language education and the TESOL context, however, this study will be the first of its kind to focus on Scottish ESOL education. Therefore, it is ‘travelling’ to an unexplored field (Romero, 2017), aiming to bring the discussion of new perspectives into Scottish ESOL education. This means that the way Intersectionality is operationalised in this study and its subsequent findings are only relevant within the context in which the study has been designed and the data collected and explored. Thus, identity variables, their intersection and how they relate to the broader context of ESOL and Further Education in Scotland, may differ if the study is replicated at a different time, or with different participants. However, it may also serve as a catalyst to a discussion of wider, associated issues and may encourage future research on similar and related contexts.

In order to avoid misusing the framework and not engaging adequately and appropriately with it, as Carastathis (2016) warns, I have followed the guidelines from Harris and Patton (2019 p.353) who emphasise the need to explore the origins of the concept of intersectionality, citing, and discussing the work of scholars from minoritized backgrounds and reflecting on how the findings of the study may influence change:

When scholars fail to cite Kimberlé Crenshaw, Patricia Hill Collins, the Combahee River Collective, Gloria Anzaldúa, and other women of color when writing and speaking about intersectionality, their perspectives, and the epistemological lenses these women crafted and contributed to, are disempowered, diminished, and decentered. It is equally imperative that scholars recognize and cite the foremothers of

intersectionality (e.g., Anna Julia Cooper, Harriet Tubman, Ida B. Wells) all of whom engaged in social movements that ultimately influenced Crenshaw's coining of the term.

I, therefore, began to explore the background of intersectionality in the context chapter, and I continue to engage with the literature of minoritized scholars throughout the thesis to ensure that I do not 'erase' intersectionality from its political origins.

In addition, it is important to clarify the way in which identity categories are perceived in relation to this study. For this research, identity categories such as gender, sexuality, L1, class, and ethnicity will be perceived as static in the way that they are very much ingrained in institutions and the profession in general (Kubota and Lin, 2006; Hume, 2013), but fluid as they can change if the context changes (McCall, 2005).

Another important aspect to define in the area of intersectional studies is the way in which the level of oppressions is understood (Dhamoon, 2011). Some studies that have employed intersectionality as a method of analysis take one identity characteristic as primary form of oppression and explore its intersections with other identity factors (see: Stella, 2010). According to Garneau (2018 p.330) this approach may be interesting for intersectional studies that aim to "see the localized and amplified effects of one specific axis of domination on the others". In this study, however, all identity categories are understood in a non-hierarchical way, and under one overarching matrix of oppression (Collins, 1990; Collins and Bilge, 2020), because the focus is not on a particular axis of oppression but on the exploration of the different axes of oppressions that may affect ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges (ibid.). This particular approach may also help to uncover new perspectives and relations of power that were not originally anticipated (Garneau, 2018; Leckie and Buser De, 2020).

Lastly, it is important to discuss the identity characteristics and intersections that will be explored in an intersectional study (Dhamoon, 2011). Initially, intersectionality was employed to explore race and gender (Crenshaw, 1989); however, as the framework developed, it has been used to consider many different identity factors and their interactions (Carbado *et al.*, 2013). Some studies that focus on specific intersections may predefine the identity characteristics that will be explored in the study (Garneau, 2018). However, as I will discuss in the methodology chapter, the identity categories explored in this study were guided by the participants' responses. The method was adopted in order to give voice to all participants and emphasize that their identities are unique, dynamic and intersectional (Varghese *et al.*, 2005) and cannot be defined by strict categories. This approach not only enabled participants to choose the way in which they wanted to talk about their own identity, but it offered them the possibility of exploring new ideas and perspectives that arose from their own responses.

4.3 Methodological challenges and categories

As explained above, complexity is one of the tenets of intersectionality. It not only refers to the way identity categories are understood, or the power structures that are explored, but it

is also reflected in the methodological choices that scholars make in order to apply intersectionality in their studies. In an attempt to categorize the different methodologies employed in intersectionality and understand how scholars manage the complexity of intersectional analysis, McCall (2005) suggested three different methodology categories.

The first category within the continuum of complexity is what she defines as “*anticategorical*” (p.1773) which is based on the deconstruction of all master categories themselves – gender, race, class, and so on – that have been socially constructed and are not based on scientific evidence. Scholars whose work falls into this approach consider these master categories an oversimplification of social relations. In their view, “nothing fits neatly” (McCall, 2005, p. 1777) into these categories, but they are used to make society more homogeneous than it actually is. Therefore, their analysis of inequalities and power relations do not consider fixed categories; this has been, among the three approaches, the “most successful in satisfying the demand for complexity” (p.1773) as it allows for a more complex analysis of identity and power structures.

The second category in the continuum of complexity (although, chronologically, the first one to be employed in intersectional studies) is the “*intracategorical*” (p.1773) approach which also questions the master categories but accepts them for the purpose of the analysis, focusing on the relationships that are generated within the people involved in the research:

The point is not to deny the importance – both material and discursive – of categories but to focus on the process by which they are produced, experienced, reproduced, and resisted in everyday life. (McCall, 2005 p.1783)

Lastly, McCall (2005) defines the *intercategorical approach* which focuses on the relationships of inequalities among different social groups, taking gender and race as the major categories of analysis. In contrast to the anticategorical approach, this one “adopts existing analytical categories to document relationships of inequalities among social groups” (p.1773). This methodology is systematically comparative; it compares different factors of the components of the different groups – gender, race, class, income and so on – creating a more complex system of analysis than a single-group analysis. In addition, research that employs this type of methodology necessarily requires a hierarchical rather than additive system of comparison.

Although McCall's (2005) model to categorise methodological complexity has been widely used or discussed by different scholars in the field (Stella, 2010; Carastathis, 2016; Garneau, 2018), she acknowledges that not all research on intersectionality can fit into these categories and that others may fit between the boundaries of two categories. As will be discussed more in-depth in the methodology chapter, the analysis for this study will not fit strictly into any of these categories; however, it is closer to McCall's (2005) *intracategorical* approach in the way that analytical categories are understood: they are challenged and questioned but accepted in order to explore the relationships of power and inequality within them.

Fig. 1. Representation of McCall's (2005) methodological approaches for intersectionality

Based on the three methodological categories proposed by McCall (2005), Choo and Ferree, (2010) suggest four alternative ways of conceptualizing methodologies employed for intersectionality studies to tackle issues of social inequality. Their suggestion is based on the potential strengths and limitations of each methodology based on aspects of “inclusion, analytical interaction and institutional primacy” (Choo and Ferree, 2010, p. 131).

The first model is what they termed as “inclusion centered” (Choo and Ferree, 2010, p. 132) which emphasizes the difference among people and focuses on giving voice to those who have been traditionally silenced or forgotten, paying special attention to those groups who are multiple-marginalized. This model is similar to McCall's (2005) *intracategorical* approach in the way that it focuses on differences of power and inequalities among individuals of a single group. Choo and Ferre (2010) argue that the main weakness of this model is that it does not give enough attention to the unmarked categories and leaves “normative standards” (ibid., p.133) unquestioned.

The second model is what Choo and Ferree (2010 p.133) define as “process centered”. This model focuses on the analysis of interactions by using comparative analysis to identify the different power structures within the society; however, they point out that categories are culturally constructed and, therefore, this kind of analysis requires a good understanding of cultural differences in order to avoid a misinterpretation of power relationships.

The “social constructional” (ibid. p.134) model is similar to McCall's (2005) *intercategorical* approach in the sense that both challenge socially constructed categories and emphasize how these categories change over time and across culture. However, this model of analysis is hierarchical rather than horizontal. This means that in this view, there are oppressions that are considered ‘primary’, or more important than others, which are considered ‘secondary’. This division depends on the perceived effect they have on a particular society.

Lastly, the model of “systemic intersectionality” (ibid. p.135) sees all types of inequalities at the same level, rather than in a hierarchical order. However, in this model, it can be difficult to discern the inequalities, as explained below:

This view of intersectionality as a complex system assumes a methodology that sees everything as interactions, not “main effects”. The challenge is to identify the local and historically particular configurations of inequalities since every system is contingent and path dependent. (Choo and Ferree, 2010 p.136)

These two different ways (McCall, 2005; Choo and Ferree, 2010) of categorizing methodologies within intersectional research shows how methodologies are not fixed, but rather, each scholar has classified methodologies according to different criteria. Ultimately, McCall (2005) and Choo and Ferree (2010) suggest that researchers may choose the one that best fits their research needs, or even consider using them all in combination to complement each other in order to create a broader and more effective analysis of inequalities. As has been explained earlier, the methodology for this study will be discussed in the following chapter; however, this initial exploration served as an indication of the ambiguity and flexibility of intersectionality in relation to selecting an appropriate methodology for a study, as well as a consideration of these issues has helped to situate the current study.

4.4 Intersectionality: Main criticisms and defence.

In previous sections it has been highlighted that intersectionality has proved to be a solid framework and that many scholars encourage its application in studies centred in the fields of social sciences and education (Davis, 2008, Lykke, 2010, Carbado et al., 2013, Tefera, Powers and Fischman, 2018, Freeman, 2019). However, the theory is not exempt from criticism; it has been described as a “fuzzy concept” (Tefera, Powers and Fischman, 2018 p.18) or an ambiguous theory as there is no consensus about what it means, how to identify the intersections themselves and what methodology is the most effective one to do so (Nash, 2008, Levon, 2015). On this note, Harris and Patton (2019) believe that the downside of such an ambiguous concept is that some institutions and organisations use the concept of intersectionality for material gains, that is, to access grants and publications, rather than for social transformation which, according to them, is the ultimate goal of this type of research. Yet, others such as Davis (2008) think that this ambiguity is precisely “the very secret of its success” (p.69) making it a “buzzword” (p.75) in many social and feminist studies. Collins (2015) explains that this ambiguity is what makes this theory flexible and dynamic and able to travel across disciplines without the boundaries of time or space.

However, Tefera, Powers and Fischman (2018) have also pointed out that due to its ambiguity, some scholars do not believe that intersectionality can be considered a “consolidated comprehensive framework” (p.14) to build any serious research in education, and that doing this can be “dangerously wrong” (p.14). In order to effectively employ intersectionality in scholarly studies, Carastathis (2016) suggests that scholars who research on intersectionality should be familiar with the term, its history and origins.

For Collins (2015) using a narrower definition for the term could be an obstacle to apply and to adapt the framework to all the different disciplines that have adopted it so far; therefore, the definition of intersectionality should serve as a “starting point for investigation rather than [an] end [point] of analysis.”(Collins, 2015, p. 3). She explains that intersectionality can be studied in three possible ways: as an individual field of study examining the different debates around it, its history and possible directions; as an analytical tool to explore new perspectives and ideas about a field or as a critical praxis, investigating how it is used for social justice projects. Following Collins' (2015) definition, this thesis makes use of intersectionality as an analytical framework to explore the multi-layered identities of ESOL practitioners in Scottish colleges. In addition, it aims to explore how lecturers' identities are perceived in the profession in order to identify any perceived instances of disadvantage based on these identities and how they might interact with the evident or implicit power structures within ESOL education departments and the broader Further Education sector in Scotland.

As a flexible and dynamic theory, intersectionality may be used to uncover new perspectives, points of view, questions and ideas that perhaps have not been previously considered within educational research, and in relation to this particular study, within the field of ESOL practitioners in Scotland. Employing this framework is precisely one of the elements that is unique in this study, and is considered by some (Carbado *et al.*, 2013; Leckie and Buser De, 2020) one of the most valuable tools in contemporary qualitative research.

4.5 Intersectionality: Research possibilities in language education

Intersectionality is a well-established research framework (Haynes *et al.*, 2020), and it is considered by some (McCall, 2005; Harris and Patton, 2019) to be one of the greatest contributions to feminist studies, where it has had its major impact, serving as an analytical lens to destabilize and subvert social binaries such as gender and race, “enabl[ing] robust analyses of cultural sites” (Nash, 2008, p. 2) and aiming to transform the system. Since 1989, the intersectionality framework has been employed in academia worldwide to examine not only gender and race but other identity variables such as class, nation, ability, ethnicity, and sexual orientation in many diverse fields such as education, social care and psychology, serving as a bridge between disciplines and creating multiple interdisciplinary theories and debates (Carbado *et al.*, 2013; Collins, 2015). This has transformed Crenshaw's (1989) initial theory into a more complex, dynamic and flexible framework that can be adapted to specific contexts in order to identify the perceived axes of oppression and their relation to power, aiming to transform the current social order and related power dynamics (Carbado *et al.*, 2013, Collins, 2015, Harris and Patton, 2019, Collins and Bilge, 2020).

In the education sector, the discussion of intersectionality is closely linked to critical education (Freire, 2000; Collins and Bilge, 2020) as it aims to challenge the status quo, question structures of power and make education more accessible, diverse, and inclusive. Scholars such as Tefera, Powers and Fischman (2018 p.viii) consider intersectionality to be “both a conceptual aspiration and a research imperative” within the field of education as it provides a framework from which to identify gaps and silences that traditional single-axis analyses have

been unable to target. As I will expound below in this section, its impact on education is clearly visible both in theory and research as well as in specific practices across educational institutions.

The framework of intersectionality has been used across all sectors of education; from childhood education to educational leadership and Higher education (Tefera, Powers and Fischman, 2018; Harris and Patton, 2019); all with a focus on the exploration of individual identity and the intersections within power dynamics, and with the ultimate goal of social transformation (Tefera, Powers and Fischman, 2018; Haynes *et al.*, 2020; Leckie and Buser De, 2020). As Leckie and Buser De (2020 p.119) highlight, one of the strengths of employing an intersectional approach in educational research is its “flexibility to include different dimensions”, enabling the researcher/s to explore a range of identity characteristics and their interactions within this field from a non-hierarchical perspective; instead of selecting one oppression as a primary struggle, exploring other secondary oppressions in relation to it.

Such theoretical discussions around intersectionality in educational research have also impacted education on a practical level. As an example, many universities and college campuses in the UK (Gunn, Morrison and Hanesworth, 2015) and the US are actively implementing initiatives to support equality and diversity in education. Some of these initiatives include intersectionality training for staff, developing legal anti-discriminatory policies and the establishment of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion teams within the institutions (Collins and Bilge, 2020). In addition, intersectionality research has positively impacted the relationship between teachers and their peers, especially by helping some teachers better understand their students’ experiences. In addition, it enables practitioners to understand the way in which different matrices of oppressions operate within their institution (Leckie and Buser De, 2020). The present study aims to contribute to this last application of intersectionality by exploring the experiences of ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges and the relations of power within their own departments, and more broadly, within their institutions.

In the context of Scotland, there are also examples of how intersectionality research is being employed to identify, among other social issues, experiences of poverty, racial inequalities and the experiences of disabled people accessing public services with a view to create relevant policies to tackle these issues (Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2019; APS Group Scotland, 2022). This is an example of the ways in which intersectionality research in Scotland has the potential to influence policymaking and transform Scottish education and society.

4.5.1 Intersectionality in (T)ESOL

There have been previous studies in TESOL that explore different identity variables following an additive model, without focusing on the intersections of the identity variables (Holliday, 2014, Kamhi-Stein, 2016). However, these additive models can be considered limiting as they may fail to identify any possible form of oppression that is created at the margins of the ‘crossroads’. As pointed out earlier, Collins (2000) believes that additive models are linked to dichotomous ways of thinking. This idea can also be applied to the work of Kamhi-Stein (2016) Holliday (2018) in the sense that one is regarded as a native speaker or not at all, one is from the English-speaking countries or is not, and so on. This binary setup implies at least three ideas. First, that there is not a middle point between being native or non-native: if you happen

to be in the ‘wrong’ side of this dichotomy, you will not have the same value as an English teacher in the job market regardless of your qualifications. Second, such categories are perceived as static, rather than fluid, which means that there is no space to move from one side of the dichotomy to the other. That means that people who are on the disadvantaged side of the dichotomy can never move to the privileged side; and those who are on the side of privilege, will remain forever privileged, thus, perpetuating categories through time (ibid.). This view is in conflict with the dynamic nature of intersectionality (Collins and Bilge, 2020). Thirdly, it implies that there is no space for those who do not strictly fit into these fixed categories; for example, one who holds a passport from an English-speaking country, but does not speak English as an L1 would not fit into such dichotomy and, therefore, the study would leave the experiences of this person outside the discussion. In order to avoid this, as explained in an earlier section of this chapter, in this study, intersectionality is understood as the interplay of many factors rather than just a “mere addition” (Lykke, 2010 p.51) of them, aligning with Collins’ (1990) view, in the sense that all oppressions are represented under the same overarching matrix of domination, and all understood from a non-hierarchical perspective.

More recently, Kayi-Aydar, Varghese and Vitanova (2022 p.1) acknowledge that the “research and pedagogical implications [of intersectionality] for English language teachers are just starting to emerge”. This statement implies that the field is moving beyond additive models to explore ‘interlocking’ characteristics. There are some examples of how intersectionality has been employed to analyse the perception of different identity factors in a variety of TESOL contexts. For example, the work of Nelson (2019) uses an intersectional framework combined with a “visual analysis” (Nelson, 2019, p. 15) to explore how race, gender and class have been represented in English language textbooks. In her study, Nelson (2019) aims to identify patterns of representation and advocate for inclusivity in English language textbooks. The work of Lawrence and Nagashima (2019) is another example of intersectionality in the TESOL context. They employ intersectionality and duoethnography to explore how their own identity as teachers influences their classroom practices. Similarly, Maddamsetti (2020) also combines parts of her own reflections with the intersectionality framework to explore how English language teachers negotiate identity in the classroom. In her study, she identifies tensions between social class and multilingualism in the classroom that, she asserts, often cause situations of privilege and marginalisation. There are other examples (see: Jenkins, 2017; Tatar, 2019) where the intersectional framework has been applied to examine hiring practices in TESOL related to the identity of job applicants. These examples demonstrate how intersectionality can successfully ‘travel’ to the field of TESOL, to explore identity and power dynamics from a variety of angles. In fact, as Kayi-Aydar, Varghese and Vitanova (2022, p. 5) state, TESOL is a global field that is “uniquely positioned” to engage in debates about identity, social identities and power structures. This ‘unique position’ can be explained partly because the field itself is about intercultural communication between people, teachers, or students, who may not share a common L1, social or cultural background, and because it involves not only teaching and learning the structure of a language, but it can also be a vehicle through which to convey ideas associated with certain values, cultures or social class (Courtney, 2017; Copley, 2018; Brown and Nanguy, 2021). For this reason, using intersectionality as an analytical framework in English language education can bring “meaningful conversations”

(Kayi-Aydar, Varghese and Vitanova, 2022, p. 7) into the field that can help to create “awareness of the multiple factors that underlie the language teaching profession” (Kayi-Aydar, Varghese and Vitanova, 2022, p. 5). Such meaningful conversations and awareness can also be applied to the specific context of this study, ESOL in Scottish Further Education, where the identities of lecturers and students are also multiple and diverse.

It is clear that there are numerous research possibilities for the intersectional framework to be employed in the field of language education. For this reason, this study aims to bring the recent interest in and discussion around intersectionality into the underexplored context of ESOL education in Scotland, to examine the multiple and diverse identities of lecturers in the College sector, with the view to uncover and discuss any perceived discriminatory practices among ESOL college lecturers.

4.6 Conclusion

This chapter has provided a definition of intersectionality, and the way it will be applied in this study. It has also further examined main criticisms of intersectionality, methodological discussions and research possibilities of the framework in the field of language education. This has served to help me define how intersectionality is understood and operationalized throughout and provided a solid justification of these choices.

From my point of view, the fact that the intersectionality framework can be used by everyone in any context enables scholars to explore a topic from a unique perspective, supported by previous research on the field. Although the framework of intersectionality was originally used by Crenshaw (1989) to explore the experiences of Black women, it has been demonstrated that this does not limit the potential use of the framework to explore any other identity variables, by “actors of different genders, ethnicities, and sexual orientations [...] to engage an ever-widening range of experiences and power structures” (Carbado et al., 2013 p.305). The aim of intersectionality is to move beyond a single-axis analysis of inequalities and discrimination (Crenshaw, 1989, Tefera, Powers and Fischman, 2018), and this can be enriched by exploring a range of identity variables, in different contexts and fields.

It is particularly important in the Scottish ESOL context to provide a unique overview of any discriminatory practices against ESOL practitioners in a way that has not been previously explored in Scotland. It is intended that this may start a discussion around this topic and invite other scholars to engage in research within the wider Scottish ESOL context from different perspectives, since “no particular application of intersectionality can, in a definitive sense, grasp the range of intersectional powers and problems that plague society” (Carbado et al., 2013 p.305).

Chapter 5: Methodology

5.1. Introduction

Every study should be carried out from a particular philosophical perspective or paradigm, which helped me as the researcher to engage in the academic discussions, select an appropriate methodology and research questions and present the findings of this study in a coherent way (Scotland, 2012). In addition, setting a clear representation of the paradigm will also help any potential reader to identify my perspective and to situate the findings within a specific context (ibid.). Therefore, the present chapter focuses on defining and justifying the selection of the paradigm, as well as its ontological and epistemological perspectives. The second part of this chapter presents the research design of this study and its implementation, defining the research methods and instruments that were employed to gather the data as well as providing an exploration of the ethical considerations for the study.

5.2. The paradigm of the study: Intersectionality within a critical paradigm

Guba and Lincoln (1994 p.107) describe a paradigm as a “set of *basic beliefs* that deals with ultimates or set principles”. It sets the worldview from which the researcher is carrying out the study, as well as their philosophical perspectives and their intentions. Their set of beliefs is “inextricably linked with the research they do” (Mack, 2010, p. 6) and informs the choice of research questions, methodologies and key theories as well as the interpretation of the findings of the study (ibid.).

This study is informed by the theory of intersectionality, discussed in the previous chapter, to explore the identity of FE ESOL lecturers in Scotland and the web of power relationships in the field, aiming to put the diverse voices of the participants at the forefront of the study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). In addition, intersectionality theory falls into a critical paradigm “with a social justice imperative” (Smooth, 2013, p. 13). Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2018) believe that the use of critical paradigms for social research is significant as they not only aim to address and understand situations of inequality, but also to challenge, question and, ultimately, change the status quo of a certain aspect of society, pursuing the emancipation of the oppressed.

The role of the researcher in making use of a critical paradigm is to address power relations and situations of oppression within a specific topic (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017); this aligns with the research aims of this study as it focuses on identifying the power relationships within ESOL Further Education by exploring ESOL lecturers’ identities and their intersections. Therefore, this paradigm helped to unveil any potential discriminatory practice within the context of this study.

Within the context of education, critical research has been carried out to examine and interrogate the relationship between schools and society exploring how the power

relationships are exercised and reproduced throughout different educational contexts as well as to question who defines the ideological interests of an educational institutions and the legitimization of such interests (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Therefore, using a critical paradigm to develop the methodology, research questions, and data collection within the context of ESOL education in Scotland enabled this study to investigate power relations among staff, and to identify any kind of discriminatory practice and its effects on the profession's diversity and, ultimately, the learning environment.

In order to understand the paradigm within which this study is situated, and to select an appropriate methodology, it is essential to consider the ontological and epistemological underpinnings that have guided and supported the study, its methodology, research questions, data collection and, ultimately, the findings (Scotland, 2012). Thus, the following sections have been dedicated to presenting the ontological and epistemological underpinnings of the study.

5.2.1 Ontology

In order to make an informed selection of the paradigm, it is essential to understand and define the ontological perspective of the study; in other words, what is “the nature of reality”(Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018 p.53) of the studied phenomenon. This enables me as the researcher to identify my own beliefs and assumptions about the nature of reality and in what way they may influence the research (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). There are mainly two contrasting ontological perspectives: objectivism, which views reality as “undeniable truths” (Leedy and Ormrod, 2020, p. 25) that are already created, fixed and measurable and the role of the researcher is to discover them; and constructivism, which understands reality as complex and changeable as the product of social processes, and where each person will have their own way of understanding and interpreting reality (Tuli, 2011; Scotland, 2012; Rahi, 2017).

The ontological position of critical paradigms like the one chosen for this research falls into the second perspective. This perspective believes that reality has been shaped by factors such as gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, values, and politics, that have influenced the way people think and act, as well as the power relations between them (Scotland, 2012), “privileging some views of reality and under-representing others” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 53). Objectivists, on the other hand, believe that reality is “out there” (Tuli, 2010 p.101) and it is the duty of the researcher to discover it being as objective as possible and without interfering in the findings with their previous ideas or thoughts (ibid.).

In previous chapters, the Foucauldian idea of ‘Truth’ (Foucault, 1980) was described as socially constructed and subject to change, but also as a construct which shapes the discourse of the profession in a way that seems to benefit a particular type of ESOL practitioners over others. By employing a critical paradigm such as intersectionality, the legitimacy of this idea of ‘Truth’ was analysed “uncover[ing] the vested interests at work that may be occurring consciously or subliminally, revealing to participants how they may be acting to perpetuate a system which keeps them either empowered or disempowered” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018 p.54)

or even simultaneously empowered and disempowered by different systems of oppression, depending on the context (Smooth, 2013).

5.2.2 Epistemology

Epistemology is concerned with the relationship between the researcher and the subject of research (Rahi, 2017). There are two main epistemological positions depending on how the researcher understands the discovering of the world. These positions correspond with the two ontological perspectives explained above. On the one hand, researchers who choose an objectivist ontology will have a positivist epistemology. They believe that the researcher's previous thoughts and ideas should be separated from the research so that they do not influence the results. Instead results come from empirical and experimental means that are directly observable. This view is generally employed in natural sciences such as biology or physics (Tuli, 2010). On the other hand, the researchers who hold a constructivist ontology will also hold an interpretivist epistemological position that understands the discovery of the ideas through an inductive process rather than testing facts and hypothesis. Interpretivists rely on personal contact with participants to gather a more detailed and richer dataset, which is not generalizable but explains a specific phenomenon in a specific context (Tuli, 2010). The epistemology of this study falls into in interpretivist position as it focuses on power relations between people and their perception of reality rather than on set facts.

For critical paradigms such as the one employed for this study, epistemology is understood from a subjectivist position, where my interpretations are not value-free, but rather they add value to the research findings and place the findings of the research within a specific historical and societal context (Guba and Lincoln, 1994, Tuli, 2010). This is explained by Lykke (2010 p.127-128) as follows:

The knower will always be anchored to a specific historical, societal and bodily material context, which frames and influences her or his knowledge-producing practices. This axiom of the interconnectedness of context and knower, [...], is shared by many feminists and other critical epistemologists who consider science and knowledge-producing practices to be part of society and not as something that simply follows its own internal logic of development.

Therefore, the findings of this study should be understood within the particular historical, geographical context within which the study is situated rather than detached from the surrounding context. Thus, the power relations and any perception of unequal practices that may be present or occur within the context of ESOL in Further Education in Scotland can only be perceived, explored and understood within the specific historical context, and societal infrastructure in which the research has taken place. The data in this study was analysed using thematic analysis and CDA, and in both cases, the findings rely on my interpretation of the text (Fairclough, 1989). Consequently, this is aligned with the subjectivist epistemological position because the aim of the research was not to create generalisable findings that are true for any context, but to gain in-depth non-generalisable understanding of the studied phenomenon, or as Kivunja and Kuyini (2017 p.34) explained, interpretivist researchers focus on "understand[ing] the individual rather than the universal laws".

5.3. Research design and implementation

In this section, I explore the methodological choices that I made in designing the study, and I discuss the implementation, including the changes that were made to the original plan, and the reason for these changes.

5.3.1 The selection of the methodology of the study: Qualitative research

“Methodology is a research strategy that translates ontological and epistemological principles into guidelines that show how research is conducted” (Tuli, 2011 p.102). In this sense, once the paradigm of the study has been decided, and the ontological and epistemological perspectives have been explored, the discussion should lead to the selection of the methodology that should be employed in the study (Tuli, 2011). For this particular study, a qualitative methodology was employed as it was deemed to be the most appropriate approach for gathering and analysing relevant data to address the research questions. The rationale for this decision is discussed below.

Regardless of the chosen research paradigm of the study, both qualitative and quantitative research were considered; however, it was important to undertake a close evaluation of the strengths and weaknesses of each type of methodology in order to select the one that would be more suitable for this study, or even decide to use them in combination to provide different perspectives on the topic (Guba and Lincoln, 1994).

Quantitative research tends to focus on limited number of variables, convert the data into precise mathematical formulas and detach them from any form of context (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). This type of methodology has traditionally been considered as “ultimately valid, or of high quality” (Guba and Lincoln, 1994 p.106), compared to qualitative studies which have been perceived as less valuable due to their narrower focus and lack of generalisability of the findings. As pointed out by Seidman (2013), it was not until recently that qualitative research gained popularity with social researchers (Tuli, 2011), especially in the field of education.

Despite the traditional ‘prestige’ of quantitative methods, there are certain types of research questions which cannot be explored using a quantitative methodology. This is the case in this particular study, which focused on the participants’ identities, views and perceptions of diversity in Scottish FE ESOL departments. Using a qualitative methodology seemed to be a more suitable approach for a study with this focus (Tuli, 2011; Bryman, 2012).

In addition, in quantitative studies context is not usually considered relevant as it is believed to affect the rigor and generalisability of the findings (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). On the contrary, for studies that employ qualitative methodologies context is considered to be vital to understand the exact circumstances in which the study was conducted, and the influence this had on the study. As Bryman (2012, p. 392) puts it “qualitative findings tend to be oriented to the contextual uniqueness and significance of the aspect of the social world being studied”. In order to address this particularity of qualitative studies, I included a detailed description of the background of the study in chapter 2, and discussions of relevant contextual elements and

their influence on the findings at different points throughout the thesis, as well as a detailed description of the participants of this study in chapter 6.

On this particular point, Guba and Lincoln (1994) explain that qualitative research can provide more detailed contextual information than quantitative research, which may be useful to uncover *emic* (insider) perspectives on a topic. They describe how in some cases, the *etic* (outsider) perspective may have “little or no meaning” (ibid. p.106) in relation to the *emic* perspective of the studied group. In other words, general perspectives on a topic, may not be useful to explore a particular context. For example, the broad topic of intersectionality in ELT has been previously explored by other scholars such as Romero (2017) and Maddamsetti (2019); however, their studies are based on different contexts, and their findings may or may not be relevant for the Scottish ESOL context. A qualitative approach enabled the researcher to discover the *emic* views that were relevant to the particular context that was studied. In addition, according to Leedy (2015 p.271), qualitative research can be potentially useful for uncovering “key problems [and] obstacles” that occur within the studied phenomenon. This is relevant in this particular research as one of the aims of the study was to identify any perceived discriminatory practices and their intersections that occur within ESOL departments in Scottish colleges.

Another key difference between qualitative and quantitative studies is the way in which participants are considered within the study, and the relationship between participants and researchers. In quantitative methodologies, the researcher is usually “uninvolved” (Bryman, 2012, p. 408) with the research participants, as they tend to be perceived as mere objects of research, and the researcher “ignore[s] an individual’s emotions and feelings or environmental context” (Rahi, 2017 p.2). On the contrary, in qualitative research participants are treated as people who are “writers of their own story” (Tuli, 2010 p.101), which is an empowering process that gives voice to their own realities and experiences (ibid.). As Bryman (2012, p. 399) puts it, through a qualitative methodology “the social world must be interpreted from the perspective of the people being studied, rather than as though those subjects were incapable of their own reflections on the social world”; however, participants’ behaviours and reflections should be understood within the context they are being studied, otherwise this can lead to misinterpretations (ibid.). In order to understand the participants’ views, it is common for the researcher to be closely involved with the participants and to position themselves ‘inside’ the research context (Bryman, 2012). This characteristic of qualitative methodologies is very much in line with interpretivist epistemologies (ibid.). In this particular study, the participants’ perceptions of identity and power relations in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges was key to exploring the research questions and, therefore, their own interpretations of the world were at the forefront of the study. As I discussed in chapter 1 of this thesis, in order to position myself as an ‘insider’ in this study, I located the study in a familiar context which helped me to understand the participants’ experiences in relation to the context of ESOL, identity and the Scottish college sector.

Quantitative approaches aim to avoid the influence of the researcher on the study results. On the contrary, qualitative researchers believe that the researcher's interpretation of the data plays a crucial role on the analysis and, ultimately, on the findings of the study (Guba and Lincoln, 1994). The researcher is "not neutral" (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018, p. 302); we bring our own biases, views, and interpretations into the research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). For this reason, it is essential to include a detailed description of the researcher's positionality within the study, their biases and personal experiences that might influence the interpretation of the data (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018); I presented this in chapter 1 as, by placing it at the beginning of the thesis, I established the perspective from which to understand the study. In addition, self-reflexivity is another key element of qualitative studies, where the researcher explores the way in which their own values and biographies influence the study. I embedded this reflexive activity throughout the study, and I refer to it explicitly at different points in the thesis. This, however, does not mean that my own views and values remained static throughout the research; in studies of this kind, researchers should be open to modify their views and biases after or during the exploration of the research questions (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). I explore this in the last chapter of this thesis.

As explained in the previous chapter, this study was firmly situated within an intersectional framework. This kind of study situates knowledge in the "subjectivities and lived experiences of both researcher and participants and is deeply reflexive" (Freeman, 2019 p.1) in an attempt to identify and unveil the different systems of oppressions within a specific context and field. A qualitative approach was selected for this study as it could provide a new perspective on intersectionality in intersectionality in ELT in a context that was not explored before. In addition, the study addressed the ways in which the Scottish ESOL context differs or resembles the experiences reported in other studies on related topics.

5.3.2. Research methods/instruments

The choice of research paradigm, the ontological and epistemological underpinnings and the methodology chosen for a specific study prescribe the methods or instruments for the data collection (Tuli, 2010). A study which is placed within a constructivist ontology and an interpretivist epistemology is expected to use data collection instruments that allow a non-numerical data analysis technique in order to have an in-depth analysis of the participants' views and experiences (ibid.). This can be explored through different research methods including observations, surveys or exploration of policies and documents from a particular educational institution (Seidman, 2013).

The choice of a particular research instrument depends on the purpose of the study and the research questions. This particular study aimed to give voice to the experiences of FE ESOL lecturers in Scotland in order to uncover any perceived unequal practice related to the perception of their identity and others'. Therefore, for a study of this kind, Leedy (2015 p.273.) notes that it is common for "researchers [to] depend exclusively on lengthy interviews" with a relatively small number of participants. This enabled an in-depth and multifaceted exploration of the topic of research.

Other types of instruments such as observations were discarded as, at the time this study was conducted we were in a national lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, which included strict guidelines from the Government to stay at home (*ITimeline of UK government coronavirus lockdown and restrictions, 2022*) and college classes were moved to an online setting. In normal circumstances, using participant observations in their social context in combination with interviews might have been helpful to explore power structures in their natural setting. However, as I explored in the limitations section in chapter 8, this was not possible at the time due to the aforementioned restrictions.

5.3.2.1. Semi-structured interviews

The purpose of interviews is not to test a preexisting theory or hypothesis, but rather to understand the lived experiences of the participants and the meaning they make of it (Seidman, 2013). The interview process is considered to be “one of the most powerful tools” (Carter et al., 2014 p.545) to collect rich information about perspectives and experiences of people working within the Scottish ESOL context, as it enables the participants to use their own voice to articulate their views and to make sense of their lived experiences.

This type of interviews was useful for me as a researcher to explore in-depth the social and educational issues related to intersectionality and perceived unequal practices in the ESOL departments in Scottish colleges through the participants stories (Seidman, 2013, Gray, 2018). Thus, my role as a researcher during the interview process was to show that other people’s stories are important and that “we are not the center of the world” (Seidman, 2013 p.9). Hence, most of the talk was done by the participants but it was my responsibility to be supportive and alert to any pauses, questions or expressions that might be relevant for the analysis (Leedy, 2015).

An additional positive aspect of interviews is that they enable participants to reflect on certain topics without the need to write them down on paper, which in some cases can make participants uncomfortable (Seidman, 2013, Gray, 2018). In addition, interviews seem to be a better method to gain personalised feedback, and allows clarification of responses, something that is not possible with other research instruments such as questionnaires. This enabled me to delve into the participants’ responses and add or modify questions about a certain topic that may seem relevant for the study (Gray, 2018). On the contrary, other instruments such as questionnaires do not leave space for clarification of any ambiguity or developing a certain topic (Gray, 2018).

The selection of the research instruments for this study was also informed by a consideration of the possible drawbacks of semi-structured compared to other methods such as questionnaires and surveys. First, in order to undertake face-to-face semi-structured interviews with participants, I was required to make direct contact with participants, and this can be potentially more difficult than in other methods such as questionnaires, exploration of policies, or surveys where a direct contact with participants is not essential (Seidman, 2013). However, this direct contact with participants is especially relevant in this type of research where the discourse of the interviews was critically analysed (Fairclough, 1989) and the responses are about identity and power structures, a topic that might be considered sensitive at times. In this sense, having direct contact with participants allowed instant clarification of

potentially complex concepts such as how identity is understood in this study, or any other relevant aspects that arise from the conversation with participants. In addition, some scholars such as Gray (2018) claim that other methods such as questionnaires may be more time effective. This is a logical claim as having a conversation with participants in the form of semi-structured interviews requires a considerable amount of time from both participants and researcher, and then, the transcription of these interviews also take a considerable amount of time (Seidman, 2013). I took this into account when planning the timeline of this study, allowing sufficient time to carry out the interviews, and using AI platforms such as Otter.ai (otter.ai, 2023) to assist with the interview transcriptions.

In this way, the literature consulted informed the choice of research instrument which was employed for the current study; lengthy semi-structured interviews and open questions with participants. The purpose of these interviews was to explore the research questions of the study; therefore, the interview questions were designed around issues of power hierarchies, unequal practices, othering mechanisms and ESOL, although there is also space for prompt questions that emerge from participants' responses and that contribute to the production of relevant data for this particular study (ibid.). An example of the interview schedule has been included in Appendix 2 of this document.

5.3.3 Sample selection

Qualitative studies of this kind tend to focus on a smaller number of participants than quantitative studies as this enables an in-depth and detailed conversation with each participant (Tuli, 2010) and "gives enormous power to the stories of relatively few participants" (Seidman, 2013 p.59). However, the exact number of participants that are needed to fully address the research questions of a study depends on a number of variables, such as the nature of the study, and the researcher's needs (Seidman, 2013). For this reason, Seidman (2013) suggests two factors that should influence this decision. The first is sufficiency; the researcher should consider if the chosen number of participants is sufficient to provide an adequate response to the research question. Although, as noted below, initially I aimed for a larger sample, the final number of participants in this study (nine) is deemed adequate because the collected data had sufficient depth that enabled me as a researcher to address the research questions. The second factor is saturation of information; having too many participants would have resulted in repetition which would have not added new information that could enrich the answers to the research questions of the study. In addition, I could have had too much data from which to draw any conclusions. Thus, the number of participants in this study provided me with sufficient data and allowed me to thoroughly explore and reflect on the insight provided by the participants during the interviews. Due to the nature of this study, it was my intention to give voice to the stories of these participants and to go for depth rather than breadth.

Other factors that I had to consider before making this decision was the length and timescale of the study. In this case, the UWS guidelines for PhD thesis (University of the West of Scotland (UWS), 2023) indicate that the study should have a maximum of 80,000 words and take between 26 and 48 months to complete.

Based on these factors, the selection of the sample of the study was originally planned according to the following process, which involved contacting different colleges directly in order to get consent to conduct the study:

1. Contact the principals of different Scottish colleges by email asking for consent to carry out the study (Appendix 4).
2. Following consent from the principals, email potential participants individually inviting them to participate in the study
3. Arrange suitable time/date for the interviews with those who agreed to participate.

During April 2021 I contacted three different college principals. However, I did not get consent from any of them to contact ESOL lecturers in the colleges as “members of staff [were] currently working under very challenging circumstances with the prospect of a return to normality being many months away”⁶. All three made reference to the pandemic and the additional workload that it created for staff.

As a consequence, I had to modify my plan to recruit participants for the study. Due to the limited possibility of networking due to the restrictions of the pandemic, I decided to contact potential participants mainly through two different methods: firstly, through an open call for participants posted on different social media platforms such as Twitter and LinkedIn, from which I expected to get some engagement from people interested in participating, and secondly, through a snowballing process, that consists of asking the first possible participants to forward the invitation to other colleagues who may be interested in participating (Rahi, 2017). This way, I expected to recruit between 18 and 20 participants for the study. The open call was published on social media in June 2021, and it was liked and shared by colleagues from the sector. However, only 10 participants contacted me to express interest in taking part on the study. In the end, only 9 participants were able to participate.

Considering the unprecedented times that we were living in, where people were affected by the pandemic in many ways (mentally, physically and professionally), and given the sensitive nature of the research which focuses on identity and power, I concluded that it was not ethical to continue looking for participants. Having come to this conclusion, I moved to arrange the interviews during the summer and early autumn of 2021.

When potential participants contacted me in response to my social media posts or referrals from others (through snowballing), I sent them a ‘Participant information sheet’ (appendix 1) where, in line with the UWS ethics guidelines, the nature and purpose of the study, and the participant's involvement were explained. I also sent them a consent form (appendix 3) to be signed before the interview by those who, having considered the information about the study, agreed to participate. In addition, I made myself available to answer any questions they may have had about the study, the interview, or how the information was going to be treated.

Interviews were arranged online through a virtual meeting platform and lasted approximately 1 hour with each candidate. After the interviews, participants were given the opportunity to debrief by having an off the record discussion of any issues that might have caused distress.

⁶ Quotation from email response from a college principal.

Some participants took this opportunity to follow up some of the information they disclosed during the interviews. Others, however, did not request a debriefing session, as they felt it was unnecessary despite the sensitivity of the topic. Despite the small number of participants, the interviews produced rich and varied data as all participants were open to have in-depth conversations about the issues presented in the interview schedule.

5.4 Analysis of the data

The recorded data from the interviews was transcribed in order to facilitate the analysis and to protect the anonymity of the participants (Gray, 2018). Due to the small number of participants, and in order to have a richer understanding of the data, I undertook two different, but complementary, types of analyses. Firstly, I undertook a thematic analysis of the interviews where my aim was to identify common, and unique ideas among the different participants (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Once this first analysis of the data was completed, I conducted a second analysis using Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). This second part of the analysis has enabled me to analyse the language and identify the power structures that are embedded in the participants' discourses (Wodak, 2002).

The two types of analysis have been developed separately and presented in two different chapters. However, it is important to view them as complementary in order to fully understand the richness of the analysis. As discussed in previous sections, the purpose of a study of this kind is not to generate generalisable findings but rather to describe unique stories that apply to the particular context in which the study is located (Guba and Lincoln, 1994; Leedy, 2015; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). However, the findings were also compared and contrasted with findings of previous studies (discussed in the literature review) to consider how they relate to them.

5.4.1 Thematic analysis

According to Braun and Clarke (2006 p.78) thematic analysis "should be seen as a foundational method" in qualitative studies that allows researchers to identify and analyse the common patterns or themes that appear in the data. Therefore, this type of analysis was conducted before CDA as it was an opportunity for me to familiarise myself with the data before undertaking a deeper analysis of the discourse itself.

One characteristic of the thematic analysis that has been highlighted by Braun and Clarke (2006) is its flexibility. The intention of using thematic analysis in the present study was to discover the shared and different views on the topic of intersectional identities and unequal practices in the further education context of ESOL in Scotland.

In order to undertake this kind of analysis, it was important to acknowledge my role as a researcher as well as my positionality as I am responsible for identifying the themes and subthemes that emerge from the data and the relevance of each theme in relation to the research questions of the study (ibid.) and my own biases and perceptions affect the way the findings are understood. As discussed earlier, the exploration of my positionality in the study

was presented in chapter 1. However, throughout the thesis I reflected on how it influenced the analysis.

According to Braun and Clarke (2006), there is not a common guideline or specification of what can be considered a theme within a specific dataset; as a researcher I was responsible for judging what could or could not be relevant to answer the research questions of the study (ibid.). Researchers must ensure that the development of the themes is rigorous and systematic (Bryman, 2012). To assist with this, I used NVivo, which is a specialised qualitative research software that allows researchers to organise and make sense of qualitative data. However, after initial analysis using NVivo, I decided to conduct the main analysis manually as this allowed me to immerse myself in the text and engage more deeply with it.

The thematic analysis was conducted following the steps suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006). Firstly, I became familiar with the data by transcribing it and reading it multiple times while identifying initial ideas. After this, I started coding the data and arranging it into possible themes and subthemes in relation to the research questions. Following this, I reviewed and defined the themes, creating clear definitions for each of them. Lastly, the analysis concluded with a written account of the findings in relation to the research questions of the study; this account can be found in chapter 6. However, as Bryman (2012) points out, this process is not linear. During the analysis process, I had to move back and forth to compare ideas, look for gaps or contradictions, and review the process, aiming for a rigorous analysis of the data. A more detailed description of this process can be found in chapter 6.

As explained earlier in this chapter, this study is situated within a constructivist ontology, a position that believes that reality is socially constructed by the many factors that affect individuals and society and, therefore, there is not just one, singular reality for everyone (Scotland, 2012, Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Rather, there are multiple realities, that can be perceived and interpreted differently by different individuals. In this sense, there is space to accept contradictory interpretations of a single issue. This means that the thematic analysis of the data may identify contradictory realities, but they should all be accepted as valid within this perspective.

5.4.2. Critical Discourse Analysis

The second approach that I used to analyse the data from the semi-structured interviews with the participants was Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). This type of analysis enables an exploration of “the relationship between language and power” (Wodak, 2002 p.6). While the thematic analysis facilitates the discovery of common patterns in the data, CDA enables an exploration of both explicit and concealed power relations and helps to unmask ingrained beliefs that occur within the specific context of a study, as “language can be used to challenge power, to subvert it, [and] to alter distributions of power” (Wodak, 2002 p.11). However, it is important to remember Fairclough's (1989 p.3) words in relation to power and language:

I am not suggesting that power is *just* a matter of language. [...] Power exists in various modalities, including the concrete and unmistakable modality of physical force.

Although language plays a huge role in shaping society, creating, and maintaining relations of power, it is, by no means, the only way of exercising power. Although power was discussed in more depth in the literature review chapter, it seemed pertinent to emphasize the role of language and CDA in relation to the overreaching framework of power.

Mullet's (2018) work has been instrumental in understanding the various schools of thought and approaches to conducting CDA. It has given me a comprehensive view of the purpose of CDA and its relevance to this specific study. She describes discourse as the “talk, text and media that express ways of knowing, experiencing and valuing the world” (ibid.2018 p.119), therefore, the analysis of the discourse can take many forms.

As discussed in an earlier section, for this study the data was gathered from semi-structured interviews, which were recorded and transcribed. Therefore, the discourse analysed in this study was in the form of conversations where the participants shared their own story and presented their perspective about how identity characteristics of college ESOL lecturers interact and intersect, and whether the way in which different identity features are perceived in the profession may cause unequal practices in the field. This was vital in exploring the way in which participants choose to use language, consciously or unconsciously, to express their own way of experiencing reality and power as “language not only expresses meaning but also constructs and establishes meaning about the world we experience” (Thompson, Rickett and Day, 2018 p.98).

There is not just one single approach to undertaking CDA, however, what is common in studies that employ CDA as a method of analysis is that they aim for “enlightenment and emancipation” (Wodak, 2002 p.10) of those who have been traditionally silenced, oppressed or otherwise (ibid.). This study aims to do so by putting the participants’ voices and experiences at the forefront, investigating their multiple identities and their intersections. This allowed me to understand, through their own experience, any perceived unequal practices in Scottish ESOL departments that arise from the way in which identities are perceived in the profession.

The analysis of the discourse was conducted following guidelines created by Fairclough (1989), Wodak (2002) and Mullet (2018). They suggest focusing on the language used by the participants by exploring the way in which the vocabulary is used to create an idea of otherness or inclusivity, the choice of grammatical structures, metaphors and word order, and other linguistic features such as pauses, hesitations and laughter and the rule of three, which refers to the idea that concepts, arguments, or themes are often presented in threes to create a rhythm and make information more memorable and persuasive (Fairclough, 1989).

5.5. Reliability and credibility

The concept of credibility is used in interpretivist research, instead of the concept of validity typically employed within positivist research, to refer to the trustworthiness and authenticity of the data (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). This should be ensured by any researcher who aims for rigorous findings and acceptance within the research community. However, as Evans (2004) highlights, this is almost impossible to achieve, and researchers can only aim for “pursuing validity” (ibid. p.61), or credibility in this case, by undertaking the necessary measures for it.

Firstly, Evans (2004) suggests identifying and explaining key concepts in order to reduce any potential ambiguity and ensure that the study is coherent. In this study, this has been pursued by providing a glossary of key terms, and a theoretical framework chapter which attempts to outline and justify the key theories that support the study. As explained in earlier sections, this type of research is not concerned with replicability of the research, or the production of generalizable findings; rather, another way of *pursuing* credibility within interpretivist research is by ensuring that the researcher contextualise the findings and address their own biases. In this study, this is ensured by providing a detailed discussion of the context of the study in chapter 2, as well as explaining how the research has been designed and implemented. In addition, at the beginning of chapter 6 I have included a discussion of the participants without breaching their privacy and anonymity in order to follow the ethical considerations of this study.

Qualitative research values self-reflexivity at every stage of the research as a way to acknowledge the impact of the researcher's positionality on the study and evaluate the potential effects that the study may have on every person involved and on the broader research community (Parry, 2020). In order to pursue this, Leedy (2015) suggests asking questions such as "Might I be wrong?" (p.279) while analysing the data. In addition, trustworthiness and credibility within a qualitative study of this kind is also assured by "transparent articulation of the researcher's standpoint" (Mullet, 2018 p.120). I engaged in self-reflexivity throughout the study, and I have included relevant reflections at various points in the thesis, including a section on my positionality in chapter 1.

5.6. Potential limitations

At the time of designing the research, I reflected on the potential limitations of the study. The intention was to anticipate the challenges that I might encounter during the process of conducting the research. I decided to include this section in this chapter for two reasons; first, to ensure that I was as transparent as possible about the research process (Mullet, 2018), and second, to give me an opportunity to reflect on this during the discussion of the 'actual' limitations of the study, which are presented in the last chapter of this study.

The first and, perhaps, more obvious potential limitation of this study is the timeframe in which this study must be completed. The study itself is part of a PhD programme that should be completed within "at least 33 months of full-time study" (University of the West of Scotland - Study options, 2020) and last no longer than four years, with a word limit between 60,000 and 100,000 words (ibid.), as it is typical from this type of programmes in the United Kingdom. This limits the study in two ways, first in the time in which it must be completed and second, in its length, which also has an impact on the selection of the number of participants and the length of each chapter.

Another potential limitation could have been finding suitable participants for the study that were willing to engage in the interview process and agree on a suitable time and date for the interview to take place. This could have been impacted by the COVID-19 restrictions, which

only allowed the people involved to meet in an online environment using platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Zoom or Skype.

5.7. Ethics

Addressing ethical considerations is central to any research. This study was underpinned by the values of qualitative research, and was informed by Freeman's (2019, p.7) argument that ethical discussions are not just a "a bureaucratic move, but [...] a reflexive move that shows the researchers understand that no matter how much they wish it didn't, power always plays a role in the process".

In sensitive matters such as educational research which involves human subjects as is the case of this particular study (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018) ethical debates should be present "before, during, and after the process of conducting research in conjunction with the participants" (Freeman, 2019 p.7). Such ethical considerations should involve reflecting on the impact that the research may have on the participants, the relationship between participants and researcher, the topics explored in the research and the positionality of the researcher in order to minimize any possible negative effect that the study may have. These considerations became especially relevant in research after World War II, when the experiments carried out by Nazi doctors involved human prisoners and basic human rights were violated (Seidman, 2013). This led to the Nuremberg Code (United Nations, 1949) which was adopted by the United Nations to ensure that all human subjects participating in any type of study should be volunteers and should be informed of any implications that the study may have. Although this particular study did not put the participants' lives at risk, it may have had an impact on the participants in other ways as they were asked to talk about their own experiences which, in some cases, might have caused discomfort (Seidman, 2013). In this situation, it is important that potential participants are fully aware of the nature of the study, possible risks that may affect their decision to take part in the study, what their participation in the research will involve and their right to withdraw after they have agreed to participate (Denscombe, 2010; Seidman, 2013; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Before I contacted any potential participants, I submitted an ethics application to the UWS School of Education and Social Sciences ethics committee. The recruitment process started after I had received ethical approval to conduct the research. As stated in an earlier section of this chapter, I sent potential participants an information sheet with details about the study and what their participation in it would involve. I also made myself available to answer any additional questions. Those who agreed to participate were asked to sign a consent form before the interview. After the interview, participants were given the opportunity to debrief. I have offered a reflection on my relationship with participants as part of my positionality in chapter 1, and I discuss this briefly again in section 5.7.1 of this chapter.

I kept the data secure in line with the Data Protection Act, and followed relevant UWS protocols to ensure the participants' privacy. I stored the data from the interviews in a password protected system only accessible to me, and used the data only for the purposes of this study. I referred to the participants as Participant 1, Participant 2, Participant 3 etc, and

removed from the transcripts their names, the name of their colleges, and any other information that could reveal their identity.

As a PhD student at the University of the West of Scotland, my ethical choices were guided by the following principles that are included in the guidelines for ethical practice (University of the West of Scotland (UWS), 2021):

- **Honesty:** according to this principle, the researcher should be honest about the intentions of their work, and in reporting the findings. In this particular study this was ensured by providing participants and readers with detailed information about the study and by being truthful at each stage of the research, including the reporting.
- **Rigour:** this was ensured by using appropriate methods to explore the research questions, and by contextualising the findings with relevant and up-to date academic literature.
- **Transparency:** I ensured transparency by reflecting on my own biases and perceptions in relation to the topic and findings, and by sharing these reflections in the thesis. In addition, I was open to any questions about the research that participants had during the interviews.
- **Respect and care:** as discussed above, I ensured anonymity and privacy for the participants of the study by removing any specific data that could identify them. In addition, after the interviews participants were given time off the record to debrief. Additionally, I ensured respect and consideration for both my current and former colleagues by omitting any details about my own career that could have negatively impacted them.

5.7.1 Researcher and participants

As part of the ethical considerations for the study, it was important for me to reflect on the relationship between the participants and myself as the researcher. This reflection is particularly important in intersectional research, where power is being examined as part of the research topic itself. During the interview process I was aware of being in a privileged position of power as I was the researcher of the study (Fairclough, 1989); however, this unequal power relation between participants and researcher can be negotiated and minimized in different ways.

First, the active role that the participants played in the research process was acknowledged by using the terminology of ‘participant’ rather than ‘interviewee’ or ‘respondent’ (Seidman, 2013); without the participant’s collaboration it would not be possible to undertake a study of this kind. In addition, I sought to minimize the unequal power relation between researcher and participant by aiming to portray the participants’ views in an accurate way: this means ensuring transparency in the way the data was interpreted and acknowledging any bias I might have and the way in which this might influence the analysis of the data and the conclusions (Parry, 2020).

5.7.2 Researcher's reflexivity

In qualitative research, reflexivity is a “central component” (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018 p.302) of the process. As stated in the positionality section in chapter 1, there is not an ‘outsider’ perspective from which to approach a study of this kind. Therefore, rather than trying to hide or eliminate this subjectivity that being an insider offered me, which seems impossible within an interpretivist research perspective, I followed Cohen, Manion and Morrison’s (2018) suggestion to engage in an in-depth exploration of my own bias, experiences and background in relation to the research topic reflecting on the influence this may have on the interpretation of the data. This also provides a perspective from which this study should be understood and situates me and my study within a particular “place and time” (Freeman, 2019 p.7).

This study was approached from the perspective of a European, young, white, bisexual female scholar. It was necessary to reflect on my own identity to understand the perspectives of the participants of the study who may or may not share similar identity factors and experiences with me. However, I understand diversity within the ESOL context, where people of different backgrounds, ages, and contexts will mix together with the aim of teaching and learning English; therefore, it was my duty to portray the different views that I encountered in a fair and honest way.

5.8. Conclusion

This chapter has provided a thorough description of the practical process of conducting this study, and the ways in which it was developed. Understanding the design of the study and how it was implemented was an essential part of the thesis as it dictated the way in which the data was analysed and the findings reported in the next two chapters were developed; the following image provides a summary of the main concepts of the methodology and research design employed in this study.

Fig. 2. Summary of the research design.

As explained above, this research falls within a critical paradigm understood within a constructivist ontology and a subjectivist epistemology; therefore, a qualitative approach was used, relying on semi-structured interviews to gather the data which was then analysed in two ways: thematically, and using CDA.

Chapter 6: Findings part 1: Thematic analysis

6.1 Introduction and description of the thematic analysis process

As explained in the methodology chapter, the findings of this study are presented in two separate but complementary chapters. In this chapter, I present the findings from the thematic analysis of the interviews.

As indicated in the methodology chapter, with the permission of the participants, I audio recorded the interviews. I then transcribed each interview and used Braun and Clarke's (2006) thematic analysis process to identify themes. This process is well established and widely used to analyse and report patterns within qualitative data (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). This is because it provides a systematic but also flexible way to analyse text-based data, such as interview transcripts, allowing researchers to uncover insights related to their research questions (Leedy and Ormrod, 2020).

I used a combination of inductive and deductive analysis. According to Braun and Clarke (2006), in inductive thematic analysis, theme development is driven exclusively by the data, whereas deductive thematic analysis is guided by a theoretical framework. As noted earlier in the thesis, my own personal experiences and the literature review indicated that certain identity characteristics are valued more than others in the ESOL profession, and the possession of these characteristics creates privilege while lack of these characteristics is seen as disadvantage. Though, I noted that, in some cases, privileging and disadvantaging characteristics co-exist and I was interested in exploring how such intersections are experienced. For this reason, intersectionality appeared to be a helpful theoretical framework for this study. However, my thematic analysis was mostly inductive, as I was keen to allow the voices of the participants to guide the process. Once I identified the themes that emerged from the data, I considered them in relation to the theoretical framework, to see how they related. In this sense, an element of deduction was used but the thematic analysis was mainly inductive.

Below, I have outlined the steps that I followed to analyse my data according to Braun and Clarke's (2006) process.

1. Familiarisation with the Data

After a careful transcription of the interview recordings, I anonymized and organised each separately. I then listened to the recordings as I read and re-read carefully each transcript. This way I was able to grasp emerging ideas from each transcript while staying as close as I could to the data. This helped me ensure that I did not miss any important information shared by my participants. During this step, I was able to get a sense of the whole dataset and to identify recurring concepts. By the end of this step, the main concept that stood out was the lack of diversity in the ESOL profession in Scottish colleges.

2. Generating Initial Codes

At this step, I went through each transcript, creating initial codes by identifying key features and patterns within the data. I labelled what appeared to be important information that

related to my research questions. These labels became initial codes and included phrases such as ‘native English speakers’, ‘heterosexual’, ‘job specifications’, ‘hiring practices’ and so on.

3. Searching for Themes

During this step, I looked at initial codes across all transcripts, focusing on the relationships between codes and organising the codes into potential themes. Related codes were grouped together into broader categories. For example, codes related to ‘job specifications’ and ‘the hiring process’ merged into the broader theme of ‘reasons for lack of staff diversity’.

4. Reviewing the Themes

During this step, I reviewed my themes in relation to the coded extracts. I revisited the codes in each individual transcript and checked them against the overall codes that I had created. My aim at this point was to ensure that the codes reflected the entire dataset by capturing all voices and perspectives.

5. Defining and Naming the Themes

At this step, I focused on what each theme captured and identified sub-themes which explored specific aspects of the theme. During this step, the theme ‘profile of the standard ESOL lecturer in Scottish colleges’ was broken down to a number of sub-themes, including ‘gender and age’, ‘ethnicity’ and so on. An element of deduction informed this step as I considered the themes in relation to the theoretical framework and literature review; this informed the refinement and naming of themes and subthemes. A table listing the final themes and subthemes can be found below:

Fig. 3: List of themes and sub-themes

6. Writing the Report

At this step, I compiled the themes and sub-themes to create an account of the findings, using quotes from the interviews to illustrate them. This account is presented below, after the section that introduces the participants.

6.2 Meeting the participants

This section provides a description of how the participants view themselves as ESOL lecturers in the college sector. This type of detailed description of the participants is essential in qualitative studies of this kind, where context is ‘vital’ for understanding the world from the participants’ perspective (Bryman, 2012). As stated in the methodology chapter, the participants were recruited through social media (Twitter & LinkedIn), or through the use of the snowball technique. Despite not being able to reach the initial goal of 20 participants for the reasons described in the methodology chapter, the responses from the nine participants of this study provide a varied and in-depth picture of the current situation of ESOL departments in four different colleges in Scotland.

In terms of their employment at the time of the interview, six participants worked in two major Further Education establishments in a large Scottish city, one participant had experience working in different sized colleges across Scotland, and the other two participants worked in colleges in smaller areas in Scotland where the demand for ESOL classes is lower.

The table below (see table 1) provides a summary of the participants’ identity in terms of declared gender, first language, nationality, ethnicity, sexuality, age, class and amount of experience in ESOL in Scottish colleges. The table shows the identity characteristics by which the participants chose to describe themselves during the interviews; therefore, the information that was not provided directly by them has been left blank.

Name	Gender	L1	Nationality	Ethnicity	Sexual orientation	Age	Class	Experience ⁷
P1	Male	English	British	White	Straight	-	Middle	4 years
P2	Male	English	British	White	Gay	Young	Middle	1.5 years
P3	Male	English	British	White	Straight	-	Middle	ESOL is a “new thing”
P4	Female	English/P osh Scots	British	White	Straight	Middle aged	Middle	14 years
P5	Female	French	French	Other	Straight	Middle aged	-	3 years
P6	Male	English	British	White	Straight	Middle aged	Middle	15 years
P7	Female	English	British	White	Straight	-	Middle	5 years
P8	Female	English	Scottish	White	Straight	-	Working/ middle	16 years
P9	Female	English	Scottish	Slightly mixed ethnicity/ White Scottish	-	Semi- Retired ⁸	Working/ middle	25 years

Table 1: Participants’ identity characteristics.

⁷ Refers to the time working in ESOL in the college setting. On some occasions, Participants have taken different positions in the department. This is specified in the discussion below.

⁸ Although this term does not refer to age directly, Participant 9 used this term to refer to her age in relation to the usual retirement age in the UK. For this reason, I have decided to include this term in the table.

The table shows that most participants voluntarily described themselves based on gender, first language, nationality, ethnicity, sexual orientation, class, and experience, while fewer participants provided specific details about age. Their level of education has not been included in the table because only some participants referred to this, but it has been included in the discussion when necessary. In terms of gender identity there are 4 men and 5 women participants. This provides gender balance to this study and represents the situation in the Scottish college sector in general (Colleges Scotland, 2021). However, there is no specific data on gender representation of staff working in Scottish ESOL departments where, according to the participants in this study, there is a predominance of female practitioners.

In terms of the age of the participants, only Participant 2 described himself as “young”, while the majority described themselves as middle aged. Participant 9 referred to herself as “semi-retired” and although she did not mention her age, she indicated that she is of the typical retirement age in the UK. According to the data shown in the Keyfacts 2021 report (Colleges Scotland, 2021) 47% of college lecturers are 51 or over, and although this figure is not specific to ESOL lecturers, it shows that there is an overrepresentation of more mature members of staff in the college profession. The sample, therefore, reflects the general situation in the wider college sector.

All except Participant 5 stated that English is their first language. Participant 5 noted that her first language is French and that she had to learn English in France at school and at university. There is no available data that could be used to check how this sample compares to the ESOL college sector in Scotland in terms of the first language of staff; however, from the participants’ perceptions, it seems evident that there is a clear dominance of first language speakers of English in ESOL FE departments. This might be expected in Scotland, where English is “Scotland’s main language by custom and usage” (The Scottish Government, 2021). In terms of ethnicity, seven of the participants described themselves as white British or Scottish. The distinction between British and Scottish was made by some of the participants during the interviews. On this topic, Participant 6 said: “I will probably call myself white British rather than white Scottish, but [...], either of those are the same.” The exceptions were Participant 9 and Participant 5. Participant 9 made a distinction between the way she would describe herself in terms of heritage, on the one hand, and the category she would choose when filling official documents, but she did not elaborate on the reasons for this distinction:

[I am of] slightly mixed ethnicity because I'm part Polish part Irish, part Scottish. So slightly mixed ethnicity, although I would probably put myself down on a form as white Scottish.

According to Scotland’s census (2021), 62.4% of Scottish population identifies as ‘Scottish only’, 8.4% identifies as ‘British only’ and only 4.4% report that they do not identify with any UK national identity. In some contexts, such as politics, this differentiation may be relevant as it may lead to discussions around national identity. Based on the participants’ responses, this distinction between ‘British’ and ‘Scottish’ does not seem to be relevant for this study but I wanted to present the identity of the participants using their own descriptions, and therefore, I have included the terms they used to describe themselves.

Participant 5 comes from a North African refugee background, but she grew up in France and describes herself as a French woman. She referred to her identity as “quite fluid” not due to self-perception, but because she believes her identity is perceived differently by people in different countries based on stereotypical external features such as name, appearance and accent:

I think I've got.... the way I see my identity and the way other people see my identity, because they, they stereotype me as soon as, you know, in France, it was as soon as they heard my name, they stereotype me. And now and in the UK, they stereotype me as well. But for, they don't know where my name comes from. So, they don't see, but it's more like my appearance and my accent.

There is no specific data on the ethnic composition of staff of Scottish ESOL departments, however, in the wider college sector, only 2% of college staff are from minority ethnic backgrounds (Colleges Scotland, 2021), compared to a 12.8% in the general population in Scotland (The Scottish Government, 2021). Therefore, the sample for this study seems to reflect the broader college sector as a whole.

In relation to the participants' class background, all but one defined themselves as middle class. Two of them (P7, P8), unprompted, struggled to position themselves between middle class or working class, or even to clearly define what class, as a social category, meant for them. A few of them provided an elaborate reflection of what class means, which will be discussed in section 6.4.5 of this chapter.

In terms of sexual orientation, Participant 2 described himself as a “gay man” while all other participants described themselves as heterosexual. This sample, which does not show a great variety in terms of declared sexual orientation, cannot be contrasted with any real data about the FE sector because there are no figures available on this topic. However, more generally, according to the Scottish Census (The Scottish Government, 2021), 4% of the general population identifies as LGB+⁹ which more or less represents the sample of this study.

With regard to the participants' ESOL experience, a variety was identified. Participant 1 stated that he had been working as an ESOL lecturer in the college sector for 4 years, although he also had experience working in ESOL in other contexts. Participant 2 stated that he had one and a half years of experience in the college sector as well as some experience ESOL community groups in Scotland. Participant 3 described his experience in ESOL education as follows:

This is a ...this is a change of career for me, I worked for quite a long time in sales marketing. And then I career changed and I studied CELTA, and then worked as an ESOL tutor with a refugee programme. And then I moved to - I joined the college to teach ESOL more formally. So, this is a new thing to me, something I haven't been doing for a long time.

⁹ In this section, I focus on sexual orientation and have excluded the 'T' from the acronym, as it refers to gender identity. The acronym stands for lesbian, gay, bisexual, and other sexual orientations, as defined by the Scottish Census (The Scottish Government, 2021).

Participant 4 was a more established ESOL lecturer in the Scottish college sector and had taught many different ESOL courses as she explained in the following extract from the interview:

Okay, so I have been at [my current college] teaching ESOL since 2007. So, 14 years now. And at the moment, I - Well, I guess, over the 14 years, I've taught every single level, I've taught some ESOL for vocational courses as well, like ESOL for social care, ESOL for customer care, that kind of thing, written quite a few courses, and at the moment, I'm focusing on ESOL literacy.

Participant further 4 stated that she worked as an EFL teacher abroad before returning to Britain to work as an ESOL professional in Scotland. This seems to be a common route for ESOL lecturers as other participants (P6, P7, P8 and P9) have had a similar experience. As an example, Participant 6 stated the following:

I began as an EFL teacher maybe a couple of years after leaving University in the 1980s actually. My first job was in Spain, and I spent about three years in Spain teaching, followed by another five years in Latin America, in a couple of places there. And then after that, I spent another five years in Russia, before coming back to the UK. ... Before coming back to the UK, I was working with English as a foreign language, and then since being back here, more English as a second language.

Participant 7 had been working in the college sector for almost five years and, at the time of the interview, she was the curriculum manager of the ESOL department in a large Scottish college. Given that her role at the time of the interview was of a managerial nature, the data that she provided in the interviews presents more elaborate, thought-through and detailed perspectives about aspects such as hiring practices and the implementation of diversity policies in the departments. Participant 8 had been working in the college sector for sixteen years and she was, at the time of the interview, an ESOL lecturer. She had been a senior lecturer for many years and shared her experience in her previous role. For this reason, her views also add a different perspective to the data with regard to hiring practices and college policies. The question of hiring appears at different points in this chapter, so their perspectives are key to this discussion.

Lastly, Participant 9 had a long career in English language teaching. She worked for several years in different countries for private academies and universities before returning to the United Kingdom to work for different universities and colleges in Scotland teaching ESOL and English as an Additional Language (EAL). While working in the college sector she had a role as a senior lecturer and was involved in the hiring process of other ESOL lecturers, but at the time of the interview, she was working as a part time lecturer in a college. As a result, she stated that her perspectives were from both sides, as she had to go through the interview process again relatively recently:

I was interviewed again, because although I had been senior lecturer in that college, I'd moved away to a different area of work and came back in as a temp lecturer. So, I went through the interview process, and it was quite robust, I must say, pretty robust.

Given her long career and the different positions she held throughout the years, Participant 9 offered helpful insights into the shifting dynamics of diversity in Scottish ESOL departments in the college sector in the last two decades.

Some participants spoke about how they perceived their identity as educators in the college. This is worth noting as their identity as lecturers is “inseparable” (Yazan and Lindahl, 2020, p. 2) from other identity characteristics, such as the ones discussed above, and it is shaped by their experience and the context. In this regard, Participant 5 who, as will be seen below, described herself as “the odd one out”, with extensive experience in the community ESOL sector, stated that despite her current role as “ESOL lecturer for a Further Education college in Scotland”, she was not an ESOL tutor. Instead, she described herself as a “linguistic educator” with experience teaching French and English language in the community before moving to the college sector. She seemed to find this term more suitable to refer to her diverse experience in language education, particularly in the community sector, and detached herself from her ‘lecturer’ identity:

Basically, what I would say is ‘linguistic educator’, so my background is really Community Learning, adult literacy, but also language teaching. [...] I tutored both adult literacy to native speakers, and also literacy to ESOL... ESOL students in the community. I was working for community... community services. So, I've got I've got a - I would say, when did I start that? I started in 2003, really teaching ESOL in the community.

Participant 6 had vast experience working in the college sector as he had been an ESOL lecturer for the past 15 years. However, he believed that the term lecturer is a “misnomer” because “I don’t lecture, I teach adults whose first language isn’t English to improve their English language skills”. Similarly, Participant 1 indicated that he sees himself more as a teacher than a lecturer. In this case, their choice of term seemed to be a reflection of how their lecturer identity is defined by their relationship with the learners and the type of teaching practice they employ:

my job title is lecturer or ESOL lecturer and probably if somebody asked me, I would probably describe myself as an English language teacher. Probably ... I don't tend to use the word lecturer because I don't - I teach in the classroom. I don't stand and lecture. I don't work in the lecture hall, you know, what I mean. But we do. We just call ourselves lecturers.

In this section, I have offered a description of the participants' identities based on their self-identification, providing the context from which they responded to the interview questions. Each participant's identity has been considered in both the thematic and discursive analyses of the findings. Despite the small sample size, the participants provided varied and in-depth responses, contributing valuable insights, perspectives, and observations on the topics discussed.

6.3 Theme 1: Mismatch between staff and student diversity in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges

6.3.1 Lack of diversity in ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges

Generally, most participants seemed to agree that their departments are not diverse in terms of the identity characteristics of teaching staff. As noted, interviews opened an opportunity for participants to reflect about the topic of diversity in their departments and in the Scottish ESOL profession in the colleges more generally. After reflecting on this topic, all participants became fully aware of this issue, and explicitly referred to different identity characteristics to highlight the lack of diversity in their departments at different points during the interviews. For example, Participant 3 stated that his department is “not particularly diverse” and that it is largely dominated by “one gender and, mainly one ethnicity” being “about 95% female about 90%, Scottish, or UK based”.

Participant 8 seemed to think that there is diversity in her department but upon reflecting on this during the interview, she concluded that this is not actually the case:

I don't know how I just gonna look at my department and think we're all so different, but maybe if you had to kind of...predominantly, predominantly white, predominantly heterosexual, native speakers, so perhaps not really that diverse if you were to look at it.

Participant 5 also shared the idea of ESOL departments not being diverse, describing the teaching staff as “mostly white, middle aged, middle class”. Similarly, Participant 7 referred to her department as “limited” in terms of diversity, stating that, although there are certain people in the department who may have different identity characteristics, most staff members share very similar attributes:

But as I said, we in our department, particularly, there is a... it's very limited in terms of the range of diversity we have, we have a couple of little tokens, I don't mean, tokenism, like we put them in just [to tick a box] but there's a couple of people who fit slightly different criteria for each of the different characteristics. But it's not across the board, the vast majority of people are very similar in... in those characteristics.

Participant 2 also referred to the lack of diversity in ESOL departments stating that, in his view, the staff working in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges appear to be similar in terms of identity. He commented on the apparent lack of change he has seen in ESOL departments throughout the years:

I think when you look at it, some departments are all very much similar, in their kind of identities. And when you – when you look across a broad spectrum, you don't see very much change, and you don't see diversity and, working on it for a while now, it's been very static.

There is not current available data related to the diversity of individual departments in the colleges that could help me to contrast the participants' perceptions of ESOL departments and how they compare to others. However, I have compared the participants' views with the data shown in the report published by Colleges Scotland (2021) where I was able to evaluate the facts from the Scottish college sector in general. This report shows that the college sector in Scotland seems to be dominated by women, and people belonging to a white British background. Only 2% of college staff are reported to be from minority ethnic backgrounds¹⁰. Therefore, this lack of diversity in ESOL departments reported by the participants does not seem to be exclusive to this field but is extended to other departments across the college sector.

Fig.4: Information about staff in the Scottish FE sector. Retrieved from Colleges Scotland, 2021 p.36

In short, ESOL departments do not seem to be diverse in terms of the identity of teaching staff, and there is a perceived preference for a certain type of ESOL teacher. This type is explored later, in theme 2.

6.3.2 The impact of lack of staff diversity on students

A varied student cohort

As anticipated, given the nature of ESOL education in Scotland discussed in chapters 2 and 4, the participants of this study reported that the students in their ESOL classrooms come from

¹⁰ This is the term used in the report.

a variety of backgrounds. Participant 3 referred to the diversity of students in his classes as follows:

I did a survey in class last year, and there were 31 nationalities and 39 first languages. ... and that was across three classes that I was teaching. And eh...we had a lot of Syrians, and people from Middle East that's because [this area]¹¹ had a high proportion of Syrian refugees in the resettlement programme. So, there was lots of Syrians. There are lots of Eastern Europeans predominantly, and it is a big area for the Polish community to come to live and work. But we have students from every continent from every, from every part of the world. And they've all made the move to Scotland, usually with -with family members. And we have a really big Venezuelan community in [this area], which surprised me greatly because I didn't know but given the economic circumstances of Venezuela, lots of entire family groups have moved across I have brothers and sisters who come to my classes, and the most wonderful, happy people. So yeah, we do. They're amazing, absolutely amazing. [...]. So, in all those wonderful little ESOL stories that you get, but yes, the the diversity that the students come from, from every background, and they all have personal stories to tell.

Participant 4, who reported that, as ESOL lecturers “we teach quite a multicultural mix of people”, also discussed the wide diversity of students she has taught throughout her years working in the ESOL college sector, and pointed out how global politics influence the type of students who come to learn ESOL in Scottish FE institutions:

They are from a mixed bag of range of ages from like 17 to like 60 - 65, even maybe older. All ages, various different countries. I've noticed when I first started, there was a lot of students from Afghanistan, and now there's a lot more students from Syria. So, at the moment, we've got like, Eritrea, Syria, Iran, Iraq, Kurdistan, those kinds of areas. Yeah, when I started as well, a lot of students from Congo, but that's changed. So, it kind of changes politically, and depending on where the wars are, in a way.

Participant 6 referred to the wider community, pointing out that the diverse backgrounds reflected in the community that his college serves are underrepresented in the staff body in his ESOL department:

We as a body, probably underrepresent the community which we serve. We don't, as I mentioned to you, I think we don't have ... people [teaching staff] from the many different communities in, in [this city].

This mismatch is seen as unfortunate by Participant 6 who stated: “So, you know, I think that is ... that's a pity that we don't have more members of staff who come from the communities that we are actually working with”.

It cannot be expected that the diversity of lecturers will be an exact match for that of students, but the above quotes indicate a significant discrepancy between staff and student diversity in the ESOL departments in Scottish colleges. This mismatch, as highlighted by the participants,

¹¹ Replaced for anonymity

led me to explore their perceptions about the potential impact this situation might have on the learners.

Perceived impact of staff diversity on students

Two of the participants held the view that diverse staff will have no effect on students: Participant 4 and Participant 9 stated that, while they welcome diverse colleagues into the ESOL departments and “it would be nice to have a more diverse team” (Participant 4), they did not think that this could have any effect, either negative or positive, on the learners. These two participants were of the view that “you need teachers to be teaching and so you're not really probably taking anything... identity [related] into account” (Participant 9). In short, they believed that skills and ability are the priority for students and for the department. These views reflect either a lack of awareness or a lack of concern about how language teacher identities (LTIs) may impact learners.

In contrast, the rest of the participants seemed more aware of the way in which staff identity may impact students. Their responses suggested that staff diversity has an impact on two areas: learning and teaching, and pastoral care. In terms of the benefits for the learning and teaching aspect of the students' experience, Participant 2 stated that lack of staff diversity might lead to students disengaging from their English language learning journey:

I think it's important to have a range of people. If you have three practitioners or lectures that are the exact same, then if a learner doesn't really feel comfortable, it doesn't sit well, it also really does hinder progression. So, if you know for a fact that you're going to have that person through your National 3, National 4, National 5, that learner may then just leave and decide that it's not going to happen, and they won't want to continue. And I think being subjected to different people's different teaching styles gives the learner the best chance. If you have someone, say, that teaches a certain way and then they go outside and try and... ehm... put their skills to use they might not be great, they may not be valid and they may struggle so having different teaching methods as well.

Participant 2's response is supported by Kennedy (2020), who discusses that the teacher's identity, and the way teachers present themselves in the classroom can have an impact, either positive or negative, on the learners' engagement. From this perspective, Participant 2 suggests that a more diverse staff body increases the chance for students to find the teaching style that influences them positively.

Another positive effect of staff diversity on teaching and learning was discussed by Participant 8 who believed that such diversity could inform different areas of the curriculum, for example lesson planning, materials and topics of discussion in the classroom. However, she also admitted that in her view, ESOL learners do not focus on the identity of the teachers; for students teachers are 'just teachers':

I think it's important for our learners to see a diverse kinda cohort of teachers, but probably, I would imagine our learners kind of see us just as teachers and don't really examine ... differences, but definitely, ... it's a positive if you have a diverse group of

people in work, very positive. Well, I mean, you just bring different perspectives on life. And, you know, I think that, you know, the impact that that would have on your lesson planning ... topics you would deal with in the classroom and, you know, also sharing material with other teachers...and maybe that comes from a different perspective.... I think it's very important.

As another example of the positive effects of staff diversity on students, Participant 5 commented that a broader representation of diversity among staff facilitates the understanding of students' needs. She noted that the perceived uniformity among staff

is not good in terms of meeting needs [...] because different people can bring different perspectives, can bring different bodies of knowledge. So, for example, [the college] do have a lot of students, African students and having only white teachers.... [I do not] think is a [...] good thing.

Furthermore, it also helps the students to have someone in the teaching body that they can relate to because, as Participant 3 put it "we teach better when we understand our students. And if you have a diverse teaching faculty, they can give you an insight into students that you simply don't have, from your own life experience or work experience". This resonates with the work of scholars such as Varghese et al. (2005), and Winchester (2013), discussed in the literature review, who highlight that having an understanding of the students' backgrounds and their language needs may lead to a targeted approach to language learning, and more effective communication. This, however, clashes with the current ESOL policies in Scotland that seem to limit the ability for curriculum managers or lecturers in the college sector to adapt the curriculum to the learners needs (Brown, 2017, Stella and Kay, 2023).

From a pastoral care perspective, Participant 2 shared what, in his opinion, are the negative consequences of lack of staff diversity on students:

if we don't bring different personalities, if we don't bring different identities, then we're not really doing the learners any service in helping them integrate and if... and if we're the first point of contact with them. And we are...and we are kind of disengaging our equality and diversity in the profession, then it just carries on through and through.

Norton and De Costa (2018) also highlight the role of the language teachers in demonstrating the way in which diversity is embraced in the classroom. They emphasize that when teachers are attuned to the diverse cultural and linguistic backgrounds present in their teaching space, they can foster a more positive attitude toward diversity among the learners.

A broader view on the impact of staff diversity on students concerns the potential of staff from diverse backgrounds to serve as a role model for students, helping them to engage with their learning and with the community they live in as well as enhancing their sense of belonging. For example, Participant 4 believed that a diverse team of lecturers could inspire ESOL learners to become ESOL lecturers in the future:

I guess it is actually often... it's really quite motivating for the students to be taught by someone who is from a different country, because then they can look up and think actually, I can do this job as well if my English is good enough in the future.

Similarly, Participant 3 commented:

If a student realises that someone who has come without English as a first language can progress to be a lecturer or a teacher of English, I think it would be a positive thing. I think culturally it would, it would help [students] to feel more comfortable in the environment.

Participants 3 and 4 discussed how having a more diverse body of teachers may foster a greater sense of belonging for students and serve as source of inspiration for them. However, they did not seem to have reflected on how their own identities can be negotiated to serve similar purposes. This underscores the need to create opportunities for exploring LTIs within their practice as a means to promote diversity and inclusion in ESOL classrooms, as suggested by Kennedy (2020), Schissel and Stephens (2020), and Banegas, Beltrán-Palanques, and Salas (2023).

In short, in this section I have identified a significant mismatch between the narrow profile of ESOL lecturers and the diversity of ESOL students in Scottish colleges, and I have explored the participants' views on the effects that diversity, or lack of it, might have on the students. In the next section, I will explore what participants mean when they refer to a 'narrow profile of ESOL lecturers'.

6.4 Theme 2: The 'standard' and the 'other'

From the interviews I identified a 'standard' or 'dominant' profile of ESOL lecturers that all participants are aware of. As Participant 8 put it, this 'standard profile' in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges seems to be "predominantly white, predominantly heterosexual, native speakers, so perhaps not really that diverse if you were to look at it". Participant 3 acknowledged that people in his department resembled his own background:

It is a very small department in [my¹²] College. I see identity of the people I work with to be very similar to me. So, they be of the same ethnicity and same first language as myself.

This 'standard' profile of ESOL lecturer resonates with the type of English language teacher that seems to be favoured in the broader TESOL profession, as discussed in the context and literature review chapters. The reasons for the prevalence of this 'standard' profile are, indeed, central to this study and will be discussed in the findings chapters and summarised in the conclusion.

¹² Replaced for anonymity

Two of the participants did not ‘fit’ the standard profile in the way they presented themselves in terms of a number of features of their identity. One of them was Participant 2, who, as seen above, identified himself as gay and young in relation to the average age of his work colleagues. According to him, “everyone that I know at the moment [working in the ESOL college sector] is probably above 40. I’m probably the youngest by far”.

Participant 5 also made it very clear throughout the interview that she felt – “a bit like the, you know, the odd one out” in her ESOL college department, as she put it. Her feeling of ‘otherness’ is expressively described in the following extract:

[...] not having people who look like me all the time is difficult. And I don't mean exactly the same background as me. But I'm from a mixed background. I've lived in different countries, and in my family, people speak different languages and finding myself with colleagues who they don't speak any other language, they're white middle class, middle aged, and say, well, apart from the middle age, you know well, we don't really have a lot in common.

During the interview, I invited participants to reflect on the lecturing staff diversity in their department, and the Scottish ESOL college sector more generally: the perceived lack of diversity, causes and reasons and ways to address the situation. Perhaps not surprisingly, ‘standard’ participants admitted to their lack of reflection on the matter prior to the interview. For example, when I asked Participant 4 about staff diversity in her department, she started her response by confessing that “[she hasn’t] really thought about it”. As will be analysed in chapter 7 in more detail, their responses were tentative and hesitant, albeit elaborate.

On the other hand, Participant 2 and Participant 5 (who, as a reminder, did not see themselves as fitting into the standard profile) demonstrated an in-depth reflection on matters related to lack of diversity prior to the interview. Participant 2 noted that he had detected a reluctance on the part of his colleagues to discuss issues related to diversity. As he put it: “people may not be speaking out about [the fact that we are] not a diverse profession yet”.

Therefore, the interviews created an opportunity for most participants to reflect on aspects of identity that they had not thought about before. From a methodological point of view, these findings demonstrate the importance of studies such as this one, where there is a space to share perceptions and opinions (Seidman, 2013; Freeman, 2019). This also crucially shows that those regarded as ‘standard’ (and therefore occupying a privileged position in this context) and those whose identity and experience are more peripheral to the norm, had a clearly different level of awareness of certain issues that affect their position. As argued by Appleby (2016) the perceived privileged groups seem to be unaware of how they might be benefiting from the system.

At this point, it is worth noting that this distinction between the ‘standard’ and the ‘other’ employed as part of the discussion in this thesis, is only a methodological choice that facilitates the discussion around mechanisms of power in this particular context in order to “understand where inequalities [...] are generated and the negative impact they have [...]” on the ESOL profession. As examined in the literature review chapter, power is never unidirectional nor static, and shifts depending on context (Appleby, 2013; Fairclough, 2013;

Smooth, 2013). This means that in certain situations, those who have been described as the 'standard', might also be subject to disadvantaged situations in the profession as I discuss in a later section of this chapter. In the following sub-sections I discuss how the perceptions around different identity characteristics in the ESOL college departments contribute to reinforce this division. For this discussion, the non-hierarchical approach to identity variables suggested by Collins (2000) has been helpful to understand and explore the different ways identity characteristics intersect with each other and with the current structures of power. This way of conceptualizing identity characteristics has enabled me to understand the dynamic nature of power in relation to identity characteristics without imposing a rigid hierarchy.

6.4.1 Gender and age

All participants seemed to agree on the fact that there is a perceived gender imbalance in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges. In this regard, Participant 1 stated that "[they have] mostly female staff". Similarly, Participant 3 noted that "the department is about 95% female" and Participant 4 stated that "there's not quite so many men". This resonates with Participant 7 who commented that the department "is definitely heavier on the female side". Participant 8 argued that departments are becoming more diverse in terms of gender and "that was a good thing with the merger, because we were all women and then suddenly, you met male ESOL teachers". However, in line with most other participants, in her opinion, ESOL departments are dominated by "white Scottish women".

The apparent gender imbalance in the ESOL departments is not surprising as it seems to be following the trend of the wider TESOL profession, which is female dominated, as discussed in the context and literature review chapters. Participant 2, who, at the time of the interview, worked in a smaller department and was the only male ESOL lecturer in his college, stated that this imbalance was so obvious that it was surprising for his students to see a man teaching ESOL, so students "may say [they]'ve never seen a young male teaching English".

As the above statement indicates, when discussing the perceived prevalence of women in the profession, some participants also referred to a specific age bracket. For example, Participant 2 stated that, apart from him, the department has "women over the age of 45". Others such as Participant 5 referred to "middle aged" women, and Participant 3 to women who are "predominantly 40 or over". Participant 2, who agreed that there is gender imbalance in ESOL departments, also commented on the prevalence of middle-aged staff in his department. Participants did not elaborate further on their responses about this specific matter, and this particular point may need exploring in further research projects. However, it is worth pointing out that, as noted above, according to Colleges Scotland (2021) 61% of all staff members in the college are women and more than 47% are 51 or over, so this figure seems consistent with the participants' perceptions.

As indicated in this section, the participants perceived their ESOL departments as dominated by women. It should be noted that 'domination' means 'majority', which is the most common understanding of the word for these participants. The other meaning of the word - that is,

'overall control' - is not so relevant in this context as will be seen in section 6.5.2, which discusses the power dynamics that the group of so-called 'dominant' female lecturers are also subjected to.

6.4.2 Ethnicity

According to the Scottish Government (2021), over 17% of the population of the three major cities in Scotland, Glasgow, Edinburgh and Aberdeen, belong to ethnic minorities, which include White Other, White Polish, White¹³ Irish, Chinese, Indian, Pakistani, African and Asian Other. This percentage contrasts with the figure shown in section 6.3.1 above which indicates that only 2% of all college staff in Scotland identify with ethnic minorities. This lack of ethnic diversity in the Scottish college sector seems to also be reflected in ESOL departments, according to the participants, as most seemed to agree that "[there is] a very limited range of race within the department" (Participant 9): the departments are predominately dominated by white, Scottish or British members of staff who have been educated in the UK.

Some participants noted that in their departments there are some ESOL members of staff who come from other ethnic backgrounds; however, they are still a minority in the departments. For example, Participant 6 pointed out that "there are maybe two or three members of staff, [...] actually, that would be considered to belong to ethnic minorities". Similarly, Participant 1 stated that although the majority of his colleagues are originally from the UK, there are members of staff from different countries, as "[they have] [someone] from Russia and [someone¹⁴] from Germany so there is a mixture there". He also discussed his perception of ethnic diversity in the ESOL college context in Scotland as a whole:

I've gone through a lot of training sessions, and I've met people from lots of countries ... I've met teachers from, you know, all over Europe and lots of different countries and and and, uh, people from minority backgrounds as well, certainly.

Despite this perception of change, for Participant 9, the apparent move towards diversity in ESOL departments is progressing slower than she expected, and, as such, noted that she was "shocked" by the minimal evolution she had seen since she began teaching ESOL in 1995:

I don't think [the teaching body] is [diverse]. I really don't think it is. My perception going back in all these years later, to one of the very big colleges, is that the percentage of non-white non... non-UK teachers is ... is still very low. I think you could count on one hand, you know, maybe... maybe I'm wrong, but I don't see a massive change, which is quite shocking, really.

Thus, all participants seemed to be aware of the lack of ethnic diversity in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges, although some were noticing a small move towards diversity. Despite staff awareness of this ethnic imbalance, and the positive effects that more ethnic diversity could bring to Scottish ESOL education – as discussed in section 6.3.2 of this chapter - there are

¹³ 'White' appears capitalised in this context as it is how it is written in the Scottish Census.

¹⁴ This has been changed to preserve the anonymity of the practitioners mentioned in this section.

different reasons that were perceived to be perpetuating this current situation, which I discuss in section 6.5.

6.4.3 First language

All participants agreed that there is a prevalence of 'native' English speakers in their departments. Participant 2, for example, stated that in his small department, all members of staff, including himself, are considered to be native speakers of English. Participant 9 also referred to the staff in her department as "99.9% white, native English speakers". Other participants (Participant 1, Participant 6) stated that, although there are a few members of staff in their departments that come from other countries, mainly in Europe, the majority of their colleagues are native speakers of English.

Some participants related this dominance of native English speakers in ESOL departments to the global neoliberal notion of nativespeakerism. The clearer case in point is Participant 8 who, based on her experience working in continental Europe, stated that "basically, you could get a job if you were a native English speaker" and "there was a bit of snobbery attached to it", thus echoing Llurda's observation of the "dominant status of the native speaker over non-native speakers" (Llurda, 2020, p. 52) in Western approaches to English language teaching (ibid.). Participant 8's qualification of native speakerism as "snobbery" is an indication of the level of awareness of the issue, which, according to Participant 8, is rising in ESOL departments, where there has been some change in the last ten or fifteen years. In fact, she believes that people are more aware now of the benefits of having people who had to learn the English language themselves:

I think that as the years have gone by, people are more open to... especially in my department, we're such a big department. So it's not only Scottish people, we have some, I think we've got one Polish ESOL teacher and a Russian that maybe 15 years ago, maybe wouldn't have happened. I think people are more open to that you don't need to be like a native speaker to be a successful ESOL teacher, I think, probably, maybe 10 years ago, I had a different opinion on that. But I've really changed. Having worked alongside these teachers, I can see that it's, they bring a lot to the, to the role that maybe I don't even have, you know, the same kind of qualities that they have.

Participant 6 also seemed to be aware of the perceived value that is attached to native speakers in the profession in western countries, as he points out that "certainly in the overseas context, native speakers of English as teachers are highly valued, and vastly overrated, in [his] view". Participant 6 argued that this mentality also affects ESOL departments and the curriculum, as the preferred variety of English seems to be the 'standard English'. In his opinion, the "overrated" value of 'native speakers' in TESOL in general and particularly in ESOL in the Scottish context is "wrong". He used himself as example to explain that although his first language is English, he is not Scottish and, therefore, he does not speak the local variety of English that students encounter outside the classroom and, as a result, his 'native' English could also be considered foreign in this context:

Because I mean, this was.... if we think about our context, I'm not a native Scottish speaker. And my accent doesn't reflect that of the Glaswegians that my students will interact with on a daily basis. And so you could possibly say that, you know, the standard English that I teach them, and the accent that I use to talk to them in doesn't represent what they hear. And and I suppose, you know, that's a that's, that's, that's an interesting aspect as well, because for me, I mean, we teach a standard English because, you know, in education, education is delivered in standard English. And we do try to reflect to a certain extent, depending on our own abilities, the way English is spoken in locally.

The change in Participant 8's mentality (the improvement as she sees it) has come about for three main reasons. Firstly, from working alongside colleagues whose first language is not English, as she indicates in the quote above. Secondly, from the ever-increasing scholarly work on the subject – as she points out: “there's more literature on kind of nonnative speakers, and if you're interested in keeping up with that, then you can... begin to analyse [...] the advantages of having different kinds of teachers in your department”. And thirdly, from personal motivation to learn on the subject: I am “a bit more educated about [it]” (Participant 8).

This shows that while native speakers are still the majority in ESOL departments, there seems to be a certain level of awareness of the global profession's concern about ‘nativespeakerism’ and the discussions around this topic. This awareness is evident in participants' references to this phenomenon during the interviews, and particularly in the way in which Participant 6 and Participant 8 were critical of the perceived privilege attached to native speakers. However, this change of mentality is not yet reflected on the composition of the ESOL departments.

6.4.4 Heteronormativity

According to the participants' responses, their departments seem to be “predominantly heterosexual” (Participant 9). In fact, heterosexuality seems to be the default sexual identity, to the extent that sexuality, in general terms, is not a key identity feature that naturally springs to mind when self-declared heterosexual participants discuss staff diversity. As an example, after sharing her reflections on aspects of identity such as ethnicity and class, Participant 7 noted that sexual orientation was “overlooked”:

I've just completely overlooked the fact that we do have slight diversity in our own sexuality within the department, but it just didn't even occur to me. And completely slipped my mind that that is, in fact, the case.

This ‘overlooking’ could be understood as evidence of acceptance and normalization of sexual diversity in contemporary British society; however, when contrasted with the perceptions of Participant 2 (who identifies as gay) it becomes clear that the failure to pay attention to diversity in terms of sexual orientation should be seen as one of the effects of heteronormativity that are present in society in general, and in ESOL in particular (Gray and Cooke, 2019) which, in turn, lead to the invisibility of the LGBTQ+ community in the profession (Baynham, 2021; Shin-ying Huang, 2022). This lack of representation of LGBTQ+ staff in ESOL has been discussed by Gray and Cooke (2019, p.200) who claim that “LGBT people have fought

for decades [...] for positive representation in the public, social and aesthetic realm” and this struggle is also visible in ESOL, “a field in which LGBT students and teachers have traditionally been almost entirely invisible and inaudible”.

As will be seen in the next sections of this findings chapter, there are at least three intersecting factors that contribute to this invisibility and the reinforcement of heteronormativity, which can be considered as the dominant discourse. First, the feeling of otherness that members of the LGBTQ+ community experience in the profession seems to act as a barrier to apply for certain positions in ESOL. This intersects with the strong views about the LGBTQ+ community that some ESOL students may have as a consequence of their religious and cultural backgrounds. It also intersects with the role of the institutions and curriculum managers in perpetuating the heteronormative status quo.

6.4.5 Class

As Table 1 shows, all participants but one (Participant 5) explicitly identified as middle class. As Vandrick points out (2014 p.86), class is an “amorphous term”, with “a lack of distinct boundaries”, a part of identity that is “always shifting rather than fixed” (ibid.) That is the case with three of the participants of this study for whom self-identification with a particular class is not straight forward. They provided elaborate answers on the complex relation between socio-economic status and class-related values; more specifically, on the dynamics of their working-class background in relation to their current middle-class professional position and salaries.

As an example, Participant 7 stated the following: “Class is a difficult one. I feel like I would say I come from working class, but I'm definitely middle class now.” This is echoed by Participant 9 who comes from a working-class background, but, as she explains, “when you study, you work, you move into a kind of different more middle-class background” and as a result of this social mobility (Vandrick, 2014), she considers herself now to be settled as middle-class.

For Participant 8, social class is defined by the person’s ethos and values rather than by the salary; therefore, she identified herself as working class, with a middle-class salary. She discussed this on two occasions during the interview:

I think I see it more as values and kind of your culture and kind of your aspirations and what you believe kind of work to be in to represent but I'm aware that others may think it's more to do with salary. And, and also, if I look, if I compare my life to my parents’ life, I've got a much easier life financially.

I kind of identify as a working class, white Scottish woman, and probably in regard to salary, I'm probably considered more middle class, but I come from a very kind of working- class background [...]. Well...I just think probably, like, I think my ethos is working class. And, you know, I believe in, you know, a lot of... you know, I'm a quite an active member of the trade unions, but probably as regard to salary I would maybe, I don't know if sometimes I think maybe I earn too much to be considered working class, I don't have maybe some of the problems that maybe working class people on a

lower ...from a lower salary would have but certainly, I, I would consider myself more working class than middle class, but others might have different opinions.

The significance of this reflection becomes clearer when compared with Participant 5 who (as a reminder, comes from a French speaking refugee background) noted that:

finding myself with colleagues who they don't speak any other language, they're white middle class, middle aged, and say, well, apart from the middle age, you know well, we don't really have a lot in common.

This quote indicates that, despite enjoying the same economic benefits of middle class as the rest of her colleagues, Participant 5 experiences an 'I'- 'They' contrast. This leads her to believe that her financial position, which, based on Participant 8's reasoning, puts her in middle class, is not sufficient because a whole set of other identity features such as provenance, first language and migration status intersect to mark her as 'other'.

6.4.6 Professional context

As outlined in the context chapter, ESOL in Scotland has traditionally been delivered within community settings. However, in the last two decades, there has been a notable increase in ESOL provision in Further Education institutions (Meer, Peace and Hill, 2019; Stella and Kay, 2023). Although these two types of educational settings have the same clearly defined objectives, which are to pursue social integration and to enhance the employability of migrants who speak other languages, to English-dominant countries (The Scottish Government, 2007; The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015), participants do not perceive them as complementary but, rather, as two separate worlds. As will be seen in this section, this chasm directly impacts on lecturer identity and, ultimately, on staff diversity.

During the interviews, four participants (P1, P2, P3 and P5) discussed their perception of the college as a privileged setting for the delivery of ESOL compared to the community setting, with the latter being perceived as a place for the 'other'. As will be seen, their views varied depending on whether they align with the 'standard' or the 'other' practitioner categories. As will be argued, this stark differentiation contributes to the reinforcement of divisive practices and the feeling of otherness in the profession which, as a consequence, may be supporting the current system and preventing diversity (Foucault and Gordon, 1980; Powell, 2015; Courtney, 2017).

Teaching ESOL in the community seems to be where a number of participants (P1, P2, P3, P4 and P5) started their careers before moving to the college setting; therefore, they speak from experience in both environments. When Participant 3 decided he wanted to change his career and got his CELTA qualification, he started teaching ESOL in a community programme and after some time he "joined the college to teach ESOL more formally". In a more elaborate response, Participant 1 noted that ESOL in the college sector seems to be for a "highly qualified professional teaching workforce", while the community sector is for teachers who have a lower level of qualifications. In his attempt to venture a solution that can help increase the diversity of college ESOL staff, he suggested that

maybe there should be a place for people with maybe not quite such a high level, to teach maybe lower-level learners with the college because maybe they don't need that super high level [of qualification] and maybe there's a balance there

This idea is based on the (rather condescending) assumption that community ESOL staff lack the necessary skills to teach at Further Education institutions, particularly at higher levels.

Participant 2 also started teaching ESOL in the community sector once he got the qualifications, and after almost two years, moved to the college sector. These three participants share the perception of the higher degree of formality in the college sector and the almost natural journey of ESOL practitioners towards Further Education establishments once enough experience and the right qualifications have been obtained. The connotations of 'prestige' associated with the college sector and 'lowliness' attached to the community sector are clearly expressed by Participant 2. Taking an obviously critical stance, he stated that working as an ESOL lecturer seems to be perceived as a "privileged position" by those who are working in the community sector, and in other departments in the college, "maybe because of the type of person that has, traditionally, taught ESOL", that is, middle-class and white.

As was the case on many occasions in this research, Participant 5 offered the most elaborate and critical stance in relation to this divide as well as her own feelings as a person who has had experience in both the community sector and Further Education institutions. In her own words, the community sector is a challenging setting as there are often students who are "very traumatised, who [can't] go to college because of their experiences, and also [there are] people with learning difficulties". She also started working as an ESOL tutor in the community in 2003, and after many years in this sector, got a position in the college as an ESOL lecturer. Although she is a highly qualified professional who has a long career in ESOL education, Participant 5 acknowledged that she "would much prefer teaching in community-based organisations, you know, the voluntary sector, and also council services" than in the college. She stated that "[she doesn't] feel comfortable, [she] can say that, you know, [she doesn't] feel comfortable in a college environment". The college sector constitutes a setting where she personally feels like an outsider but has potentially the same effect on other people with similar identity: "I think that people like me are more likely to teach in community education than in college" (Participant 5). As a result of this fatalistic view, despite her experience and qualifications she felt "lucky" for having a place in a college department. Her perception was that her professional achievement was not due to merit but due to luck.

Thus, one marker that differentiates the 'standard' from the 'other' suggested by the participants, is the location where ESOL is taught in Scotland: the community and the college sector. The participants' accounts reported in this section seem to reinforce the idea of 'privilege' associated with college ESOL departments and of 'otherness' associated with community settings. This differentiation can be noted in the current ESOL policy context in Scotland, in which more funding is allocated for accredited ESOL courses delivered in further education institutions, while non-accredited courses typically delivered in the community are regarded as 'less important' in terms of funding (Stella and Kay, 2023).

6.5 Theme 3: Reasons for lack of staff diversity

From the participants' responses discussed in the preceding sections, it is clear that participants are aware of low levels of staff diversity in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges. During the interviews, the participants reflected on this lack of diversity and suggested reasons for it. These reasons are presented in this section.

The two main reasons that emerged from the interviews are captured in the following quotes from the interview with Participant 2 who said:

And I think, why are we so stagnant? Why are we so kind of set in the past? Is it because of our learners? Or is it because of the people that are leading the department? Or is it a bit of both?

I think, when you've got someone maybe who's in charge of the department, and has been there for a very long time, they are reluctant to have that change, and I think there's a worry that the learners may react TO it.

Participant 2 suggests that heads of ESOL departments may be responsible for the lack of diversity in lecturing staff because they are change-averse and because they are concerned about how the ESOL students will respond to being taught by lecturers who do not fit the 'standard' ESOL lecturer profile. The reasons for a stagnant workforce, including what Participant 2 called "the power dynamics within certain departments" and college-wide recruitment strategies, will be discussed in sub-section 6.5.1. The impact of the perceived expectations of learners about the characteristics of teaching staff will be considered in sub-section 6.5.3. The next section focuses on the impact of the recruitment process on the lack of diversity in ESOL lecturing staff.

6.5.1 The recruitment process

6.5.1.a *The applicant pool*

Some participants identified a 'barrier' to diversity in the type of candidates that apply for ESOL lecturer positions in the Scottish college sector. In their view, these positions tend to attract candidates who fit a specific profile that aligns with the typical ESOL lecturer described earlier, but the participants' discussion revolved mainly around the topic of gender and ethnicity.

Gender imbalance

Participant 1 (male) commented on the lack of diversity in relation to gender. He suggested that one of the reasons why there seems to be a higher presence of women in the profession is because of the different type of degrees that men and women decide to do and, as a consequence, the type of employment these degrees lead to:

My sister for example, she did English literature at [university]¹⁵ and then the CELTA as an immediate follow on from doing that within the university to try and find work. You know it's...it's a lot about people having degrees in these subjects and wanting to find, you know, meaningful and rewarding employment, and I'm sure, I'm sure it's not a stereotype to say that there would be a lot of... a lot of women, like my sister who are ...Uhm...white middle class Scottish that, that go through arts degrees.

According to the Wright (2024) the teaching profession, and particularly in languages, is highly influenced by the stereotypes of women being teachers and studying languages. These stereotypical views are reflected on the potential candidates that choose to apply for these positions, and also in the hiring team (ibid.). In Participant 1's view, this stereotypical view is still prevalent and influences women's career choices, resulting in bigger numbers of women aspiring to become teachers and ESOL lecturers. As a consequence, this results on a less diverse applicant pool for ESOL lecturing jobs in terms of gender.

Another possible reason that could help to explain the perceived gender imbalance in the applicant pool is the perception of salary and prestige associated with language teaching roles (Wright, 2024). According to Wright (2024) men are usually 'pushed' by society to choose professions related to business and finance as they are perceived to have higher salaries. The participants of this study do not make any references to this, so there is no evidence to support this claim in my study. However, as I discuss later in this chapter, participants believe that women do not seem interested in management roles in ESOL, and when they do, they do not feel comfortable in these positions. This could be explained with reference to the stereotypical view that management roles are more suited to men which could result in women having self-limiting beliefs about their suitability for such roles.

Little interest among 'diverse' practitioners

Participant 9, who has participated in recruitment panels in the college, referred to lack of diversity in the applicant pool in relation to ethnicity:

I suspect in Scotland, there are fewer, fewer teachers from different ethnic backgrounds, if you like, applying for jobs. I think we don't have a big pool of non-white teachers.

Participant 7, who, as part of her role as a curriculum manager has been actively involved in the recruitment of new ESOL lecturers for her department, also seemed to be very aware of this lack of ethnic diversity in ESOL departments and had reflected on this aspect from a recruiter perspective. In the next excerpt she describes and illustrates with a concrete example the fairness – as she perceives it – of the recruitment process to conclude that there is not much interest in ESOL positions among individuals from diverse ethnic backgrounds:

So it's something I think, I guess, particularly in terms of race, is something that has been... it's obviously been very prevalent in the world recently, and it's something that I've been reading up on myself, and there's parts of that, through my own reading that I've been sort of considering now that I'm in a position where I could do something

¹⁵ The name of the university has been removed for anonymity reasons.

about, you know, hiring people of a slightly broader range of people. And we have literally just done some interviews and actually, we don't know what race candidates come from, you can maybe guess by a name, but that doesn't necessarily always ring true. There was certainly somebody that I thought might have been, might have been black from her surname. But actually, because she was married to an African man. And so, she was white in the end. And I we haven't had the candidates, I think, that have had any kind of broader ehm diversity there.

Her reflection ended there, without elaborating further as to the reasons why that is the case.

Participant 6 wondered whether the reason for the lack of diversity lies in the recruitment process or “some other barrier” that may prevent people from diverse ethnic backgrounds from applying for jobs in the ESOL college sector:

And, you know, I'm a bit surprised with that, really, because I'd thought that there would be people, especially from ethnic minority backgrounds, who have maybe skills in more than one language, who would perhaps naturally have been interested in working with people who come from overseas to settle here. And I don't know whether that's perhaps the fault of the recruitment process, and that is not reaching the whole of the community here in [this city], or, or whether it's some other some other barrier to having people apply. So, you know, that's, that's, I think that is a that's a pity that we don't have more members of staff who come from the communities that we are actually working with.

This participant's surprise is based on the crucial assumption that ethnically diverse and multilingual people would have a natural interest in working with students like them. Beyond his expression of 'pity' that will be discussed in chapter 7, the participant does not reflect on the potential, intersecting issues that may be erecting this 'barrier', which reflects a lack of reflection on the reasons for this apparent lack of interest. This lack of reflection could be attributed to his perceived privileged position in this instance where he does not seem to be personally affected by this issue (Appleby, 2016).

Participant 2, taking an obviously critical stance, stated that working as an ESOL lecturer seems to be perceived as a “privileged position” by those who are working in the community sector, and in other departments in the college, “maybe because of the type of person that has, traditionally, taught ESOL”, that is, middle-class and white. The external and internal perception of the college sector as a place of privilege might be the barrier Participant 6 (above) was struggling to identify, that is, the reason why staff from diverse ethnic backgrounds, particularly those coming from the community sector, are not applying for ESOL jobs at Further Education institutions. Or, as Participant 5 put it: “I think that people like me [that is, from ethnic minorities or refugee backgrounds] are more likely to teach in community education than in college”. So, an initial exploration of the lack of ethnic diversity in lecturing staff in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges may lead one to believe that this issue stems from a lack of interest from individuals from diverse backgrounds to work in this sector that seems to have remained consistent for at least the last 30 years. From this perspective, the lack of diversity in ESOL departments seems to be the 'fault' of the 'other'. In this way, the lack of ethnic diversity in ESOL departments could be seen as a self-othering practice (Freire, 2000)

where the 'other' perceives the profession as a 'foreign' place where they do not belong because of the internalisation of the dominant discourse, which is that the typical ESOL lecturer is white, middle class, and native English speaker, and, therefore, practitioners who do not fit this profile do not have a place in ESOL departments. However, as will be seen below, this perceived self-othering is not the only reason that may be preventing ethnic diversity in ESOL departments; other intersecting factors are at play as well.

6.5.1.b Hiring practices

According to the participants of this study, apart from the assumed 'lack of interest' from those who are perceived as the 'other' in the profession, there seem to be barriers in the recruitment process that might be preventing diversity and reinforcing the current status quo in ESOL departments. Participants' perceptions on the levels of equality and fairness of the recruitment process and its impact on staff diversity varied depending on their status and sense of self-identity: in general terms, those who are more likely to fit the 'standard' ESOL lecturer profile were less critical about the process and vice versa, which, again, shows how those who might be in a more privileged position may not be aware of their privilege and how they might be benefitting from the system (Appleby, 2016).

Trust and faith in the system

It may appear evident that the college as an institution has anti-discriminatory measures in place, in line with the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010). Such measures should ensure that candidates are not discriminated against due to one or more identity characteristics. These types of measures are not only in place in ESOL departments. They are institution-wide practices informing the hiring process; therefore, some of the discussion in this section may be relevant to other departments across the college. Participants who align with the 'standard' profile, seemed to have faith that these practices are effective and do not question them. However, Participants 2 and 5, who are identified as the 'other' in this context, seemed to be sceptical.

Participant 4, who identified as white, heterosexual, native English language speaker and, based on these identity characteristics, could be considered the 'standard' ESOL lecturer, believes that the college abides by the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010) with regards to hiring criteria, although she is not entirely sure if and how this might be implemented:

I think because ... there's the protected characteristics and the Equality Act, I'd like to believe that recruiters are recruiting solely on their ...the merits of the skills that are in the CV and on the interview. But whether in reality that happens, I don't know.

In a similar way, Participant 6, another lecturer who could be perceived as 'standard', has "faith" in the system, believing that the college as an institution adheres to the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010). However, he did not develop the argument further perhaps because he has not been directly affected by this:

the college, like many major employers, goes to some lengths to present itself as an equal opportunities employer. And, and I have quite a lot of faith in that message that they present, I do believe that my employer has a very strong desire to be an equal opportunity employer and, and takes measures to ensure that recruitment is there (Participant 6)

This was also the perception of Participant 3, who was not involved in the hiring process but stated that “in [his] own working place at the moment, everything seems to be based on interview, and how the person interviews” (Participant 3).

On this topic, Participant 7, who had been involved in the hiring process in her institution not long before she was interviewed for this study, did explain part of the process of how the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010) is implemented in her institution. According to her, curriculum managers only have access to the candidates’ information that is related to the essential and desirable criteria for the post. They do not have access to any information related to the identity of the candidates, apart from their names, and, therefore, this does not play a part in the decision before the interview stage:

the majority of characteristics are hidden in the application, so the applications are blind. Ehmm so for the first stage of an application, we don't even have candidate names. And so, I don't know even if they're male or female, again, that would be a guess, based on what I would perceive a male or a female name to be, but so, in the... certainly in the first round, [identity] is not something that plays a role because it's not presented to me to be able to consider it.

Similarly, Participant 8, who also had experience interviewing candidates, believed that the identity of the candidates is not a determining factor in the hiring process:

I was interviewing, we didn't think - I don't....it certainly wasn't something we were told to look at, to.... It was just the application, the interview, and if the person, you know, came across well, at the interview, it didn't really matter, you know?

Despite the existence of policies that aim to regulate the recruitment process and to promote anti-discriminatory practices, studies conducted in different educational contexts such as the University of Manchester (Beattie and Johnson, 2012) and a range of education institutions in Ontario (Abawi and Eizadirad, 2020) suggest that it is impossible to be entirely bias free and managers will, unwittingly, be influenced by their own experience, values and prejudice. In addition, Abawi and Eizadirad (2020) claim that policies that do not consider differences among candidates may ignore the barriers that potential candidates may encounter when applying for these kinds of positions and will fail to address the structural issue of lack of diversity in departments and institutions. Interestingly, Participants 3, 4, 7, and 8, who could be considered as the ‘standard’, are not entirely aware of the details of the recruitment process, and they based their comments on ‘trust’ or ‘faith’ without exploring this process further. By doing this, they seem to have given no thought to the potential consequences that blind-policies might have for potential candidates who do not fit the ‘standard’ ESOL lecturer profile. As will be seen in the next session, a more critical view is expressed by Participant 2 in relation to two different levels of the recruitment process: departmental and college wide.

Gatekeepers looking for 'like for like'

Reflecting on the challenges that candidates who apply for ESOL lecturing positions and do not fit the standard profile of the ESOL lecturer may face, Participant 2 commented that those who are responsible for hiring new staff are acting as “gatekeeper[s]” that “tend to hire alike people. [...] they’re all very similar”. This suggests that hiring practices may be privileging those who are perceived to fit the ‘standard’ profile of ESOL lecturer. This claim is supported by the work of Abawi and Eizadirad (2020). Participant 2 continued his reflection about hiring practices commenting on how people like himself – that is, gay men – who do not fit into what is perceived to be the ‘standard’ profile of ESOL lecturer are aware of their disadvantaged situation with regard to hiring criteria:

We know fine well, we aren't going to get them jobs, even though we may be the best person for them, because they're looking for another like for like person to fill the shoes of the person who's left.

In the previous section, a number of participants showed their trust and faith in the blind recruitment practices which involve the removal of personal information from applications before these are passed on to those who select candidates for interview. This implies that curriculum managers, who tend to be responsible for candidate selection, do not have access to information relating to candidates’ identity characteristics, including their sexual orientation. Those participants expressed their confidence in the selection decisions made by recruiters. There is, however, another stage in the process, not mentioned by them but brought to the fore by Participant 2: the completion of the application form before it is submitted for consideration. Participant 2 explained that for him, having to identify himself as gay while filling in the application is the first barrier to apply for a position as an ESOL lecturer as he perceives that the hiring team may not want learners to be exposed to people who do not fit the heteronormative ‘standard’:

I think the application process can sometimes be a barrier, because if you're having to tick that you're a gay man, or you're part of the LGBT community, I think that sometimes that is your first barrier, because maybe there's thought that their learners wouldn't want to be taught by someone like that. Or they want to be taught by a certain type of person. And that almost is filtering out the kind of people that they don't want to identify with their departments.

As already noted, the current blind system employed by HR departments at Further Education colleges prevents recruiters, at departmental level, from accessing the personal details of applicants. Therefore, Participant 2’s words denote either lack of faith in the system or lack of knowledge. Be this as it may, his fear of being discriminated against in the application process on account of his sexual orientation is neither irrational nor uncommon among ESOL practitioners who belong to the LGBTQ+ community, and, on many occasions, forces some practitioners to hide this part of their identity in the workplace (Nelson, 1993, Gray and Cooke, 2019). Flage's (2019) meta-analysis of 17 different studies from OECD countries that focused on sexual orientation discrimination shows that discrimination based on sexual orientation is

common in the OECD labour market, with openly gay or lesbian people facing 40% lower positive responses to job applications than openly straight people -although this varies from industry to industry and across countries. The reasons for this, as Flage observes, are partly the stereotypical views and prejudice that some institutions or hiring managers may have about gay or lesbian people (Flage, 2019). Although there is no data to suggest that this is the case in the Scottish Further Education sector, Participant 2's statement highlights the concerns that applicants who do not fit the standard ESOL lecturer profile are likely to have.

Prior experience

As noted in section 6.4 of this chapter, participants seem to agree on (and regret) the fact that “[there is] a very limited range of race within the department” (Participant 9), as Scottish ESOL departments are predominately dominated by white, Scottish or British practitioners. Some participants reflected on the potential reasons for this lack of diversity. As seen above, ‘standard’ participants put it down to lack of interest from practitioners who do not fit the standard profile in joining the profession. None of these participants put it down to actual discriminatory practices; however, there seem to be other ‘hidden’ or less obvious barriers. One of them is the type of professional experience required to work as ESOL lecturer in the Scottish college sector. Some participants (Participant 4, Participant 7 and Participant 8) stated that a requirement for candidates who apply for ESOL lecturer jobs is to have experience within the Further Education sector. The implication of this requirement, according to Participant 7, is that it may exclude competent candidates who have experience in other ELT contexts, having worked abroad or in other types of institutions, thus perpetuating the lack of diversity in the profession:

I felt like that really excluded quite a lot of candidates that probably were very good candidates, but hadn't necessarily already worked in this context, but have worked in a number of different contexts within the EFL world, but not necessarily ESOL in a college.[...] Maybe the fact that we used desirable criteria of having college experience in that selection process is actually perpetuating the problem, because the people who have the college experience already, are from a particular background group, characteristic group. And then therefore, if we're using that as a way to narrow down the list, we're not allowing that problem to change. Because, perhaps, there are other people within that list who are more diverse, but don't have the college experience ... we're not allowing those people.

It is worth noting two euphemisms in this excerpt: the one used to refer to the community ESOL sector: “not necessarily ESOL in a college” (Participant 7); and the one used to refer to the typical ESOL lecturer identified earlier in this chapter: “the people that have the college experience already, are from a particular background group, characteristic group” (Participant 7). Thus, what initially seemed to be a job requirement based solely on experience also intersects with issues of ethnicity, along with the perception of the ESOL community sector as the 'other' or less prestigious - as discussed in section 6.4.6. In the extract above, Participant 7 appeared to be aware that some of these requirements act as barriers for qualified individuals from more diverse backgrounds and are supporting the status quo, and indicated that this should be reviewed:

But perhaps, experience wise is where we could make tweaks to what we would consider a shortlist of applicants (Participant 7).

This shows that some curriculum managers, who are in a position of relative power in ESOL, are becoming aware of the lack of diversity in the departments and are reflecting on the possible challenges that some of their hiring criteria may present for people from more diverse backgrounds who may be interested in entering the profession. This is an example of what Freire (2000) calls solidarity with the 'oppressed' group; that is, those who, like Participant 7, have some power to transform the practices and policies that are stopping diversity in the profession are the ones that should be initiating the change to make the profession more inclusive.

However, although, as Participant 7 suggested, relevant prior experience outside the college sector could be considered, this may not be sufficient to increase staff diversity in ESOL departments given other, often unspoken, exclusionary practices such as the tendency to employ native English speakers. As noted in section 6.4.3, all participants seemed to be aware that there is a prevalence of 'native' English speakers in their departments. This came up at various points during the interviews, including when the focus turned to the recruitment process. For example, Participant 3 stated that his institution seems to favour native English speakers in the hiring process, although he admitted that this is only based on his own "intuition", and he has not explored this further:

my gut feeling would say, [the identity of the candidates] probably does [influence the hiring process]. But I wouldn't have anything to back that up other than intuition. And by that, I mean that people hiring would be more likely to hire someone they perceive as a native speaker. But I don't have any, I don't have any evidence to back that up. It's just a sense of, of kind of what the preference would be within the organisation.

Therefore, while participants did not explicitly attribute this lack of diversity to discriminatory practices, subtle barriers, such as the preference for candidates with Further Education experience, perpetuate the dominance of a particular demographic in Scottish ESOL departments. These requirements, coupled with an unspoken bias towards native English speakers, maintain the status quo and hinder greater diversity in the profession.

Qualifications

Experience of teaching in Further Education is not the only requirement that may prevent individuals from diverse backgrounds from applying for a position as ESOL lecturer in a Scottish college. As Participant 7 explained, another requirement would be that applicants have a degree and a Certificate in Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages (CELTA , 2022):

we will ask for a CELTA as a minimum and a degree, that's our kind of bare minimum criteria. And then you've got layers of other things on top of that, that people could have masters or DELTA or TQFE or you know, all sorts of other acronyms of qualifications that you could get. And I still think they are valuable. I think there's use,

there's a reason that people do these qualifications, or there's a reason why we asked them to do them. So, I don't think that's something that would change.

The information provided by Participant 7 with regard to the minimum requirements seems consistent with almost all the job adverts consulted for this study, and during my time applying for ESOL lecturer roles in Scottish colleges. As an example, West College Scotland's advert published in 2024 (*TESOL Career Center: West College Scotland Lecturer (ESOL), 2024*) clearly states that candidates need a CELTA or equivalent qualification together with a qualification to SCQF level 9, which corresponds to an ordinary degree according to the information provided in the Ready Reckoner (SQA, 2023):

Currently we are looking to recruit a full time, permanent lecturer in ESOL. You will be qualified to SCQF level 9, and will have a Recognised TESOL qualification (Cambridge CELTA or equivalent) as well as evidence of relevant CPD¹⁶ (*TESOL Career Center: West College Scotland Lecturer (ESOL), 2024, n.p.*).

Another example from Dundee and Angus College's advert for a similar position does not seem to require¹⁷ candidates to have a degree, but it explicitly states that having a CELTA is one of the essential criteria for this position.

¹⁶ CPD: Continuing professional development.

¹⁷ I could not gain access to the full specifications for this position as the job advert was expired when consulted. For this reason, I cannot entirely assume that a degree was not part of the requirements for the job.

Fig. 5: Dundee and Angus College. Job advert 2023 (retrieved from NATECLA SCOTLAND, 2023)

Only one of the adverts for the position of ESOL Lecturer consulted in the context of this study did not require a CELTA qualification for the post; it only required candidates to have a degree in a relevant subject. This advert was for North East Scotland College, as shown in the figure below:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Fig. 6. ESOL Lecturer job advert from North East Scotland College (North East Scotland College, 2022)

Therefore, it seems that a CELTA qualification is a standard requirement for the position of ESOL lecturer in Scottish colleges. Some participants believe that this requirement is problematic because, although this type of qualification can be considered a “specialist qualification” (Participant 6), it is awarded by private institutions and, very importantly for this study, the associated cost can be a barrier for people from disadvantaged backgrounds, thus limiting their opportunity to enter the profession. As an example of the importance of financial resources for acquiring such a qualification, Participant 1 explained that he was only able to obtain his qualification because he had financial support from his family. Participant 1 also touched upon the intersection of socio-economic status and ethnicity suggesting that it can potentially impact career development and staff diversity. He seemed to be aware of his privileged position, and acknowledged that for other people, like his own students, – that is migrants with no financial resources or family network – the opportunity to study is near impossible:

I mean, I had - when I did the PGDE I had a young family. My wife couldn't work because the children were young, and it was really tough financially. Now, I only was able to do that because my parents were able to basically support us for a few months, I mean, my parents aren't wealthy, but I would describe - my mum was a teacher and so, my dad maybe more working class in his profession but my mom was a teacher. I come from middle class background who can afford to fund their kids through periods like that. I don't know how it's going to be possible for a lot of my students ... imagine this situation where they've got young families, you know. At the moment their - their, you know, dad is struggling to find work post COVID just you know, working in logistics or doing deliveries.

Money can buy the time necessary to gain the required qualifications. As Participant 1 explains in the following excerpt, currently, Further Education institutions are requiring higher levels of professional qualifications, and, in his view, this could be another barrier for people from minority or disadvantaged backgrounds, who have neither the money nor the time needed to pursue them:

In the past, a lot of people came into the college sector without... without a teaching qualification and there's been this drive to professionalize the sector. Now, if you're going to do that, if you're going to professionalize, uhm..., you know, they want us all to be GTCS registered now, and the implication of that is going forward. We're supposed to be hiring people that have either got a TQFE or PGDE, or something like that...if you're going to have people that have either done a degree or - Well, yeah, I mean if you're if you're going to be hiring people who've got TQFE or PGDE like I do, then you're going to be hiring people that have also done a degree. I mean, that's going to be a long pipeline - if you're wanting to expect people from minority backgrounds that have recently arrived in the UK, people from refugee families to get them to the point where they managed to get through university have the money and the inclination to then do either the TQFE or the PGDE, like I did. I mean that takes time.

Again, Participant 1 eloquently discusses the barriers that migrants from ethnic minority backgrounds may experience to gain the required qualifications to work as ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges. For him, it is not only a matter of funds but also a matter of time because, for some migrants, getting their right to work in the UK is a lengthy process. As an example of this lengthy process, I have included a statement published by The Scottish Government (2023, n.p.) referring to the process for asylum seekers to obtain permission to work:

asylum seekers in all parts of the UK have to wait 12 months before being able to apply for permission to work from the Home Office and if granted permission they are restricted to roles on the Shortage Occupation List.

This 'essential' qualification requirement highlights an intersection between the economic or class background of the candidates and their migration status, which serve to exclude a potential pool of candidates that appeared not to be interested, as pointed out at the beginning of this section. Thus, the limited diversity in the Scottish college ESOL departments may not be related to a 'lack of interest' from individuals from diverse backgrounds, but rather

to some of the requirements listed in job adverts for such positions, which are less likely to be met by individuals who do not fit the 'standard' ESOL lecturer profile.

The discussion in this section has served to establish that despite policies such as the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010) that aim to ensure fairness in the hiring process, there are other structural factors that are preventing this diversity. This is an example of what Collins and Bilge (2020) describe as the *structural domain* of power which, in this case, is reflected in hiring practices that function as institutional mechanisms to reinforce social inequalities and uphold the dominance of certain groups within ESOL departments. However, as I discuss in the next section, due to the dynamic nature of power (Smooth, 2013; Appleby, 2016), those who are perceived to be the dominant group in the ESOL departments can also experience situations of disadvantage.

6.5.2 Career trajectories of female lecturing staff

While considering reasons for the lack of staff diversity, it was interesting to reflect on some comments relating to gender representation in management roles in ESOL departments in the Scottish college sector. It seems clear from available data (see section 6.4) and from what the participants in this study said, that white, middle-aged, British women hold certain positions of power in the ESOL college profession as they can be considered the 'standard'. However, as discussed in the literature review, power is dynamic (Appleby, 2013; Smooth, 2013) and individuals or groups can be discriminated and privileged at the same time, depending on the context. When it comes to management roles in a female dominated profession, one would expect to see more women as heads of departments or curriculum managers. However, that is not always the case, as Participants 4 and 8 in particular explained during the course of their interviews.

At the time that this research was conducted, according to Participant 4, the management team of her college was predominantly male. In her opinion, this imbalance was due to women appearing uninterested in this type of managerial positions at that particular moment in time, although she noted that the situation has been shifting throughout the years:

Actually, a lot of the team when the curriculum head jobs went up, a lot of the women in the team just weren't really that interested in doing that particular role, for whatever reason, whereas before our head of department was female. And then we had, I think, three at one point, three curriculum heads that were female, so it changes all the time. But it's quite interesting at this particular point in time.

This male prevalence in the management team at the time of the interview is construed as an exception when she says, "but it's quite interesting at this particular point in time". It is worth noting that Participant 4 used the same language to refer to women's lack of interest as other participants used to refer to ethnic minorities' reluctance to apply for ESOL positions in the college sector. Having noticed this lexical similarity, I probed the participant to elaborate on the possible reasons beyond this alleged 'lack of interest'. She replied:

ehm.... I think...I guess just the luck of the draw and the people that were interested at that particular point in time, they changed the roles from.... I can't remember what it was called Senior Lecturer was it? And then they changed the rule so the curriculum heads would have line management responsibilities for similar pay. And I think a lot of people weren't that keen on the idea of line management, they were more interested in kind of strategic and supporting the lecturing staff.[...]..and then there's also things like some women, some of them, some of our team had childcare roles, so just wanted to focus on that.

Her answer indicates that there are two types of reasons for the female lecturing staff's perceived lack of interest in managerial roles. The first one is coincidence (what she calls the "luck of the draw and the people that were interested at that particular point in time"). The second one is related to changes in the curriculum head position and the new managerial remit which seems to be in conflict with certain female lecturers' interest in contributing to strategic development and supporting lecturing staff, on the one hand, and with motherhood responsibilities, on the other.

Participant 4's comment on women choosing between childcare responsibilities and their careers reflects Guyotte's (2018, p.44) experience, who, reflecting on her career and her role as a mother, admits that "[she] knew that, eventually, a decision would have to be made", explaining that she had to question what things she would need to "give up" if she prioritised her role as a mother or her career. This seems to be a common struggle for women who consider taking on increased responsibilities in Further and Higher Education as it is reflected on the work of Arenas Ramiro (2017). It also shows a structural issue that goes beyond ESOL departments, and even the college as an institution. For this reason, Guyotte (2018) believes that this problem cannot be solved without government policies in place to help women who want to take on higher positions, for example by providing financial help for childcare, or covering family travel expenses for conferences and career development opportunities (ibid.). The Scottish Government is aware of the struggles of women in Scotland in this sense, not only in the FE and HE context, but in the whole Scottish economic landscape, and has acknowledged that "[a]vailability of high quality, affordable, and flexible childcare is a central factor in enabling women to participate fully in the labour market" (Scotland, Scottish Government, and APS Group Scotland, 2019 p.11). To tackle this and other issues, the government suggest flexible working, however, the implementation and analysis of the consequent effects of this measure has not been reported:

Flexible working and thinking about job design is crucially important to women who have caring responsibilities, to disabled women, and for those who wish to change their working patterns as they approach the end of their working life (Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2019, p. 23).

The struggles of women working in the FE or HE education context do not seem to be only a matter of juggling motherhood and career. The reluctance to take on managerial positions mentioned by Participant 4 was also elaborated on by Participant 8. The context of her experience is similar: with the college merger, the senior lecturer position she had recently applied for became more business-like, more managerial and, as a result, less enjoyable. A

later restructuring forced her to choose between reverting to a lecturer post with no managerial responsibilities and a full managerial position; she chose the former for reasons she provides in full in this excerpt:

[...] at that time, I applied for a senior lecturer post, and I got the post and stressed myself out horribly for about six...six years? yeah.... I don't even know why I applied for that job. I think it was just an inevitability, have you been somewhere and you've been a good teacher, then you were kind of pushed then to go in for a promotion, but as the college merged, it just changed the whole kind of ethos of the college and it became very, very corporate.... And initially, I kind of ran with that, and... you know, I was holding the banner for the college, but then I just became very disillusioned with it, and thankfully, they restructured about two years ago and they made senior lecturers redundant, but you could keep your teaching. So, it was either, you know, go back to full time teaching or take a promotion into complete management, line management. So, although at the time I felt very... Yeah, I was a bit betrayed by the whole thing because I felt like I'd put you know, I've made a lot of sacrifices...and, you know, I've had, you know, a couple of times off with really pretty bad stress... You know, I felt like I'd done a lot of work and it was like, not appreciated at all, but actually, it was a blessing in disguise. I've gone back to the classroom and I'm much happier again, you know, and just we connected with students and with other teachers as you know, a peer not, you know, being a senior lecturer, I was in the middle I wasn't one thing or the other, you know, it wasn't teacher but I wasn't a manager. So, it was just not for me. Soand although I was like angry at the time of the restructure, it was really was a blessing in disguise.

Beyond the feeling of the inevitability of promotion, which is not exclusive to female educators, this reflection by Participant 8 creates an opportunity to question why some women do not feel comfortable, or are not interested in positions of greater responsibility within the departments, as this also seems to be the case in the broader TESOL profession, where the underrepresentation of women in positions of power has been addressed by different scholars throughout the years, such as Prentis and Mayne in their IATEFL session Where are the Women in ELT? (2015), and more recently by Sullivan and Kimura (2020) in a different context. In the Scottish FE context, the underrepresentation of women in senior positions has also been explored (Ducklin and Ozga, 2007; McTavish and Thomson, 2007) and acknowledged by the Scottish Government who have implemented an action plan to tackle this issue and facilitate the inclusion of women in more senior roles in FE and HE with measures which include “targeted mentoring, women-only development events around promotions rounds and reviews of promotions criteria” (Scotland, Scottish Government, and APS Group Scotland, 2019 p.37) and “urge[s] institutions, in consultation with the relevant trade unions, to careful [sic] consider the recommendations contained with the Universities and Colleges Employers Association report into intersectional gender and ethnic gaps in higher education” (ibid.p37).

This shows how, although, as discussed above, middle aged women are overrepresented in the profession and may appear to be privileged, they are also in a perceived disadvantaged position when it comes to promotion into more senior roles in the college.

6.5.3 Recruiters' perceptions of student expectations

In addition to issues relating to the recruitment process, participants also attributed the lack of staff diversity to colleges' attempts to match what they perceive as student expectations regarding the profile of teaching staff. One aspect that came up on a few occasions is sexual orientation. From the participants' responses, it seems clear that ESOL learners, particularly adults, may "come to class with strong, fully formed views on these issues" (Stella and MacDougall, 2021, p.375) and perhaps, being openly out or discussing aspects of sexual orientation may "clash with the cultural and religious sensibilities of learners" (ibid.).

In the following excerpt, Participant 1 shares his approach to LGBT+ issues, which are consciously avoided and only addressed if they casually emerge:

Personally, because it's something that's quite difficult and a lot of people have very strongly held religious points of views in the class...It's something that I will...I will raise if it comes up and I will make it very clear what my point of view is on the subject, but it's not something I would plan a whole session around like some of my colleagues might. I probably wouldn't.

However, Participant 1 clarified that the student population cannot be regarded as one homogeneous group. He referred to an age and level-related difference in the student cohort, explaining that it is easier to discuss issues related to sexual orientation with younger students than with older students who may have stronger views on this matter as a result of their background:

With my, you know, especially not with my lower level ESOL learners on LGBTQI issues, whereas I might have done it with my [previous] learners in the past [in a different learning situation outside the college context].

With mymy upper intermediate students it's much easier to talk about [sexuality]. My upper intermediate class happen to be young and they're kind of just out of school at the end of 4th year and I can talk about all that kind of stuff with them and it's no problem and....Generally....You you experience very little prejudice from them, but.... sometimes with the lower-level learners who also happen to be older and they...also happen to be more...usually more religious and traditional in their backgrounds. Sometimes that that's a bit harder to talk about, so...it's just a skim over.

Participant 8 argued that it may be controversial for some ESOL learners to be taught by a member of the LGBTQ+ community, and, as a result, LGBTQ+ lecturers may need to hide this part of their identity to protect themselves from possible prejudice:

I think sometimes it's, it's it's, you know, if we talk about like sexuality and all that it's more difficult to be diverse and be openly diverse about it when you're working with ESOL learners. Ehmm... so perhaps some colleagues who ehm.... some, you know, some gay colleagues might not be open... they might not be talking about that so

much in the classroom because they just don't want this the spotlight to be on ... on them.

The fear of being questioned by students intersects with concerns about how ESOL learners might react if they discover their lecturer is gay. Together, these fears contribute to the reinforcement of heteronormativity in ESOL departments, reflected in the classroom materials and the way these topics are approached in the field and contribute to what Collins and Bilge (2020) call the *disciplinary domain* of power. This domain operates by enforcing standards that shape individuals' behaviours and thoughts, often subtly reinforcing social hierarchies and inequalities. In educational settings, such as colleges, the curriculum, classroom discussions, and materials can serve as mechanisms of regulation and control, which in this case leads to privileging heteronormative values while marginalizing others.

It is also worth noting Participant 8's discussion above in regard to how LGBTQ+ lecturers may need to 'hide' this identity characteristic from the learners to avoid difficult or unpleasant situations. This is a clear example of how interactions with students shape the way in which LTI is negotiated or 'performed' in the classroom and influenced by students (Barkhuizen, 2017). In this case, this 'performance' may reinforce the feeling of lack of belonging among LGBTQ+ staff and generate tensions between the lecturers' identities and the students' beliefs. This practitioners' reluctance to be 'openly out' in the classroom has been identified previously in other ELT contexts such as America (Nelson, 1993) and the UK (Gray and Cooke, 2019). In the American context, Nelson (1993) points out that the perceived 'heterosexism' makes some 'queer' people "compelled" (Nelson, 1993, p. 144) to hide any personal information from learners to avoid problematic attitudes. Stella and MacDougall (2021) point out that, as a consequence, there is an invisibility of LGBTQ issues in ELT and ESOL, and discussions on topics related to gender identity and sexuality are often avoided in the classroom. As suggested in the previous section, these perceptions may also, consciously or not, influence the hiring decisions of ESOL curriculum managers and of the college as an institution because of a perception that, as pointed out by Participant 2, "that their learners wouldn't want to be taught by someone like that". Therefore, despite having policies in place such as the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010) that prevent institutions from discriminating against job candidates or staff based on their identity characteristics, the perception of how ESOL students may react can generate unconscious bias on curriculum managers that have negative impact on the LGBTQ+ community (Ivanovic, 2019). This could be understood as an example of the *institutional domain* of power (Collins and Bilge, 2020), where the hiring practices are perpetuating the heteronormative status quo. However, as I discussed in section 6.5.1 of this chapter there are curriculum managers who are becoming aware of their position of relative power, and the effects that their decisions may have in terms of diversity; as a result of this awareness, they are starting to look for alternative practices. The solutions suggested by the participants themselves will be presented in the following section.

6. 5 Theme 4: Ways to increase staff diversity

During the interviews, most participants seemed positive that "everybody would like to see more diversity within the teaching staff" (Participant 1). This was based on the belief that

bringing more diversity into the ESOL departments in Scottish colleges can have positive effects on the profession and is important for ESOL learners, from an academic and pastoral perspective, as discussed in section 6.3 of this chapter. This section considers the participants' views and reflections on how such change can be achieved.

6.5.1 The 'other' as the driver of change

When considering ways to increase staff diversity, an important question to ask is whose responsibility it is to drive this process. During the interviews, there seemed to be a suggestion that such change must be driven by "the younger ones" (Participant 1) and "the newcomers" (Participant 5) who seem to be coming from more diverse backgrounds, compared to ESOL lecturers who are "well established" (Participant 5). The indication seems to be that staff from diverse backgrounds (including those who are outside the middle age bracket which, as noted in theme 2, seems to be the 'standard' in the Scottish ESOL teaching force) are best positioned to introduce diverse perspectives and make relevant changes in the ESOL departments. This resonates with Crenshaw's (1989) basement metaphor discussed in Chapter 2 specifically in relation to identities which are constantly negotiated. In this metaphor, those at the bottom, in this case the 'Other', hold a "revolutionary potential" Carastathis (2016, p. 73) of liberation, or change. Those at the bottom cannot only liberate themselves but also liberate everyone else in the basement. In the context of this study, the 'Others' are seen as not only potentially revolutionary to incorporate change for themselves, but also to bring change to the whole department. This can be seen clearly in the excerpt below where Participant 8 refers to "teachers who are diverse", making an evident distinction between the 'standard' and the 'other', and putting the responsibility for change on those who "want to share their diversity":

if you have teachers who are diverse, and who want to share their diversity with their learners, then it becomes less forced, if you know what I mean, like, it's not just something you're saying, "Okay, this week, we're going to do this". And it's, it's more a natural process....

Similarly, in discussing issues related to sexual orientation, Participant 1 shared that he does not feel comfortable discussing these issues with students, but that one of his colleagues who is part of the LGBTQ+ community could address these issues with students:

In terms of sexuality, we've got one member of staff that is gay, and you know, will address issues, of equality in that respect with the students.

From the perspective of the 'other', this responsibility for being the change makers seems to be internalised. This emerged from the interview with Participant 2, who does not fit the 'standard' heteronormative profile, and described himself as 'young'. Referring to lecturing staff who have characteristics that are outside what is considered 'standard', Participant 2 stated very openly that "we should be embracing change". In his opinion, as a young, gay lecturer he has been able to offer different perspectives, and other people in his department "found it refreshing to have a new pair of eyes". Participant 2 argued that it's "quite good for [more established members of staff] maybe to see what our younger audience has got to bring". These statements suggest that Participant 2 sees himself as somebody who can help staff embrace more diverse perspectives and seems to be willing to take an active role in this.

For him, the change needs to come from 'inside' the profession, from the bottom, moving upwards. In his view, "unless we start making the change then the change won't happen".

Participant 5, who as a reminder, perceives herself as the 'odd one out' in her department because of her migrant background and her French as first language, also believes that people 'like her', who have been in similar situations to the ones the students might be facing, are able to introduce new perspectives into the ESOL field, as, in her opinion, she is able to understand the students' struggles better than others:

I can bring things like for example, what I discussed with my colleagues, when I arrived in [this city]¹⁸, I couldn't say the name of the streets, the name of the neighbourhoods, the name of the other cities in Scotland, the name of people, I couldn't pronounce first names or surnames, and it's something you need to teach. It's not something that you can learn fast. If you can't say the name of your doctor, and you've got an appointment, it's the first thing they ask you at reception. Well, if you haven't been in my situation, you will not think about that.

It is worth noting that, although Participant 5 made very clear throughout the interview that she feels othered in her department in the college, for example, when she stated that she "feel[s] a bit like the, you know, the odd one out", she seemed to feel very connected to the students and empathetic towards them. She seems to be aware of the challenges they may face and, drawing on her experiences, is keen to support them in developing skills that can help them navigate these challenges. This is illustrated in the following excerpt where she restates her opinion about the reasons we need more diverse teams in Scottish ESOL departments:

So that's why you need a diverse team. If you've never experienced racism, or other forms of discrimination, how can you relate to your students? Whereas I've got, I've got colleagues from Western East Africa, they've experienced discrimination, I've experienced discrimination. We know what it's like, we know how it feels. And we can relate to our students, and we can discuss the topics and ways to deal, you know, with some, some issues. So, I think that's why it's very important to have a diverse team, because obviously, there are things that I don't know and that my other colleagues know.

These statements are aligned with Freire's (2000) argument that change must come bottom up, initiated by the 'other'. However, when the onus to drive change is on the 'other', one could argue that this is a double-edged sword: on the one hand, diverse staff are given the opportunity to make changes that can be beneficial for students and the wider teaching force, but, on the other hand, this places a disproportionate burden on them. In this situation, staff who fit the 'standard' ESOL lecturer profile could be seen to relinquish their responsibilities to improve a situation which they have acknowledged as requiring change (theme 1). If increasing diversity should be a collective goal shared by everyone then staff who fit the 'standard' profile should consider what actions they can take to contribute to achieving this collective objective, or what Freire (2000) describes as having solidarity with the 'oppressed'

¹⁸ Replaced for anonymity

and questioning the ways in which they can contribute to support the issues that affect the 'other'. Participant 7 seems to recognise this. As a curriculum manager who is responsible for hiring new members of staff in her department, she has actively worked on educating herself and has become aware of her ability to introduce change within the college:

having done bits and bobs of reading and things recently, I have become aware of how you might need to positively create a situation where people are being put into roles in order to then be able to perpetuate itself more moving forward. Because if you're never giving people the chance to get into those roles, then it doesn't have the chance to sort of filter down through this, through the system.

Participant 7 seems to suggest that college staff who have the power to appoint teaching staff from diverse backgrounds should do so because this can help increase diversity moving forward. She seems to be hopeful that this can be done:

Well, I guess it's for, again, I can only talk from [...] myself, and the fact that I am trying to educate myself on being more diverse and more inclusive, I do see the value in having a diverse staff. So I'd like to hope that we can find ways to make that happen.[...] [M]aybe moving forward, we can think and I hadn't actually considered until I'm talking to you right now that perhaps using that particular criteria to narrow the list down has affected the pool of people that we have. And so maybe in the next round of interviews, we consider something different so that we can try to, to diversify a little bit more.

This willingness to change responds to Richardson's (2016) request to employers to analyse discriminatory practices in their own context in order to revise their hiring criteria and use their position of power to transform the profession. This highlights how the work of Foucault and Gordon (1980) around power and misuse of power has permeated the ESOL and ELT profession. In the field of ELT, Richardson (2016) also asked those who are in positions of power to re-think and reevaluate hiring criteria to encourage inclusivity.

6.5.2 Positive discrimination

According to some participants, one way to increase staff diversity is through positive discrimination. One concrete suggestion relating to this came from Participant 6 who argued that in order to diversify the profession, funding should be available to people from diverse backgrounds who would like to study for these types of specialist qualifications that are required to work as an ESOL lecturer in Scottish colleges but do not have the financial resources to do so:

I suppose access to the specialist qualifications I mentioned to you would have to be broadened perhaps through, you know, public funds or some sort of funds becoming available for people to access those courses.

However, Participant 6 acknowledged that this may not be feasible as these specialist qualifications are offered by private institutions, which is a complicating factor:

But you see those...those qualifications are provided by ... Well, Trinity College, London, Royal Society of Arts, I think. And as far as I know, these are private bodies, they're not state bodies. And so, I think there would be a problem there in a in a, in a state institution, what is effectively a state institution like the college recognising.... I don't know whether that's the case or not. But I mean, you have to have some recognition of these other qualifications....

At the moment, in Scotland there is funding available for people who are willing to study undergraduate degrees and some postgraduate degrees (SAAS: *Student Award Agency Scotland*, 2022) as well as some support available for refugees and asylum seekers to progress to Higher Education (Universities Scotland 7 Scottish Refugee Council, 2016). However, there is no funding available for 'specialist' qualifications such as CELTA that, as discussed earlier, are considered to be 'essential requirements' for ESOL positions. In the UK only England offers financial help for people who would like to undertake this course (*Cambridge: English Language Assessment*, 2022).

According to Participant 1, another way to encourage diversity in the ESOL profession through positive discrimination is by introducing flexibility in the hiring criteria. He was optimistic in believing that current ESOL learners will be willing to become ESOL lecturers in the future:

I'm hoping that will change over the years as the students that we are teaching become better at English, become more integrated in Scottish society and maybe want to do the job themselves. Certainly, a lot of the students say to me "I would like to be an ESOL teacher like you. This looks like a good job" and quite often they'll find work once they've, you know, progressed through upper intermediate. They'll be able to find work as interpreters within the school or just for local, you know, for charities doing volunteer work and things like that, and... ultimately, I hope some of these people could be ESOL teachers.

However, in his view, this may only be possible if there is some level of "flexibility about what is expected from an ESOL teacher and, as will be seen in the next section, he suggests that compromise may be necessary.

As alluded above, Participant 7 also considered positive discrimination during recruitment, explaining that, as a Curriculum Manager, she would support "positive discrimination" because "the learners [in her college] are from such a wide variety of race backgrounds, that [she] think[s] it would be a really useful thing for [the department] to have that represented more on [their] staff". However, she recognised that this may not be possible in the current system, as members of the panel selecting applicants for interview do not have access to information about applicants' personal characteristics:

'And I'm also kind of constricted with HR processes. That's dictated to me I cannot do that ... not follow what the rules of the college are, what their HR processes are.'

While positive discrimination may increase diversity in the ESOL profession, this suggestion should be considered in the context of the following comments by Participant 5, who as

previously noted, comes from a diverse background and could be identified as 'other'. Participant 5 remarked that the challenge is not about welcoming diverse people into the profession, but allowing the newcomers to be "different", as, in her view, once they enter the profession, they are required "to fit the mould" and adapt to a curriculum and teaching environment that "[is] bums on seats" and there is no space for any other methods or adaptation. Participant 5 seemed to believe that, in the college environment, there is no "flexibility to be diverse" and even if there "[was] a diverse team, and we want to, we want to bring our diversity, we don't always have the opportunity, because that's not what we are... meant to do. That's not what we are paid for." Consequently, in Participant 5's view, the change should start by allowing more flexibility in the curriculum and in the classroom in a way that embraces other ways of teaching that perhaps are not so 'standard' in the college sector but that would suit better students and teachers who do not come from a traditional Western education system.

6.5.3 Compromise

As noted above, when discussing the ways in which the ESOL profession could be diversified, Participant 1 remarked that ESOL students who come from a variety of backgrounds could be good candidates to work as ESOL lecturers in the future. However, he made clear that for this to happen, the curriculum managers might have "to compromise a little on somebody having a very, very high level of grammar ability in order to get somebody who is more representative and that the students can identify with". These statements show Participant 1's willingness to change, and welcome people from different backgrounds into the profession. However, his idea of 'compromising grammar' implies the assumption that the 'other' may not have a good command of the language and may never be as good as those who speak English as first language, which, in turn, suggests that they could never be at the same level as 'native speakers'. This, coming from the perspective of a white, native English speaker, resonates with Courtney (2017) who highlights the way in which having a good command of English is perceived as power. Furthermore, it highlights the discourse of whiteness and native-speakerism that is still so prevalent in the global TESOL profession (Floris and Renandya, 2020, Gerald, 2020).

On a related note, Participant 1 suggested that maybe

there should be a place for people with ... not quite such a high level, to teach in community classes and to teach maybe lower-level learners with the college because maybe they don't need that super high level [qualification] and maybe there's a balance there.

While this compromise could increase staff diversity by allowing ESOL practitioners who do not have specialist qualifications to teach some college classes, albeit lower-level ones, arguably, this arrangement could reinforce the divide between the 'standard' ESOL lecturer who teaches in college and the 'other' ESOL practitioner whose teaching is mainly restricted to community settings.

6.5.4 Organic change

Some participants seemed to believe that diversity in ESOL lecturing staff will occur organically, in tandem with changes in the wider community. As Participant 4 put it, the profession will “get more and more diverse just the same way that Scotland's getting more and more diverse. Well, more and more, a little bit more diverse”. Three participants (P5, P8 and P1) remarked that this change towards a more diverse profession is already visible in Scottish ESOL departments in some ways. For example, Participant 8 highlighted that “in comparison to 16 years ago, it's certainly moving in a more diverse direction”.

Gradual diversification in relation to gender was highlighted as an aspect of identity that is making the departments more visibly diverse. For example, Participant 1 noted that “there are more ESOL teachers writing ‘they’ as their gender pronoun”. This would suggest a step towards the conception of gender as a spectrum rather than as a binary, which reflects wider societal moves in this direction.

Participant 9 also suggested that change will come organically, from ‘outside’ the profession. She commented that, although “the percentage of non-white non... non UK teachers [in ESOL departments] is ... is still very low”, the change will come from bigger social movements such as ‘Black Lives Matter’, which will permeate the profession and will make it “attractive enough to attract people from different, diverse backgrounds into it” in a similar way that has happened “down South”¹⁹ where, in her view, the teaching population is “much more diverse”. The data regarding the ethnic backgrounds of the staff working in Scottish colleges shows that only 2% of the staff belong to Ethnic Minorities²⁰ (Colleges Scotland, 2021) while in England it is over 11% (Education and Training Foundation, 2020). Although this data reflects the whole college sector in these nations and is not specific to ESOL departments, it indicates the difference between England and Scotland in this particular aspect that Participant 9 reflects on.

While most participants were optimistic about organic change in a positive direction, Participant 3 was rather pessimistic when reflecting on the bigger picture, which he linked to wider, structural forces:

I think it's also related to the political situation. I think if Scotland continues to be run by Westminster's government, then we will continue to become more of a closed nation. And that will affect ESOL and ESOL practices. If Scotland goes a different path, then I would see the country opening up and everything changing. So how will it develop? ... If we do have a kind of far-right government the way that we have at the moment... If that continues, and there's nothing to say that it won't, then I think that the UK will become more closed in and diversity in many aspects will reduce.

¹⁹ England

²⁰ This term is used in the report. The Scottish Government, (2021) defines as Ethnic minorities everyone who self-defines as belonging to the following ethnic backgrounds: White Other, White Polish, White Irish, Chinese, Indian, Pakistani, African and Asian Other; therefore the 11% of the English report has been calculated based on this definition.

Having said that, Participant 3 also suggested that it could be interesting to look at the development of more populated areas in the UK such as London to get a better idea of what the direction of ESOL departments could be in terms of staff diversity. As noted above, at the moment, college staff in England seem to be slightly more diverse than in Scotland (Education and Training Foundation, 2020), therefore, Participant 3 seemed to imply that if Scotland follows the English model, the Scottish ESOL profession could also become more diverse.

6. 6 Conclusion

In conclusion, this chapter has provided an in-depth examination of the multifaceted barriers contributing to the lack of diversity in the ESOL profession within Scottish colleges. Through a detailed thematic analysis of qualitative data from interviews, several critical themes emerged, evidencing the predominance of white, middle-aged, and middle-class lecturers in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges, and the underrepresentation of minority ethnic and LGBTQ+ individuals. The disparity between the diverse student body and the homogenous staff profile underscores the pressing need for more inclusive hiring practices and institutional reforms.

The findings highlight the influence of stereotypes and biases in the recruitment process, the financial and systemic 'barriers' faced by potential candidates from diverse backgrounds, and the impact of gender and socio-economic status on career trajectories within the ESOL college sector. To address these challenges, the participants of the study suggested several strategies, including funding for qualifications, revising hiring criteria, or compromising the level of qualifications and experience required to work in ESOL college departments.

In addition, this discussion offers an example of how the framework of intersectionality employed in a non-hierarchical approach, together with the thematic analysis employed in this chapter have been helpful tools to identify current challenges that affect ESOL lecturers and the Scottish FE ESOL profession as a whole. This approach was employed to explore the participants' identities and experiences and how they relate to dynamic power structures. Moreover, it evidenced the use of studies of this kind that invite participants to reflect and discuss issues that they had not previously considered. In relation to this, this chapter also showed the need to include a reflection of LTI and its effects on the departments and on students as part of the college practice.

The next chapter focuses on critically analysing the language used by the participants of this study during the interviews, to explore how, through discourse, they contribute or challenge the current hegemonic structures in Scottish ESOL education, and the Further Education institutions.

Chapter 7 - Findings Part 2: Critical Discourse Analysis

7.1. Introduction

This chapter presents the findings of the critical discourse analysis (CDA) of the participants' interviews. As noted by Esposito (2024), the framework of intersectionality in which this study is situated enables the critical discursive analysis of the different systems of oppressions that shape our multiple identities and determine our positions within hierarchies of power and privilege. The thematic analysis of the findings offered in the previous chapter identified four main themes relating to specific aspects of ESOL education in the Scottish college sector; it also explored how different identity characteristics and practices of the teaching staff intersect and reinforce certain unsupportive practices over others in the profession. The structure of this chapter has been guided by the language the participants used to discuss the division between the 'standard' and the 'other' (addressed in Chapter 6), as well as topics related to gender roles, LGBT+ issues, and ethnicity. Other identity factors such as class, addressed in chapter 6, are excluded as the analysis of the participants' language did not contribute any new insights beyond those already covered in the previous chapter. As discussed in the methodology chapter, both chapters should be read as complementary, rather than in isolation, as together they enhance the discussion around power dynamics and identity in the Scottish ESOL college sector.

In this chapter, I explore, from a critical discourse analysis lens, how language and discourse have been used by the participants of this study to reproduce or challenge what is perceived as the 'Truth', that is, a set of beliefs that are considered the norm within a particular group of people or a society (Foucault and Gordon, 1980), in this context, within the ESOL teaching profession in Scottish FE colleges. There is a mutual relationship between power and knowledge as "knowledge shapes what action is possible and what power is exercised, those actions also shape the creation of new knowledge and what is thereby given credence" (Powell, 2015, p. 403). For this reason, and indeed for the purposes of this study, language is considered an essential tool to explore power systems as it is through language that power can be challenged, subverted, distributed, and even abused (Fairclough, 1989; Wodak, 2002).

From this perspective, Fairclough (2013, p. 532) believes that educational institutions such as colleges are a "core domain" of linguistic and discursive power as they are designed to transmit knowledge focusing on maintaining the status quo and replicating existing cultural values, identities and pedagogies. A related argument was put forward by Foucault, who understands educational institutions, as well as political and economic institutions, as apparatuses that help to circulate the 'Truth' for the benefit of a few who hold positions of power in society, and it is often the language of, and used within, such institutions, which evidences the interweavings of power (Foucault and Gordon, 1980). It is important to note that power is not *just* language; there are other ways in which power can be exercised, for example by using physical force (Fairclough, 1989) but this is out with the focus of this study.

For this reason, a further analysis of the data has been conducted using critical discourse analysis focusing on exploring the relationship between language and power within the specific context and historical setting in which this study is situated. This analysis enabled me to identify explicit and implicit power relations related to ingrained beliefs that are present in the day-to-day practices of the colleges in Scotland so that these can be discussed and explored within their contexts (Wodak, 2002). This led me to analyse the participants' language to address the research questions of this study, which focus on identifying unequal practices resulting from a perceived imbalance of power in the relationships within the profession. The analysis also explores how participants' language reflects the interaction and intersection of identity characteristics, affecting both individual ESOL lecturers and the broader ESOL profession in Scottish colleges.

7.2. The approach to CDA in this study

There is no one single approach to CDA; instead, it can be approached from many different perspectives (e.g., semantic, syntactic, pragmatic, stylistic) and using a variety of different methods (e.g., observations, interviews, experiment) (Fairclough, 1989; Wodak, 2002). Regardless of the strategy employed, CDA is an essential tool to explore the relationship between language and power structures in a particular setting with its own ideologies, social practices and interactions (Wodak and Meyer, 2009). Thus, the analysis and interpretations of language discussed in this chapter should be read within the particular perspective from which each participant was responding to the interviews, that is, from their position within the college and their own identity, and must not be generalized to any other context (Wodak, 2002). Accordingly, for the purpose of this study, I selected an appropriate approach to help me, as a researcher, to answer the research questions, providing sufficient contextual data for the reader to understand the basis for the analysis (Wodak and Meyer, 2009; Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). For this reason, in order to understand the analysis of the findings provided in this chapter, the reader should take into account the contextual information provided in chapter 2, and the information about the participants discussed in section 6.2 of the previous chapter. At specific points in this chapter, I included additional information about individual participants that is relevant to the understanding of a particular part of the analysis.

For the present study, the analysis follows the steps described by Thompson, Rickett and Day, (2018) in conducting a Foucauldian-informed critical analysis of the discourse. This means that the overarching analysis relates to power, and criticality is employed in analyzing the specific language used by the participants (Foucault, 1991). In order to analyse the language used by the participants in depth I started to familiarise myself with the data. First, I selected and labelled words and phrases in a way that helped me identify recurrent codes and discursive patterns. Thus, in this chapter I analyse key extracts from the interviews focusing on the exploration of linguistic aspects such as vocabulary, grammatical structures, and linguistic functions that are explicit in the text while noting what is 'not there'. This can help to identify and explain what aspects are important or emphasized in a particular interaction, helping to shape and identify the dominant discourse of particular spoken utterances. Following Amoussou and Ayodele (2018), I conducted a critical discursive analysis focusing on the sociological context of the specific locus of the research. My own positionality and experience

within the study's context have also played a crucial role in shaping this analysis. Self-reflexivity has been consistently employed, as demonstrated throughout the chapter, to ensure a critical engagement with both the data and my role as a researcher and as a former ESOL lecturer in a Scottish college.

7.3 The 'standard' v the 'other'

As discussed in the previous chapter, most participants observed that their ESOL departments are not particularly diverse in terms of the lecturers' identity characteristics and a 'standard' profile of ESOL lecturers was identified. This is characterised by being predominantly white, middle class, heterosexual, and having English as a first language, in opposition to the 'other' which referred to those participants who did not identify with these categories. It is worth noting here, as a reminder, that this distinction between the 'standard' and 'other' is only a methodological choice that enabled the discussion around power and hierarchies, and these positions can shift depending on contextual factors.

Based on this division, in this section the focus is on the different ways the participants referred to the dominance of the 'standard' and perceived lack of diversity. It seemed evident that their discourse was influenced by their own personal views, their identity, and their perceived position within the college and the broader profession. There was a clear difference in both the level of awareness and the language used to discuss the lack of diversity in departments between those who fit the positions of the 'standard' and the 'other.' For example, in the short extract below, Participant 2, who, as a reminder, perceived himself as the 'other', referred in a direct manner and with no hesitation to the lack of diversity in his department and the perceived lack of any change. This suggests that he had reflected on these issues prior to the interview, perhaps as a necessity to understand his 'otherness' and his position within his department, and within the ESOL profession more broadly:

I think when you look at it, some departments are all **very much similar**²¹ in their kind of identities. And when you – when you look across the spectrum, you **don't see very much change**, and you **don't see diversity** and working on it for a while now, it's been **very static**

Interestingly, as shown below, he balanced this utterance using both an affirmative and a negative structure, mirroring the grammatical pattern on both occasions using clear and straightforward language, which serves to emphasize his points and suggests that he was confident in the way he perceived this, but at the same time, shows preoccupation with this particular aspect of the profession:

- Very much similar = you don't see diversity
- Very static = you don't see very much change

²¹ I have highlighted the words in bold to indicate the language I am discussing in this section.

In addition, in the above utterance, the use of the intensifying adverb “very” with adjectives that, in his view, have negative connotations, such as “static” and “similar” to refer to the lack of diversity, together with the negative structures used, implies that this participant is not conforming to the current situation in the profession. In other words, he disagrees with the situation he is describing and is challenging the dominant ideology (Fairclough, 1989) recognizing a clear hegemony which he associates with institutional power. It is also worth noting the way in which, in this short extract, he started the utterance referring to his own opinion: “I think”, but he quickly distanced himself from this position by avoiding the use of the first person and shifting to a more impersonal use of the second person (you) when discussing his views on the lack of diversity in the department. This is an example of how Participant 2 views his own identity as an 'outsider' or the 'other' in this particular context. This idea is reinforced in the rest of this utterance when he referred to his own experience stating that he had been “working on it for a while now”, but he does not preface it with the pronoun “I”. This is another example of how, through discourse, the speaker shows his detached relationship with the profession and his department (Gee, 2010).

On the other hand, Participant 7, who (as discussed in the previous chapter) admitted that she had not thought about diversity in her department prior to the interview, expressed her views about the lecturers’ diversity in her own department in a more hesitant way; she was less direct than Participant 2 and reformulated sentences to clarify meaning. This suggests that, maybe, she was not so certain about her views on this, perhaps as a result of the lack of prior consideration of this issue. However, this also suggests that she may not have felt entirely comfortable expressing this opinion because she was conscious of her status within the college and aware of the potential implications this may have coming from a person of her position as the ESOL curriculum manager in a large college. If this is the case, she might be contributing to the current hegemony by not questioning the perceived ‘limited’ diversity that is present in her department:

But as I said, we in our department, particularly, there is a... it's very limited in terms of the range of diversity we have, we have a couple of little tokens, I don't mean, tokenism, like we put them in just [to tick a box] but there's a couple of people who fit slightly different criteria for each of the different characteristics. But it's not across the board, the vast majority of people are very similar in... in those characteristics.

In the above extract, there is a certain lack of awareness of the potential impact of the lack of diversity on the ‘other’ and on the profession by almost diminishing it in the way she used terms such as “very limited”, “a couple”, “slightly” to make her statements lighter. In addition, she expressed her views in a very fragmented way, very often clarifying and reformulating sentences to clear her own thoughts about this topic, which suggests that she was unsure about how to articulate her views in regard to this matter. It is also worth pointing out how, unlike Participant 2, she expressed a clear feeling of belonging to the dominant discourses by employing the pronouns “we” and “our” and is complicit in the status quo by dismissing any potential effects that this lack of diversity might have on the ‘other’. This sense of belonging contrasts with her use of the word “token” to refer to “people who fit slightly different criteria”, which creates a dichotomy between the ‘Truth’ and the ‘other’ (Foucault and Gordon, 1980) evidencing her position of power in this particular context, and

acknowledging that it may be the case that some people in her department may be part of the profession only as 'examples' of diversity. However, Participant 7 also showed certain collusion with the hegemony but does not seem to agree entirely with the dominant ideology. This is reflected in what Fairclough (1989) terms as 'oppositional' wording which consists of making a conscious change by replacing the word "tokenism", which is a term that reinforces the dominant ideology, with another concept such as "people who fit slightly different criteria" that shows the speaker's rejection of the negative connotations of the term 'tokenism'. In this way, she transformed a rather negative term to a more inclusive perception of the 'other' reinforcing a positive relation with the 'other' (Gee, 2010). The deliberate shift in perspective demonstrated by Participant 7 in the above utterance highlights how this study has facilitated a deeper reflection on her position within the hegemonic structure of her department, as well as her role within the broader institution of the college.

Participant 8 commenced discussing her views on diversity explaining that "we're all so different in my department". However, when she started exploring this in more detail, she realised that her department is made up of "predominantly white, predominantly heterosexual, native speakers" and "perhaps not really that diverse if you were to look at it". This change of perspective clearly exemplifies how she moved from a position of lack of awareness of the different identities in her department, to suddenly identifying the dominant discourse of the profession. Once she acknowledged this, Participant 8 expressed her perceptions on diversity in a similar way to Participant 7, repeatedly using hedges such as "kind of", "I think" and "maybe" as well as fillers such as "like" or "yeah". The use of fillers such as the ones employed in the extract below is worth noting as they are used to clarify, pause, reformulate, or confirm the speaker's statements (Baker and Ellece, 2011). However, they also show how the speaker is trying to organise these ideas in her own head, avoiding terms that she does not feel comfortable with. This suggests that she became conscious of her place within the hegemonic structure, and for this reason her language around inequality and injustice became more cautious. She ended her response explaining that she had not thought about this topic before, perhaps as an excuse to justify her fragmented discourse:

I think we're...yeah, we're more diverse than [the other departments] are. We have like yeah... that seems quite white male, kind of angry man kind of department. I think we got Yeah, I think in comparison, I think it depends on the subject, though. You'll always find like, maybe in business, there'll be more like, and.... Yeah, I think ESOL probably is a bit more diverse than other departments. Yeah. But not that I'd ever thought about that (Participant 8).

In addition, Participant 8's extract above shows her assumptions about other departments in the college and the position of power they hold within the institution. For example, she perceives the business department to be represented by "white male, kind of angry man" which seems to represent the dominant ideology in the college. In contrast, she believes that her ESOL department is more diverse, and therefore, is presented in opposition to the dominant ideology in the college. This way, she shows her awareness of diversity and power structures within the broader institution and how, in her view, her department may be less powerful within this structure as it does not fully align with the dominant ideology of the college.

While Participant 2's language is direct and clear, the language used by Participants 7 and 8 is full of hedges, hesitations and reformulation. While the 'other' (Participant 2) had reflected on these aspects, and his position within ESOL college departments, the 'standard' (P7 and P8) demonstrated that they had not reflected on this issue before. This shows how those who fit the standard in this particular context tend not to think about issues that are of utmost importance for the 'other', and suggests a lack of engagement with the concerns of the 'other' (Appleby, 2016). In this sense, by not being aware of the issues that do not affect them directly, they are reinforcing the status quo, missing the possibility of change, and widening the gap between the 'standard' and the 'other'. It is interesting to observe at this point how the CDA in this section underpins and serves to further elucidate issues explored through thematic analysis and presented in chapter 6. In addition, it provides an example of how power is created and embedded in the institution and reflected in the language used by people who work in that institution.

This contrast in the discourse between Participant 2 and Participants 7 and 8 is interesting not only in the way they express their ideas linguistically, but also from the power positions they hold. While Participant 2 was an ESOL tutor in a small rural college, Participants 7 and 8 were, or had been, in managerial positions in bigger and more affluent colleges and, therefore, part of the hegemonic structure. This may help to explain the fact that their views were presented in a more cautious manner and that they were conscious of their position of power; that is, they were aware of themselves in a larger setting where the capillaries of power may be more evident on a daily basis, and they may be more sensitive to how they sit within the overall power structure. They may be beholden to, or even at the mercy of these capillaries of power, and they need to be careful with the language they use lest they diminish themselves in the eyes of the people who hold this hegemonic power. In addition, working for a more affluent college means that their views and perceptions have the potential to impact a larger number of students and, as a result, they may be careful about what views they share and how they express them, and of the implications that their words may have on others and on their ESOL departments. This is an example of how their position of relative power in their departments and in the profession more widely, could have been used to engage with the issues that affect those who, like Participant 2, feel othered in the profession partly because of the lack of diversity of staff in ESOL departments. This shows how inequality permeates ESOL departments.

This perceived lack of awareness of the structural issues that affect the 'other' identified in the Participant 7 and Participant 8's discourse, resonates with the work of Freire (2000), who believes that those who are in privileged positions, to whom he refers as the 'oppressors', are often not aware of their position of *having more*, which results in leaving the 'others' at a disadvantage. In this particular context, it could be said that it is not just a disadvantage, but institutional inequality. It is important to note, however, that all participants are also affected by the structural domain of power (Collins and Bilge, 2020), which shapes how institutions are organised to maintain the hegemony. In this particular context, Participants 7 and 8 are also

at the mercy of other power structures within the institutions, and, therefore, as Freire (2000) might describe, could also be considered oppressed²².

Such implicit prejudice is also present in the participants' discussion around blind hiring practices and how they influence, or not, diversity in the departments. Participants who identified as white, native English speakers, heterosexuals, and British and who, in this context, could be perceived as privileged, described the process employed in the college to implement the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010) using the semantic fields of 'faith' and 'trust' as highlighted in bold in the extracts below:

there's the protected characteristics and the Equality Act, **I'd like to believe** that recruiters are recruiting solely on their ...the merits of the skills that are in the CV and on the interview (Participant 4)

I have quite a lot of faith in that message that they present, I do **believe** that my employer has a very strong desire to be an equal opportunity employer and, and takes measures to ensure that recruitment is there (Participant 6)

in my own working place at the moment, everything **seems to be** based on interview, and how the person interviews (Participant 3).

The way in which these participants (P4, P6, and P3) used language with expressions such as "I'd like to believe", "I have quite a lot of faith", "believe" and "seems to be" shows that they did not have the need to investigate how their institutions implement these policies because they did not appear to be negatively affected by them. For this reason, they can rely on 'faith' and 'trust' and choose not to challenge the status quo by not investigating this further. On the contrary, Participant 2, who believed to be negatively affected by the hiring practices, used more direct language and referred to concrete behaviours that, in his view, reinforce the current status quo, and prevent diversity in ESOL departments:

We know fine well, we aren't going to get them jobs, even though we may be the best and best person hired for them, because they're looking for another like for like person to fill the shoes of the person who's left.

It is worth highlighting the contrast between the semantic fields of 'trust' and 'faith' used by the participants above (P4, P6 and P3), and Participant 2's utterance which seems to be based on certainty and knowledge: "we know fine well". Participant 2's awareness of unspoken biases during the hiring process, despite the presence of formal equality policies, reflects an understanding of how his identity and positionality intersect with institutional structures of power. On this occasion, this variance in the use of language between the different participants fits the distinction between 'standard' and 'other'.

During the interview with Participant 9, I asked her if she had considered how the 'other' might feel working in an ESOL department where all the other colleagues had similar identity characteristics. Participant 9 had a long career in ESOL and although at the time of the

²² This is the term employed by Freire. In the context of this chapter I understand it as those who are not in a position of privilege in a particular situation.

interview, she was an ESOL lecturer, she had previously held a senior position in an ESOL department in another college. For this reason, I anticipated that her response could be influenced by her experiences of being a former senior lecturer and current lecturer in a similar way to Participant 7's response. The language she used in her response suggests a certain level of awareness of the struggles that the 'other' might encounter in the profession in relation to their sense of belonging. As I have highlighted in bold below, Participant 9 repeated three times "it must be tough", which serves to strengthen her opinion about this topic. This is reinforced with her use of grammar where she switched between the modal verb "must" and the present tense "it's tough", which shows a high degree of certainty and acknowledgement of the 'other'. In this sense, she is the only participant from those who fit within the 'standard' that was able to identify the perceived lack of diversity in departments as a potential issue for the 'other'. This acknowledgment of the potential struggles for the 'other' can be understood as what Freire (2000) calls solidarity with the oppressed; however, there is no indication from Participant 9 that she intended to challenge or overturn this situation:

I think **it must, it must be, it's tough, it must be tough** to come into an all-white environment, if you're the only person from a different ethnicity (Participant 9).

Instead of developing her argument, she continued her response by suddenly distancing herself from her previous position of solidarity with the 'other' and adopting a similar perspective to that of Participants 4, 3 and 6 discussed above. She wants to believe that everyone feels included, but this is only a 'suspicion'. This is expressed with grammatical structures that are less certain than the ones used in the first part of her response, as highlighted in bold in the excerpt below:

But I **suspect if you spoke** to the teachers who are from different, different ethnicities and backgrounds, I think they **would probably** say that they do feel quite welcomed, and they do feel that you feel part of the team (Participant 9).

This change of attitude towards the 'other', moving from a position of solidarity and understanding, to failing to acknowledge that there might be an issue could be because Participant 9 does not want to explore how her own actions as part of the privileged hegemony might support or hinder inclusion in ESOL departments. As I discussed in the previous chapter, during her interview Participant 9 reiterated on many occasions that the lack of diversity seems to be a consequence of the limited pool of candidates that apply for ESOL lecturer positions in the college, but, from her perspective, ESOL is a very welcoming profession. Therefore, overall, it seems clear that she does not want to question current practices, or the ways in which the current system and behaviours may be contributing to the perceived feeling of otherness among staff and the general lack of diversity in ESOL departments.

In addition, the use of the second conditional (if you spoke to the teachers... I think they would probably say...) shows that despite admitting that it must be difficult for colleagues who come from a different background to feel welcomed in the department, in reality, she had not engaged in conversations with those colleagues to understand their perceptions. This resonates with the idea of 'faith' discussed above, that by 'believing' that everything works

well, there is no need for further investigation. This type of language, especially coming from positions of perceived power perpetuates inequality by leaving it unchallenged.

Freire (2000) points out that in order to start to eradicate situations of inequality and injustice, each individual should be aware of their own position of power or disadvantage within a particular society; this is attempted by Participant 9 above, where she seemed to understand her position of privilege in the department and acknowledges the 'other', however, this is not enough to change the situation as she did not seem to have an interest in this, as discussed above. Other participants demonstrated a lack of awareness of their own position within the college which reveals that participants do not have the opportunity to discuss diversity in the college and to engage in conversations around inclusion with colleagues from different backgrounds and roles both within the department and in the wider ESOL college sector. In addition, it is also worth noting that none of the participants referred to any CPD training on anti-racism, decolonisation of the curriculum or equality, diversity and inclusion, which is evidence of a gap in the discourse about these matters; this has also been my experience while working as an ESOL lecturer. When conducting the interviews for this study, I gave the participants the opportunity to reflect on their own position in the profession, and issues around diversity. Some participants made it clear during the interviews that they had never thought about these topics before, which is also an indication of a blinkered approach to social justice in the college sector. This gap in the discourse, and lack of engagement with social justice practices in this respect are evidence of underlying power structures, where certain issues or topics are excluded from the discourse, consciously or not, in a way that supports the current status quo (Foucault and Gordon, 1980; Fairclough, 1989). This perceived lack of engagement with social justice may be surprising in ESOL as there are policies such as the Adult ESOL Strategy (2015) that support such engagement within the sector; however, it is evidence of the tensions with policies such as DYW (2014) that focus on employability and practical skills and that seem to permeate different areas of ESOL in further education (Brown, 2017). In addition, the lack of agency that ESOL lecturers and curriculum managers have in terms of policies (Brown and Sheridan, 2024) seems to influence the attitude of the lecturers in other areas of ESOL education in this particular context reflecting this lack of engagement with social justice.

This is important because, as Freire (2000 p.49) states, "true solidarity with the oppressed means fighting at their side to transform the objective reality which has made them these 'beings from another'". In this context, it is essential that managers and senior members of staff who are in the position to make changes that can enable people from different backgrounds and with different identity characteristics to enter the profession, become fully aware of the current situation. This awareness is a starting point for enabling change to happen in the different areas of ESOL in relation to staff, the curriculum and the materials, which will then allow for an increase in diversity within the profession.

It is worth noting, that as discussed in the previous chapter, ESOL curriculum managers are also bound by institutional and national regulations, or what Collins and Bilge (2020) refer to as the *structural domains* of power; this institutional constraint, however, does not justify the perceived lack of engagement with social justice identified in the language of some of the participants (P8, P8, P9, P4, P6 and P3) discussed above. Even if they were to achieve 'true solidarity' with those who might be encountering situations of injustice in ESOL departments,

their power to change the profession is limited, and they would need the support of their institution, or even the government in order to fully transform the profession. However, as Freire (2000) notes, on some occasions, if those in more powerful positions are not willing to re-evaluate their position of power, the change can start from the lower level of the hierarchy, that is, the change might need to start from the 'other'.

7.4 Gender roles, promotion, and the domains of power

In section 6.5.2 of the previous chapter, I discussed the struggles of some women who feel they need to choose between their career and family responsibilities, and their negative feelings towards promotion (Arenas Ramiro, 2017; Guyotte, 2018). In this section, I focus on the analysis of the language participants used to discuss these matters, and how this relates to broader issues of power and hegemony in the ESOL college sector.

I start by exploring the following extract from Participant 8 where she discussed her experience working as a senior lecturer, and how after the restructure of her department she had to choose between going back to a lecturer role or being promoted into a role with more responsibilities. In this analysis I employ semantic fields as a useful tool to study the experiences of an individual in a particular context (Fairclough, 1989). One of the most prominent semantic fields is the one of 'bad feelings' that appears when Participant 8 describes her own experience as a senior lecturer (words highlighted in bold).

[...]at that time, I applied for a senior lecturer post, and I got the post and **stressed myself out horribly** for about six...six years? yeah.... I don't even know why I applied for that job. I think it was just an inevitability, have you been somewhere, and you've been a good teacher, then you were kind of pushed then to go in for a promotion, but as the college merged, it just changed the whole kind of ethos of the college and it became very, very corporate.... And initially, I kind of ran with that, and... you know, I was holding the banner for the college, but then I just became very **disillusioned** with it, and thankfully, they restructured about two years ago and they made senior lecturers redundant, but you could keep your teaching. So, it was either, you know, go back to full time teaching or take a promotion into complete management, line management. So although at the time I felt very... Yeah, I was a bit **betrayed** by the whole thing because I felt like I'd put you know, **I've made a lot of sacrifices**...and, you know, I've had, you know, a couple of times off with really **pretty bad stress**... You know, I felt like I'd done a lot of work, and it was like, **not appreciated** at all.

This semantic field reflects how the *structural domain* of power (Collins and Bilge, 2020) of the college can negatively affect an individual, even if this individual is in a perceived position of power. This is a clear example of the dynamic nature of power, which depends on relationships rather than being a static entity (Collins and Bilge, 2020). In this case, this participant is both in a position of power in relation to ESOL lecturers as she is a senior member of staff, but also in a disadvantaged position in her relationship with the overarching college hierarchy which exercises power over her creating these feelings of discomfort expressed in the extract above, as can be seen in the words highlighted in bold.

This contrasts with the references to 'good feelings' or 'relief' made when she explained that she took the role of lecturer again (see words highlighted in bold below). Some examples of this feeling of relief were expressed with words such as "thankfully", "connected" and "happier" and were evident when she admitted that going back to a lecturing position "was really a blessing in disguise". This statement was repeated twice, reaffirming her opinion and feelings towards this change. In contrast, there is a discourse of 'nonbelonging' to the managerial roles in statements such as "I wasn't one thing or the other" and "[middle management] was just not for me" which shows her sense of otherness in relation to the senior lecturer role:

[...] but actually, it was a **blessing in disguise**. I've gone back to the classroom and I'm **much happier** again, you know, and just we **connected** with students and with other teachers as you know, a peer not, you know, being a senior lecturer, I was in the middle I wasn't one thing or the other, you know, it wasn't teacher, but I wasn't a manager. So, it was just not for me. Soand although I was like angry at the time of the restructure, **it was really was a blessing in disguise** (Participant 8).

In this particular case, hierarchies within the institution are evident as Participant 8's perception was that the institution clearly exercised power over her as she felt "pushed" to take a more senior role. This push towards promotion described by Participant 8 could be understood as a response to unspoken norms within the college to move toward positions of power. However, despite her "sacrifices" to fulfil the expectations of the institution or more senior workers, Participant 8 ultimately felt "betrayed" and "disillusioned" with this position. Such perceptions around power could be explored through the *structural* power domains identified by Collins and Bilge (2020) who believe that there is a *disciplinary domain* of power that pushes people into the status quo forcing them to follow certain rules, beliefs and regulations that are valued in a certain institution or society. If these are not adhered to, the individual will be pressured, 'disciplined', or returned to their previous position in a particular society, in this case, the college. This idea was also explored by Foucault and Gordon (1980) in terms of ideology and repression, and adopted in relation to the Scottish Further Education context by Allan (2015 p.152), who clearly elucidates how all members of staff in the college need to adhere to the expected rules and behaviours that are required in this particular society (the college):

All the staff within a college setting have to negotiate, and perhaps even accede to, overt and covert rules, discourses of both the classroom and of the college itself, but they also have to adopt the expected behaviour involved in being a staff member in a Scottish college which has been learnt or subsumed [...] from a variety of factors, situations and more established colleagues.

For Participant 8, promotion seemed to be inevitable and almost a natural progression for members of staff who had been working in the college for a relatively long period of time. For this reason, she perceived it as part of the "expected behaviour[s]" that Allan (2015 p.152) refers to above and continued in the role despite not feeling comfortable in that position. The decision of going back to a lecturer position was not something she was able to control and

admitted being “angry” about it at the beginning. Again, this shows that despite having a position of relative power within the profession Participant 8 was, one more time, affected by the *structural* domain of power that she could not control.

These rules and expected behaviours are the ‘status quo’ or dominant ideology, which traditionally, have been shaped “by men to serve men” (Vella, 2022 p.123) and more particularly, white, heterosexual males (ibid.). This may help to understand the feeling of non-belonging expressed by Participant 8, as well as the reason why other women working in ESOL appear not to be interested in applying for managerial positions in their departments, as claimed by Participant 4 and discussed in the previous chapter.

The dominant white heterosexual male discourse in educational leadership makes it difficult for some women to combine their family responsibilities with their professional career (Arenas Ramiro, 2017; Vella, 2022). In this case, although Participant 8 could be perceived as an ESOL practitioner who fits into the ‘standard’ of being white, British and a native English speaker and, therefore, could be considered to be privileged in the profession, the analysis of the findings helped to identify a situation in which this participant shifted from being in a position of power to a position of what Freire (2000) may consider as oppression. This is a clear example of the dynamic nature of power relationships (Appleby, 2013, Collins and Bilge, 2020) and the overarching mechanisms of power that regulate institutions and affect individuals. In this case, the intersectional framework employed in this study and the non-hierarchical approach to understanding identity characteristics was helpful in enabling me to understand the power structures affecting this participant, and the way participants’ identity characteristics interconnect. This may have not been possible if I had employed a hierarchical approach to identity characteristics as I would have overlooked this particular inequality.

7.5 LGBTQ community, and the discourse of invisibility and silence

In chapter 6, I discussed how heteronormative values that are present in society, and in the field of ESOL (Gray and Cooke, 2019; Moore, 2021) are also present in the participants’ departments. From a discursive perspective, I also identified a dominant heteronormative discourse that can be perceived as the ‘Truth’ (Foucault and Gordon, 1980) and which affects the profession in different ways. Through the *cultural domain* of power (Collins and Bilge, 2020) certain ideas or cultural representations are emphasized and valued in a particular society (i.e. the college, or the department) and any deviation from this is considered ‘abnormal’ or the ‘other’ (Brons, 2015). This can reinforce the feeling of otherness and invisibility among those who do not identify with those heteronormative values, creating a division between the ‘standard’ and the ‘other’, and, as discussed in the previous chapter, impacts hiring practices, and, therefore, supports the status quo.

The invisibility of the LGBTQ+ community (Gray and Cooke, 2019) in this particular context is evident in Participant 7’s discourse where there is a clear semantic field of ‘invisibility’ in the words highlighted in bold below. It is worth noting that, at the time of the interview, Participant 7 was the curriculum manager in a larger college, therefore, she held a position of relative power in the ESOL college sector:

I've just **completely overlooked** the fact that we do have slight diversity in our own sexuality within the department, but **it just didn't even occur to me**. And **completely slipped my mind** that that is, in fact the case (Participant 7).

This interaction suggests two ideas: first that the conversation about queerness is not widely discussed within this particular department, which highlights the discussion around the perceived invisibility of the LGBTQ community in ELT explored previously by other scholars (Nelson, 1993, Gray and Cooke, 2019, Moore, 2020) and identified in the thematic analysis of this study; and secondly, it suggests a lack of awareness and understanding of the feeling of otherness that some ESOL lecturers who belong to LGBTQ community, such as Participant 2, might experience.

This type of discourse, together with the current 'blind' hiring policies, and the concerns about the religious views of the students discussed in the previous chapter, intersect reinforcing the dominant heteronormative discourse in ESOL department.

7.5.1 Representations of gender identity and the power of silence to reinforce the dominant discourse.

From the thematic analysis it is clear that most participants believe that the ESOL profession is dominated by women, and that having a "good split", that is, a balanced number of male and female professionals, is considered to be "unusual" (Participant 8). Through the lens of critical discourse analysis, it is interesting to explore how participants consider gender as binary, referring to it simply in terms of male/female or man/woman, which excludes any other possible gender representation in the department (Strunk and Shelton, 2022). This binary system is problematic because, as Butler (2004) explains, it can only be understood under a hierarchical heterosexual system which is in itself restrictive and creates an exclusive way of understanding the gender field (Butler, 2004).

The binary system referred to above limits the opportunity to think outside these parameters and, therefore, stops people who do not align with this binary from being 'seen' in the ESOL profession. On this topic, Participant 6 reflected on the gender identities of people working in his department as follows: "I am not aware of any other individual identities that wouldn't be considered to be conventionally male or female". The use of the word *conventionally* assumes that any other representation of gender will be *unconventional*, and outside of what is considered the norm (Butler, 2004; Strunk and Shelton, 2022). This type of language that reinforces the traditional representation of gender as a male/female binary, rejects the possibility of any other representation of gender and reinforces the construct of the 'standard' and the 'other' in ESOL departments.

It is also worth noting that Participant 6 fits the 'standard' of being white, native English speaker, heterosexual and British and, therefore, could be perceived to be in a position of relative power. His perception of the gender binary as conventional and his position of relative power help to shape a certain discourse in the profession that is aligned with what Foucault understands as the 'Truth' (Foucault and Gordon, 1980) or dominant discourse. This contributes to shaping the ESOL profession in different areas, such as the feeling of otherness

among staff or students who might not align with this binary representation of gender that is represented in classroom practices or teaching materials.

This way of perceiving gender may lead to the creation of a hostile space for staff and students in ESOL whose gender identity does not correspond with male or female. It can also act as a barrier for potential applicants who do not fit these gender representations (Chung-Constant, 2012; Cameron, 2014). As a consequence, this perception of gender as binary perpetuates exclusionary practices in the profession.

Conversely, Participant 1 refers to other types of gender representation in the department acknowledging that “there are more ESOL teachers writing ‘they’ as their gender pronoun”. This statement is relevant in many ways. Firstly, because it is said by someone who fits the ‘standard’ of being white, native English speaker, heterosexual and male, but acknowledges the ‘other’ and points out a change in the profession that, in his view, is positive. This demonstrates how he solidarizes with the ‘oppressed’ (Freire, 2000) in order to understand their reality. In addition, this statement highlights the need to broaden the discussion about gender identities in this ESOL departments and in the college as an institution in order to create a space where all gender representations are considered *conventional* and, are therefore, included in the ‘Truth’ becoming the dominant discourse (Foucault and Gordon, 1980).

Interestingly, only two participants referred to gender representations in ESOL departments, which also highlights the ‘silence’ around this topic. This silence might be because different gender representations have been overlooked (as Participant 7 suggested above) due to its acceptance in British society, or because they remain unquestioned, thus reinforcing the binary conceptualization of gender. In addition, as discussed in chapter 6, some ESOL students have “very strongly held religious points of views in the class” (Participant 1), and representations of gender that deviate from the binary, might clash with their beliefs. This could also explain the perceived ‘silence’ around this topic, and the apparent interest to reinforce the dominant discourse to avoid difficult discussions in the classroom, which might lead practitioners to avoid using certain materials and topics in the classroom, as discussed in chapter 6.

7.6 The discourse around ethnicity

As discussed in the previous chapter, the discourse surrounding aspects of identity related to ethnicity, whiteness and the concept of ‘ethnic minority’ and, indeed, the power relations within which these areas coalesce is evident in the interviews with the participants of this study. While the presence of these issues may not be surprising in a discussion around ESOL in Scotland, a profession that aims to support migrants from different parts of the world (The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015), it is necessary to be aware of the concomitant issues of inequality that this discussion highlights. As seen in chapter 6, most participants also seem to recognise the apparent underrepresentation of students’ ethnic backgrounds among staff (Participants 1 and 6) and the general lack of diversity in their ESOL departments (Participants 5, 9, and 2); however, this acknowledgment is expressed in different ways. For example, it is interesting to note the hesitation shown by Participants 1 and 6 when

expressing these views. According to Wang (2021) hesitation is a part of spoken utterances which, although it is often disregarded, is “crucial as a conversational strategy” (ibid. p.824) and plays an important role in communication to convey the speaker’s thought process and positionality. In the following extract, Participant 1 shows hesitation using ‘vocalizations’ (uhmmm...) and false starts (there is..there are...) which suggest some difficulty planning the utterance, and demonstrate that the speaker is struggling to find the right words to express his views. This may suggest that he does not feel entirely comfortable with this idea.

[...] I would say that as things stand at the minute...**uhmmm, there is...**there are less of the minorities present within our student groups represented within the cohorts of teachers across colleges (Participant 1)

Similarly, Participant 6 also seems hesitant expressing his views. However, in this case hesitation is shown by what are known as “smallwords” (Wang, 2021, p. 824) or fillers, which are expressions such as ‘you know’, often used when the speaker “is not sure how to respond” (ibid. p.827). In addition, hesitation is also evident in the way the speaker uses false starts (I think that is a, that’s a...) and word repetition (the, the...; or,or...; that’s, that’s...)

We **as a as a, as a, as a** body, probably underrepresent **the the** community which we serve. We don't, as I mentioned to you, I think we **have to, we have to** never stop the black, but we don't have any other other... people from many other communities in, in [this city]. And, **you know**, I'm a bit surprised with that, really, because I'd thought that there would be people, especially from ethnic minority backgrounds, who have **maybe** skills in more than one language, who would **perhaps** naturally have been interested in working with people who come from overseas to settle here. And I don't know whether that's perhaps at the fold of the recruitment process, and that is not reaching the whole of the community here in [this city], **or, or** whether it's some other some other barrier to having people apply. **So, you know, that's, that's, I think that is a that's** a pity that we don't have more members of staff who come from the communities that we are actually working with (Participant 6)

In both cases, hesitation helps the speakers organise their thoughts to express their idea in the best possible way, which suggests that referring to the lack of representation of the students’ ethnic backgrounds among staff is not an easy topic to discuss, especially for participants who are white British, and therefore could be perceived as privileged from a minority ethnic perspective (McMahon, 2007; Gerald, 2020). In addition, it appears that the use of modal verbs (would) and adverbs of possibility (perhaps, maybe) are used here by the speakers to protect their ‘face’ and status within the profession. By hedging their statements with caution when discussing such a difficult topic, they seem to be trying to avoid any situation that may cause conflict if this was said publicly. They also serve to demonstrate how the speakers may be aware of their position of privilege within the unspoken structures of power in this situation and are being cautious with their opinions.

From the perspective of subject positions, that is, the ‘role’ an individual occupies in a conversation (Baker and Ellece, 2011), the speakers interact with me in very different ways.

Participant 1 appears to position himself as someone external to the profession, being objective and avoiding the division 'they/us' when he talks about the students and "the" cohort of teachers. On the other hand, Participant 6 refers to the teachers as "we as a body" including himself as part of the teachers' community and appeals to his own feelings to show his disappointment with this situation, explaining how he is "surprised", and he thinks that this imbalance of ethnic representation is "a pity". In addition, he emphasizes his lack of power to change the situation by referring to the recruitment process or "some other barrier" out of his own control, which shows a lack of engagement with his own position and the role he plays in the power structures of the profession. This shows, in two different ways, how on this occasion both participants are challenging the hegemony; Participant 1 does this from an 'outsider' position, while Participant 6 considers himself outwardly to be part of the structure and moves away from it with his language.

Participant 9, who, as a reminder, described herself as coming from "slightly mixed ethnicity" but, in the end, identified as white, and has been working in the ESOL/ELT profession for over twenty-five years, used the term "handful" to refer to the number of lecturers in her department who come from ethnic minorities; the connotations of this term indicate how, in her view, this is not enough and that she probably expected, and, in fact, even preferred more diversity in her department. This suggests that, like Participants 1 and 6, she is aware of the perceived prevalence of white lecturers in ESOL departments. She also seems to perceive this situation as unexpected as she expresses 'surprise' and 'shock' (highlighted in bold below for clarity), but also implies that she has probably not questioned the reasons that cause this situation, perhaps because of her perceived privilege in this context, where, although she comes from a mixed ethnic background, she is perceived as white, and therefore belongs to the 'standard'. On this occasion, by acknowledging the lack of ethnic diversity but not questioning it, she is supporting the current hegemonic structure that is present in her ESOL department:

There are more there are more teachers from diverse backgrounds now employed, but it's still a handful. So, and when you think about the time that's gone by that's quite **shocking**. Really, you know, it's **surprising, surprising** (Participant 9).

She then continued her response by rejecting the notion of institutional discrimination: "I don't think it's necessarily related to any kind of discriminatory recruitment practices". By ignoring this option, she also deflects attention from the possibility of any structural obstacles to diversity that may be caused by the current hiring practices. This shows how the language used by Participant 9, in this case, reflects the lack of awareness about the barriers in recruitment identified in chapter 6. In addition, by not questioning the hiring system that is implemented by the college at an institutional and departmental level, she is also preventing any form of change, and therefore, reinforcing the current status quo. She continued her utterance by shifting the attention to the 'other', and almost blaming ethnic minorities for their lack of interest: "it's more because people are not coming forward to apply for jobs". Lastly, she concluded her response admitting that she does not have an answer for the lack of ethnic diversity: "I don't know why that is". This demonstrates a disengagement with the discussion around ethnic diversity in ESOL departments, which she identified as a "whole other area of research" – an area she seems unwilling to explore. By distancing herself from the issue, she effectively removes herself from the possibility of being part of the change.

Thus, she seems to position herself as someone who, although is prepared to see diversity, is so rooted in the structures of power that she is not actively willing to make changes to make this happen. This reinforces the idea of the 'other' as the driver of change that was discussed in the previous chapter, and helps to support this finding:

But I don't think it's necessarily related to any kind of discriminatory recruitment practices. I think it's more because people are not coming forward to apply for jobs. Maybe I don't know why that is, but a whole other area of research. Wouldn't it? why... why do people from different backgrounds not want to become ESOL teachers?

This question prompted by Participant 9 is reminiscent of Participant 5's interaction about her feeling of otherness in the department related to her ethnic background and her own experience as a migrant now working in an ESOL department:

[...] For me, not having people who look like me all the time is difficult. And I don't mean exactly the same background as me. But I'm from a mixed background. I've lived in different countries, and in my family, people speak different languages and finding myself with colleagues who they don't speak any other language, they're white middle class, middle aged, and say, well, apart from the middle age, you know well, we don't really have a lot in common.

In this extract there is an evident distinction between 'they' (people in her department) and 'me' (herself) when she talks about her own experiences of speaking different languages, not being white, and being a migrant in a Scottish city. She explains that "apart from the middle age, [...] we don't really have a lot in common". This is interesting from a power relations point of view, as the 'othering' is not being imposed by her colleagues, but it seems to be imposed by a structural pressure that does not allow her to feel part of the system. This seems evident in the way she expresses her discomfort in the department saying that "it's difficult" to be part of an environment that she feels so distant from her own, and does not allow her to fully participate in the system, to an extent that she even "[...] think[s] that people like [them]²³ are more likely to teach in community education than in college"(Participant 5). This type of discourse reinforces the discussion in section 6.4.6 (chapter 6), where the community sector was identified as a place for the 'other'. In this way, power is not being exercised through overt pressure (Foucault and Gordon, 1980), but through hidden mechanisms of power that shape the profession in a very specific way; that is, by creating this feeling of discomfort for people like Participant 5, the power structures of the college remain unchanged.

Participant 5's feeling of otherness may help to explain exactly why Participant 9 feels that people from ethnic minorities do not seem to be interested in becoming ESOL lecturers. This can also be explained using Collins and Bilge's (2020) *cultural domain* of power, which helps to spread the dominant discourse across the profession; that is, the hegemonic discourse which arises from the decision-makers but weaves itself throughout all staff, resulting in clear structural injustice. As discussed in previous chapters, the hegemonic discourse in ELT (this includes ESOL and EFL) is that of the 'standard' English teacher is white, heterosexual, middle

²³ From ethnic minorities, migrants or people who do not speak English as a first language

class, and a native speaker of English. This idea is perpetuated and reproduced across the profession in different ways, for example in the materials used in class (Harwood, 2014), in certain job advertisements across the globe (Mahboob and Golden, 2013, Ruecker and Ives, 2015) and in the profile, the positionality and the language of English language teachers in the ELT departments (Gerald, 2020). Thus, the distribution of this dominant discourse creates a false impression of the profession existing only for people who ‘fit’ into these categories. This also reinforces the *disciplinary domain* of power (Collins and Bilge, 2020) that “coerce[s] people to stay on their prescribed paths” (p. 13) and to follow the status quo. This coercion is not done using violence or overt pressure, but by subtle, more indirect disciplinary practices which are evident in the language used by the participants in this study (Fairclough, 2013; Collins and Bilge, 2020).

7.7 Conclusion

The intention of this second analysis of the findings from a discursive perspective was to explore the way in which the participants of this study use language to support or challenge the hegemonic structures that are present within the ESOL departments in Scottish colleges, and in Further Education institutions more generally. In addition, this chapter aimed to support the analysis presented in chapter 6 by providing an alternative perspective to the discussion around power, hegemony and structural inequality in ESOL education in Scottish colleges. This has been done by exploring the language around power and different identity characteristics from a non-hierarchical perspective, guiding the analysis by the participants’ responses rather than from a pre-selected number of characteristics. This has enabled me to better understand the relationships of power between these characteristics and its relation to structures of power.

This analysis started by exploring the discourse around ‘otherness’ in the profession, and how the division between the ‘standard’ and the ‘other’ is influenced by the different positions of power and awareness of those positions that participants have at a particular time. This served to highlight how power, by its very nature, is fluid and shifts depending on a specific situation. As part of the discussion, I exemplified how even those who may be perceived as privileged for being considered to have a ‘standard’ ESOL teacher profile or hold a position of more responsibility such as senior lecturer or curriculum manager, can also feel, at times, disempowered or ‘unseen’ in the profession. However, on other occasions they might appear complicit in the discourses of inequality and injustice and support the hegemony by not taking action against clear instances of inequality.

This chapter also highlighted how the dominant discourse is present in the discussion around different, but interrelated, areas of identity, such as gender, sexual orientation, and ethnicity and permeates the language used by individual participants contributing to the maintenance of the status quo, and the general lack of diversity in ESOL departments that was perceived by the participants. In addition, I was able to identify ‘silences’ or gaps in the discourse that served to illustrate how certain ideas are excluded from the hegemonic discourse, and therefore, from different areas of the profession, including teaching materials, practices, and conversations. As a consequence, this exclusion reinforces the way in which structural inequality is continued and normalised. Thus, by putting the focus of the analysis on language

and 'how' things are said, I have been able to identify how dominant ideas are consciously or unconsciously spread and reinforced in the profession. This demonstrates how language can limit or enable certain identity characteristics which can be considered either 'the norm' or 'the other'; and makes clear how each plays a role in the discourses of power and inequality which permeate the ESOL field in the Scottish college sector.

Lastly, this chapter has highlighted a need for everyone involved in the college sector, and particularly in ESOL departments, to evaluate their position in the profession and how they might be helping to reinforce certain practices that may perpetuate inequality. Therefore, both analyses, thematic and discursive, are complementary and necessary to identify, explore, and understand situations in which ESOL lecturers may be in a position of privilege or disadvantage because of how different aspects of their identity or their role in their institution intersect. These analyses also show how the interplay of power is prevalent in ESOL departments and the broader college sector in Scotland. In addition, they also exemplify Foucault and Gordon's (1980) argument of power as dynamic, rather than static; the findings show this to be the case through the shifting positions and relationships captured in the participants' accounts of their experiences.

Chapter 8 - Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

The study explored the identities of ESOL lecturers working in Scottish colleges, and how their identities are perceived in the profession and how these may influence their experiences and practice. The topic was considered through the lens of intersectionality which proposes that identity characteristics should not be understood in isolation, but as part of a bigger, overarching, and interweaving power structure. The data for this study was gathered from semi-structured interviews with nine ESOL lecturers working in Scottish colleges at the time of the data collection. These interviews were analysed thematically, to identify the main themes and discussions relating to any perceived unequal practices associated with the lecturers' identities, and discursively, where the participants' language was examined critically in relation to power structures.

Each chapter of the study has served a particular purpose. Together, they present a rich and unique piece of research that illuminates an underexplored field and begins a discussion about the importance of the lecturers' identity in ESOL education, an important context where students are outside their country of origin and need to learn how to navigate a new culture, language, and environment (The Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2015).

This last chapter provides a discussion of the research questions as well as some personal reflections from the process of undertaking this study, its limitations, implications, main contributions and recommendations for future research.

8.2 Summary of chapters

The thesis is organised into eight chapters. Each chapter has a particular focus and function, but together they aim to contribute to the discussion around intersectionality, in relation to teacher identity in English language teaching and, particularly, in ESOL education in Scottish colleges. The study, which was motivated by my own personal and professional experiences, offers insights that could be valuable for members of the ESOL and ELT profession.

The introductory chapter started with an exploration of the rationale and the significance of the study as well as an explanation of the research questions and aims that were explored in this thesis. In the first chapter I also included an exploration of my own positionality as a researcher and a reflection on my place in this study. Chapter 2 started by introducing global issues related to the TESOL profession such as the debates on discrimination and the spread of English as a global language. Then, I continued with the discussion around the narrower context of this study: ESOL education in Scotland. In the last part of this chapter, I presented the historical background of intersectionality, and the work of two scholars who could be considered to be the 'mothers' of intersectionality: Kimberle Crenshaw, and Patricia Hill Collins. Chapter 3 consists of a review of the literature on important areas which are related to the study and underpin it, such as language teacher identity and unequal practices in TESOL

associated with identity characteristics, and 'othering' as a mechanism of power in ESOL. The topics discussed in this chapter have been essential to support the discussions in chapters 6 and 7 of this thesis.

Chapter 4 developed the theoretical framework for this study which stems from Crenshaw's (1989) theory of intersectionality and was adapted to suit the particular needs of this study in the context of ESOL in Scottish Further Education. This chapter conceptualised intersectionality in the way that it is understood in this study, and explained the way in which the framework was operationalised in the study. Chapter 5 offered a detailed explanation of the methodology employed for this research. In this chapter I described and justified the research design and outlined the research methods and instruments for data collection that were employed for this study in order to investigate the research questions presented in chapter 1.

Chapter 6 is the longest chapter as it explored the themes that arose from the interviews with the participants. It is complemented by Chapter 7, which explored the data through a linguistic lens, using critical discourse analysis to identify and understand the power relations embedded in discourse. Lastly, the present chapter, discusses the findings in relation to the research questions and aims that have guided this study. The chapter also offers an insight into the main contributions of this study to the field of ESOL, its implications and a reflection on my own experiences, and personal growth throughout the years that this study was conducted. Lastly, this chapter offers a final reflection on the limitations of the research, and makes recommendations for future research.

8.3 Research questions and aims

This study is the first of its kind to analyse ESOL lecturers' identity characteristics from an intersectional perspective within the Scottish Further Education context and, therefore, the findings discussed in relation to the research questions aim to contribute to the current debates regarding intersectionality in a broader context, but also to start a conversation around these issues in the Scottish ESOL college profession. This section draws on reflections from the findings in response to the research questions and aims.

RQ1: In what ways do the different identity variables of ESOL lecturers in the Scottish college context interact and intersect?

The identity variables analysed in this study were determined by the participants' own responses and the way they chose to describe their identity and that of others. Age, gender, ethnicity, nationality and first language were the most discussed identity variables in the participant interviews. This research question investigates how these variables "interrelate or work with one another" (Romero, 2017, p.321) creating unique experiences for each professional and "produc[ing] experiences of both privilege and marginalization" (Smooth, 2013, p.11) in the profession.

From the findings, a dominant profile of ESOL lecturer identity was identified, it being male, white, heterosexual, middle class, British, and a native speaker of English. This specific profile

was identified as the 'standard' in most situations, while any deviations from this profile, were identified as the 'other'. This methodological differentiation regarding the concepts of the 'standard' and the 'other' within an intersectional framework enabled me to identify how different identity characteristics intersect in various ways creating a variety of situations of privilege and disadvantage that serve to maintain the current hegemony in the Scottish ESOL profession, where departments seem to be dominated by ESOL lecturers fitting the 'standard' profile. The way in which these identity characteristics intersect creates a perceived situation of privilege in the profession for individuals whose identity aligns with the 'standard'. However, this does not mean that those individuals may not experience situations of marginalization or disadvantage in other ways in the profession, as every person has a unique experience, and power and privilege are context dependent, as discussed in earlier chapters. According to the intersectionality framework (Crenshaw, 1989), the more an individual deviates from this 'standard', the more layers of marginalisation or discrimination they appear to experience. This idea will be developed when discussing the second research question below. In addition, it is important to highlight that the intersections identified below are a result of the specific context in which this study is situated, and that identity, the perception of identity, and the intersection of the different variables are dynamic rather than static, and they are subject to change depending on contextual, historical, and situational elements (Levon, 2015).

Below I discuss three main intersections that I identified from the discussions in the findings chapters. The effects of these intersections on the profession will be discussed in relation to the second research question.

The intersection of class, ethnicity and migration status, and its impact on 'specialist' qualifications and experience

In chapter 6 I discussed that in order to apply for a position as an ESOL lecturer in Scottish colleges, most institutions require applicants to have a 'specialist' qualification such as the CELTA (*CELTA: Certificate in Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages.*, 2022), and previous experience in the college sector. During the discussion, it was evident that this kind of qualification needs to be privately funded, as there is not public funding available in Scotland for this purpose. Consequently, it is likely that individuals from middle-class backgrounds, who possess the financial means or support to cover the costs of such a qualification, are more likely to obtain the necessary credentials to pursue a career as an ESOL lecturer. This class-based disparity intersects with issues of ethnicity and migration status, as migrants, including refugees and asylum seekers, often face prolonged processes before acquiring work permits in Scotland, as discussed in Chapter 6. As a result, it may be more challenging for them to secure the financial resources required for these specialist qualifications, and therefore, they have potentially fewer opportunities to secure a position in the ESOL college sector.

In Chapter 6, I also explored participants' perceptions of community ESOL classes as spaces designated for the 'other'; that is, a place for those who lack 'specialist' qualifications, have less experience, or do not meet the criteria required to work in the college sector. Related to

this is that some participants viewed the college sector as a more prestigious setting for delivering ESOL instruction. These perceptions, along with the requirement for prior experience in the college sector to be considered for an ESOL lecturer position, intersect with issues of class, ethnicity, and migration status, discussed above. Those working in the community ESOL sector are often less likely to have the qualifications and experience needed to be employed in Further Education institutions, which reinforces existing inequalities and creates a wider gap between the college and the community ESOL spaces, and between the groups of people who teach in these locations, as I will explore in the discussion around the second research question below.

Thus, the findings reveal a clear intersection between class, ethnicity, and migration status, which is reflected in the varying qualifications and experiences held by individuals from different social and ethnic backgrounds. This creates a type of ESOL lecturer who, according to the participants, is 'preferred' in ESOL departments in Scottish colleges and a type who does not fit the preferred profile (the 'other').

The intersection of L1 and ethnicity and its impact on sense of belonging.

The findings of this study indicate an intersection between the lecturers' first language and ethnicity in relation to their sense of belonging to the profession. This intersection is highlighted by Participant 5, who, although she is highly qualified and has experience in ESOL, perceives herself as the 'odd one out' because she does not share a first language and an ethnic background with other members of staff in her department. This contrasts with Participant 3's sense of belonging in the profession, which is reinforced by the fact that he perceives everyone in his department to be very similar to him in terms of identity characteristics.

This particular intersection and the way in which it influences the lecturers' sense of belonging in the department and in the college sector more widely, may influence the way in which individual lecturers negotiate their identity in the classroom, and in the institution, creating tensions or conflict if it causes negative feelings in the lecturer, or enhancing communication and engagement if there is a positive feeling about the lecturer's place in their department (Barkhuizen, 2017; Gray and Morton, 2018; Kennedy, 2020).

The intersection of sexual orientation and perceptions of the students' religious views

The discussion in the findings chapters underscores a significant intersection between lecturers' sexual orientation and staff perceptions of students' religious views. The data suggests that heteronormativity is deeply embedded within the ESOL departments in Scottish colleges, influencing both institutional practices and the lecturers' identity negotiations. Given the diverse cultural and religious backgrounds of ESOL students, there is a prevailing belief among staff that any deviation from heteronormative standards may clash with students' beliefs, and therefore, any situation that could cause conflict in this matter should be largely avoided. Such practices not only shape the environment in the classroom but also impact lecturers' sense of belonging, as evidenced by Participant 2, a gay lecturer who expressed reluctance to disclose his sexual orientation in professional contexts to avoid potential rejection. This reluctance contributes to a broader invisibility of non-heterosexual orientations

within the department, which permeates multiple facets of institutional life, including hiring practices, curriculum content, and the topics discussed in the classroom. The invisibility of non-heteronormative identities and its intersection with the lecturers' perceptions about the students' religious views is also embedded in the language used by the participants, as discussed in chapter 7, where the semantic field of invisibility is evident. Thus, the marginalization of non-heteronormative identities reinforces a culture of silence, where sexual diversity is rendered invisible, and the experiences of LGBTQ+ staff are systematically overlooked, which contributes to the strengthening of the perception of non-heterosexuality as the 'other', existing within a culture of structural inequality.

RQ2: Are ESOL Lecturers in Scotland subject to unequal practices on account of perceptions around their identity (gender, race, sexuality, accent, country of origin etc...)?

The findings indicate that, as mandated by the Equality Act (The UK Government, 2010), like many other British institutions, colleges have implemented anti-discriminatory measures, which are designed to prevent discrimination based on protected identity characteristics. However, the data reveals that despite these policies, certain groups continue to experience unequal treatment within the profession or feel the negative impact of dominant power structures. Individuals within these groups may face subtle or overt forms of exclusion, marginalization, or disadvantage, which highlights the limitations of formal policies in addressing deeper, systemic inequalities. This suggests that, while anti-discriminatory frameworks are in place, they do not always translate into equitable practices or outcomes, particularly for marginalized groups. Applying an intersectionality framework has enabled me to identify and understand the ways in which the perceptions of different identity characteristics shape the profession in a certain way, reinforcing the status quo and limiting diversity among staff in ESOL departments.

The findings of this study reveal that, with respect to ethnicity, ESOL lecturers do not reflect the broader Scottish population, as indicated by Scotland's (2021) most recent, census. The majority of ESOL lecturers in the Scottish college sector appear to be White²⁴ British, with relatively few professionals coming from other ethnic backgrounds. This ethnic disparity widens at higher levels in the profession, such as in curriculum management positions, where White British professionals make up nearly 100% of the workforce (Colleges Scotland, 2021). The root of this imbalance seems to originate in the pre-recruitment process, specifically in the candidate pool for ESOL lecturer positions. The data suggests that the perceived lack of interest from individuals from diverse backgrounds in applying for these roles stems from a sense of exclusion and lack of belonging. This perception is shaped by the underrepresentation of ethnic minorities within ESOL departments, and the internal and external view of colleges as privileged spaces predominantly occupied by individuals from certain ethnic and social backgrounds. As the current system continues to reinforce this perception of 'prestige,' it simultaneously strengthens the sense of alienation for those from marginalized groups, thereby perpetuating the hegemonic profile of lecturers. Thus, while

²⁴ 'White' is capitalised in the census report.

there is apparently no explicit discriminatory practice in place, existing power structures reinforce the status quo, limiting diversity within the profession.

A similar situation is evident in terms of gender roles and representation in positions of greater responsibility. The findings suggest that the ESOL profession within Scottish colleges is predominantly female, which may be attributable to stereotypical gendered perceptions of career roles that permeate British society. However, fewer women appear to hold senior roles, such as curriculum managers. Participants indicated that this imbalance is linked to the ways in which these roles are structured; the responsibilities associated with these positions are often seen as incompatible with caring duties, which are disproportionately performed by women. Additionally, some women reported feeling unsupported in senior roles. Although there was no suggestion of overt discrimination, as, according to the participants, the positions are open to all qualified applicants, the absence of systems that support women's career progression may constitute a form of covert discrimination. This aligns with findings from other studies in further and higher education sectors in Scotland, and should prompt the Scottish Government to implement policies aimed at addressing gender disparities in senior positions, including revisiting promotion criteria to reduce this gap (Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2019).

Regarding the discussion of the first language of ESOL lecturers, there has been progress over the past two decades, influenced by broader trends in the TESOL profession. Most participants seem to recognise the value of linguistic diversity within ESOL departments, appreciating the benefits of having lecturers who speak different first languages, particularly for the students. Despite this, the long-standing issue of 'nativespeakerism' (Holliday, 2018) persists. Participant 5, an ESOL lecturer whose first language is not English, reported feelings of 'otherness' linked to this particular aspect of her identity which impacts her self-perception within the department. This indicates that while efforts have been made to address 'nativespeakerism' in Scottish ESOL departments, this issue is difficult to resolve as it appears to be rooted in structural inequality in the sector.

Social class was another identity factor highlighted by participants, with many describing themselves as working-class or working-class individuals who have transitioned into the middle class. However, as discussed in relation to Research Question 1 above, the 'specialist' qualifications required for ESOL lecturer positions in colleges must be privately funded. This creates barriers for individuals from lower socioeconomic backgrounds, limiting their ability to meet the necessary criteria to apply for these positions. As a result, the perception of the college based ESOL lecturing as a middle-class career is reinforced, a perception identified and discussed by several participants.

Sexual orientation also emerged as a significant identity factor that may be subjected to unequal practices in the profession. Participants described ESOL departments as predominantly heterosexual environments, with most lecturers expressing discomfort discussing LGBTQ+ issues in the classroom. Such an environment seems to affect LGBTQ+ lecturers like Participant 2, who may feel marginalised or 'othered' by both colleagues and students (Nelson, 1993). According to Participant 2, this dynamic can deter potential LGBTQ+ applicants from seeking ESOL positions in the college sector, further contributing to the invisibility of LGBTQ+ staff and complicating their negotiation of identity in both professional

settings and more informal interactions with colleagues. These perceptions permeate the profession in various ways, influencing hiring practices, curriculum content, and limitations around classroom discussions, often in an effort to avoid potential conflicts, thereby perpetuating the dominant discourse and marginalising non-heteronormative identities.

The language used by participants during the interviews, examined in chapter 7, also shows how the hegemonic discourse is evident in the conversations related to identity characteristics such as sexual orientation discussed above, reinforcing the dominant perceptions, and contributing to maintain the hegemonic power structures in the college sector in general, and in ESOL departments in particular.

The various identity characteristics explored in this study, along with the ways in which ESOL practitioners may feel marginalised, or 'othered' within their departments, should not be viewed in isolation. Identity is multifaceted and unique to each individual, and these factors may intersect differently depending on personal experience and context. However, it is noteworthy that participants who identified with the 'standard', that is, the dominant group, struggled to recognise the impact of the lack of diversity in Scottish ESOL education within the college sector. In contrast, those who directly experienced these barriers were more adept at identifying and discussing the unequal practices present within the profession. The exception was Participant 7, a curriculum manager in a large ESOL department, who was able to reflect on how some of her own practices might be perpetuating the status quo and limiting diversity. She was already evaluating ways in which the profession could become more inclusive for individuals from diverse ethnic backgrounds.

RQ3: What are the ESOL lecturers' perceptions regarding the future of ESOL departments in Scottish Colleges in terms of staff diversity?

The participants discussed their views regarding the future of Scottish ESOL departments in colleges in terms of the perceived diversity of staff. The majority of participants believed that there is a general willingness to make ESOL college departments more diverse in terms of representation of different identities, and discussed four different ways that, in their opinion, could help to increase diversity in the future.

Some participants believed that the change toward diversity, that is already starting to be visible, should be driven by the 'other', that is, anyone who does not fit the 'standard' ESOL lecturer profile. Closely related to this was the belief that it will be the "younger ones" (Participant 1) and the "newcomers" (Participant 5) who will introduce change and will carry with them amenable members of staff who have been working in the profession for a longer period of time. This seems to be internalised by Participant 2, who self-identified as 'young' and 'other' in terms of not fitting the heteronormative standard. Participant 2 argued that younger people like himself should be the changemakers. This perception aligns with the work of Freire (2000), who believed that, if the people in power do not collaborate, change must come from those who are at the bottom of the hierarchy, that is, the 'other'.

An alternative, and perhaps opposite, view regarding the future of diversity in ESOL departments was put forward by Participant 7, who seemed to be aware of her position of

relative power, and argued that change must be initiated from the top. In her view, curriculum managers like herself should be considering how they can encourage more diversity in their departments by modifying their hiring criteria, and even supporting positive discrimination to favour those who have been traditionally excluded from the ESOL departments in the college sector.

The third view on this topic was that diversity could be enhanced by compromising the level of qualifications and experience required to work as ESOL lecturers in a college. Participant 1 suggested that teachers who are from diverse backgrounds, and who might be, in his view, weaker in certain aspects of the English language such as grammar could be teaching lower levels and community classes in order to have teachers who are closer to the students' backgrounds in ESOL departments.

The last perspective was that change will happen organically, spurred by the influence of wider social movements such as 'Black Lives Matter' that could also permeate the profession making it a more attractive work environment for the 'other'. This organic change could also be linked to the political situation of Scotland, and the United Kingdom more broadly, so it would be difficult to predict its direction. At the time when this study was being written up, there were some ongoing tensions related to the Scottish independence from the UK (Redfield & Wilton, 2023), as well as a change of the Scottish First Minister; after Nicola Sturgeon's resignation in February 2023 (The Scottish Government, no date), Humza Yousaf was appointed as the new head of the Scottish Government. Although his tenure was brief (Scottish Government, 2023), having reached this level could be seen as promising for diversity in Scotland.

8.4 Limitations

8.4.1. COVID 19

I started my PhD studies in February 2020, a few weeks before the UK Prime Minister at the time, Boris Johnson, announced the first national lockdown on the 23rd of March, which lasted until May of the same year (Timeline of UK government coronavirus lockdown and restrictions, 2022). This meant that people were asked to stay at home, and avoid contact with other households, and universities and other public spaces were closed. After the first lockdown ended there were periods of more relaxed measures, followed by smaller lockdowns that lasted until April 2021, where non-essential retail and other services started to reopen again. However, COVID-19 has a long-term societal impact that goes beyond health, affecting the country's economy, the community and people's mental health among other factors as described in the report published by British Academy (2021). In this context, it is inevitable that some unforeseen limitations have affected this study in different ways. First, for a long period of time it was impossible to access the university buildings, which meant that the study had to be carried out from home, in a shared space and with no physical boundaries between work, and domestic life with the limitations that this has. In addition, meetings with the supervisory team had to be carried out online, lacking the personal, face-to-face value of such meetings. Related to this was the lack of contact with other doctoral students and the

opportunities to exchange ideas in a natural, spontaneous way. Instead, there were pre-planned, online gatherings which by their very nature limited the discussions. However, this unusual situation also forced me to develop my IT skills, explore alternative ways of working, resulting in me discovering more efficient ways of using technological apps to assist with the process of writing this PhD. As a result, I was able to share this knowledge in a workshop about how to use digital skills during a PhD for new students at the university who may encounter similar issues in the future. This opportunity was also a space to network with other PhD students at the university and explore other ways of working.

Another aspect of the PhD that was affected by the restrictions during pandemic was the data collection process as undertaking face-to-face interviews with the participants was not permitted at times and could have put people's health at risk. Instead, I had to communicate with the participants using online alternatives such as email, or social media, and arrange online interviews by Zoom (Zoom, 2023), a video-conferencing platform. This was a popular option in qualitative studies during this period of time and despite some limitations such as the rapport and the restricted interaction between the participants and the researcher that is caused by this unnatural way of communication, there were also some advantages to this interviewing method. For example, the participant was able to choose the location from which they wanted to answer the questions, making them feel more at ease and comfortable. In addition, the recording was of better quality as it is directly recorded in the computer, and this facilitated the transcription for the thematic analysis (Keen, Lomeli-Rodriguez and Joffe, 2022).

The lack of face to-face contact has also impacted the opportunities to present the study in conferences as there has only been one opportunity to present in front of a 'real' audience. I was delighted that my proposal was accepted to present at IATEFL, an international English Language conference, where I have had the opportunity to meet people whom I had only met previously online, as well as to expand my network meeting new academics and professionals. The conference had a huge focus on diversity and inclusion in English Language teaching, which offered me the opportunity to attend seminars and talks related to making the profession more inclusive in terms of for example, materials, assessments, disabilities, and queer issues. This has helped me question different aspects in which I could apply this to my practice as a lecturer but also to the current study.

In addition, the lack of opportunities to attend face-to-face events due to the restrictions caused by the pandemic meant that there were more opportunities to attend online conferences and present at online events in places that otherwise would not have been possible. For example, I was able to attend and present twice at a postgraduate event at another British university and explore the current trends in education that were being explored by other PhD students across the country.

In addition, as a full-time self-funded PhD student, combining working and studying in a period of global pandemic and economic crisis has inevitably impacted my original plans and

deadlines. The COVID-19 pandemic, the constant changes and the uncertainty caused by it have also impacted people's mental health in aspects such as anxiety and loneliness, and this has also been an important factor in relation to this study.

8.4.2 Recruitment of participants

As explained in the methodology chapter, there were some limitations in gaining consent from the colleges' principal to contact participants through the college. Therefore, I had to adapt the methodology, publishing an open call on social media (Twitter & LinkedIn) asking individuals who were working as ESOL lecturers in Scottish colleges to contact me if they were interested in participating in this research. This was challenging as these calls could only reach ESOL lecturers who are active on social media and within my network. In addition, the interviews were conducted during the months of March-June 2021, which coincide with the last term of the academic year in the college, which is usually a busy period as students will be preparing for exams and end-of-year assessments; but it was particularly challenging in 2021 because classes started to move from online to face-to-face delivery. In addition, there was ongoing industrial action in the college sector that affected ESOL lecturers (Educational Institute of Scotland, 2021). All these factors impacted the availability of potential participants for the study, and the final number of participants is lower than originally expected. However, the data obtained from the interviews was rich as participants offered reflections on significant elements in their interviews which were very valuable for the study. In addition, the data was explored from two different perspectives (thematically and discursively) in order to have a broader understanding of the issues explored in this study.

8.4.3 The approach to the study

The intention of this study was to bring intersectionality to the fore as a framework to address any perceived unequal practices in ESOL college departments in relation to the lecturers' identity characteristics. At the time of designing the study, I considered that the sample should include ESOL lecturers from different backgrounds in order to incorporate as many perspectives and experiences as possible. In order to achieve this, I did not plan to involve as participants lecturers with specific identity characteristics, as I thought that by doing this, I would be closing opportunities for other lecturers to share what could be insightful perspectives. In addition, I was mindful of the potentially sensitive topic of the study, and of the particular time in which the data collection was conducted (i.e. during a global pandemic). Therefore, inviting anyone working as an ESOL lecturer in a Scottish college to participate in the study was the best option for me at the time. However, in the end, this resulted in a sample that includes participants with very similar identity characteristics (white, British, heterosexual and middle-class), and only two participants who have slightly different characteristics. Although the data that they provided is rich and varied, I believe that if I had targeted a more specific group of lecturers, I could have interviewed a more diverse group of participants.

8.4.4 Time and length of the study

This study has been conducted as part of a doctoral degree, which implies that it is constrained by the university's requirements and regulations for this kind of degrees and should comply with the time and word limits that are set in this document in order to obtain the final degree. According to the university, the study should be completed within 36 months which implies that I had to follow certain deadlines for each stage of the study in order to be able to finalise the study within the time provided. In addition, the final thesis should not exceed 80,000 words, excluding ancillary data, which dictates the depth of the topics covered and the detail of the analysis.

For these reasons, this chapter provides recommendations for further research in areas that are outwith of the scope of this study and that if had been covered, the thesis would have exceeded the time and word limit constraints.

8.5 Lessons learnt from the research experience

In this section I will reflect on the aspects of this research that have taught me how to do things 'the right way' and 'how not to do things at all' in relation to the thesis in order to get an overall picture of the strengths and weaknesses of this project, and to help in future research.

8.5.1 Planning and organisation

Firstly, becoming immersed in the literature as early as I possibly could, and making sure I took notes of every piece of reading was certainly a good starting point to the research. This allowed me to start writing and reflecting on the reading from very early stages. In addition, I am grateful to have used NVivo to develop the literature chapter as this was an opportunity to become familiar with the programme, before a more complex project such as the thematic analysis.

Another positive aspect of planning and organisation was having a timeline of the whole project from the beginning and reviewing and amend it as necessary in accordance with the progress of the study and personal circumstances. This allowed me set small 'deadlines' and have a sense of development in a long project, allowing me to reflect on each chapter.

However, it was not all positive in terms of organisation as, in hindsight, planning a different approach for the recruitment of participants would have been advantageous and, perhaps, it would have resulted in a larger number of participants. Organising the timeline of this project in accordance with the academic year in the college would have allowed me to undertake the

interviews at a different time, where ESOL lecturers were not as busy as they were during March-June 2021. In addition, being both a full-time student and working in the Higher and Further Education sectors with variable working hours each month was a challenge as it necessitated modifying my working routines and schedules to accommodate all the different demands.

8.5.2 The role of social media

In this time and age social media plays a huge role in society and can be used for many different purposes. During my PhD research, I decided to start using social media platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter as professional tools to develop my PhD and my career as they are designed to create connections among people who share common interests. These tools have played an essential role in developing a sense of community and enhancing my PhD experience during the COVID-19 pandemic across different fields (Le Busque and Mingoia, 2021) and personally, they have enabled me not only to connect with scholars across the globe who are interested in similar topics, but also to discover current literature, and trends in the profession. In addition, through Twitter and LinkedIn I was able to sign up to different webinars and online conferences throughout the years that otherwise I would not have known about. They have also played an essential role in the recruitment of participants for the study. All in all, social media has positively influenced this study and my career, and I would recommend anyone starting postgraduate degrees to make use of these powerful tools to grow an online community as soon as possible.

8.6 Autobiographical reflection

In February 2020, when I started this project, I was not aware of the challenges and opportunities that I was going to encounter during the 4 years it has taken me to complete this thesis. For someone like me, who does not particularly like uncertainty, the learning process has been steep. The first unforeseen event appeared just a few weeks after I enrolled to this degree: a global pandemic started, and I had to learn to adapt my working routines, my tools, and my ways of communicating with people (supervisors, participants and other academics). While this was challenging, particularly at first, ultimately, it has made me a more resilient person. Then, my position throughout this study shifted in different ways as my professional roles in English language and Scottish education changed. At the beginning, I approached the study as someone who had experience in private language education, and who taught ESOL in community setting in Scotland. Therefore, I began to navigate the issues around the Further Education context in which my study is situated as someone who was not directly involved in the field.

A few months after the start of this study, I started my career in Higher Education in the same institution where I was studying for the PhD, and where I had previously completed my masters' degree. This required me to negotiate my identity as a student, and as a lecturer in a

HE institution. I was aware that my colleagues' perceptions of my own identity could be influenced by the context: on some occasions I could be perceived as a colleague, while on others I was a PhD student. Thus, by conducting this study and being aware of how language teacher identity negotiations could shape interactions, I was able to experience first-hand some of the theories discussed by scholars such as Barkhuizen (2021).

At the time of meeting the participants of this study, I was not involved in ESOL education, and therefore, I approached the interactions with the participants as a researcher, rather than as a colleague or someone who was involved in a similar context. However, after completing the data collection for this study I started working as an ESOL lecturer in the Scottish college sector. This new role placed me directly inside the context of my research and coincided with the time I was starting to analyse and interpret the data of my study. This new location enabled me to have a new perspective from which to understand the data, and to connect with the participants of my study on a deeper level. Some of the experiences they shared resonated with my own which, as I discuss in section 8.7.3 of this chapter, also helped me to understand the framework and the power relations that are embedded in the Further Education system beyond the theory examined for this research. In addition, this continual shift in positions, from researcher to student, to lecturer, and to colleague, enabled me to reflect on the way I performed my identity, and the way I was perceived by others. Negotiating these changes in 'roles' or as Kennedy (2020) refers to them, I-positions, has not been easy, however it has given me many opportunities to explore my own identity in full, in all these different versions of myself, and as a consequence, I am more aware of the identities of those around me: colleagues, students, or research participants.

8.7 Implications

Above all, this study highlighted the need to analyse and understand the identity of ESOL educators in order to identify potential practices that, sustain structural inequality and may, ultimately, damage individuals working in the profession. Firstly, the study has explored the identity of a range of ESOL lecturers in the college sector aiming to understand the unspoken power dynamics related to identity in the departments and the profession as a whole. This has helped to identify the mainstream or 'standard' profile of ESOL practitioners, which is white, British, native-speaker and heterosexual. The study has shown that there are potential challenges associated with the feeling of 'otherness' and sense of exclusion that are likely to prevent people who do not fit the 'standard' profile from entering the profession. Acknowledging this dominant profile could play a huge part in opening the conversation in ESOL departments and encouraging reflection on whether different members of staff feel welcome or unwelcome in their own departments and what measures can be taken to reduce structural inequity.

In addition, it has become clear that the dominant profile of ESOL lecturers has shaped the profession and its hiring practices, reinforcing these practices and erecting barriers to diversity in recruitment in ESOL departments. Inevitably, this creates a mismatch between the

lecturers' identity and those of the learners, resulting in lack of role models available for students to connect to in terms of identity, background and experiences.

8.7.1 Theoretical and methodological implications

This study has significant theoretical and methodological implications, particularly for the area of intersectionality and related discussions around power and privilege, LTI in the Scottish college sector and critical reflexivity in practice. The thesis highlights the complex ways in which different areas of identity such as race, gender, class, first language, religion and sexual orientation may intersect to shape the experiences of ESOL lecturers in the Scottish college sector, creating situations of privilege or disadvantage. The findings of this study contribute to the growing body of literature that recognizes the importance of considering multiple identity factors simultaneously in order to identify and address inequalities in a specific context. Through the application of an intersectional framework in this study, the research shows how institutional power structures, such as recruitment and promotion practices, perpetuate inequalities by favouring those who align with the 'standard' of being white, middle class, British and heterosexual, while marginalising and excluding others. This reinforces the idea that intersectionality must be considered not only at the individual level to examine how it affects individual lecturers, but also at the structural level when assessing access, opportunities, and representation in educational institutions such as the colleges. From a methodological perspective, the data of this study was analysed from two different perspectives, which helped to enhance the discussion in relation to power. The thematic analyses helped to understand the main themes from the interviews, and how they linked to previous discussions of power, while the critical discourse analysis served to identify how language constructs, reflects and challenges discourses within the ESOL profession. All in all, the study demonstrates that institutional practices, policies and processes such as hiring and promotion play a crucial role in reinforcing existing power hierarchies. It highlights how seemingly neutral or 'fair' policies can, in fact, perpetuate exclusion and inequality by failing to address systemic barriers to equality and justice.

In addition, this study also contributes to the literature around LTI, as it explores lecturers' identity in a context that was not previously explored. The study highlights the importance of considering LTI and how it affects the dynamics within departments at an individual and collective level. It also shows how teachers' identities are shaped by both their personal characteristics and the external perceptions of their students and colleagues. It contributes to developing theories of LTI by emphasizing how social exclusion, or lack of belonging, can directly impact a teacher's self-perception.

It is also worth highlighting that this study demonstrates the value of critical reflexivity from the researcher and from the participants. From my perspective, critical reflection was employed throughout the process of this study to analyse the data, interact with the participants and understand my own biases and how they affected my interpretation of the findings of this study, at different stages of the process. This is particularly important when studying issues of intersectionality and power, where researchers' biases can shape the framing and understanding of participants' experiences. Additionally, critical reflexivity was also employed by the participants as they were asked to discuss issues of identity and power

in their own context. This has served as evidence of the value of studies of this kind that encourage participants to reflect on matters that they may have previously never considered, as was highlighted on many occasions during the interviews.

8.7.2 Implications for practice in the Scottish FE context

This research has important implications for practice within the Scottish ESOL college sector, particularly regarding targeted training and continuous professional development (CPD), fostering diversity, and reevaluating hiring practices. In terms of training, the findings suggest that some lecturers might not feel equipped to address issues of diversity, for example in relation to sexual orientation. This shows that there is an ongoing need for targeted training and CPD in Scottish ESOL departments in this regard. In addition, training should include guided reflection on how individuals support or hinder diversity in their own context. This should help to enhance lecturers' ability to recognise and address unconscious biases, adopt inclusive pedagogical strategies, and navigate complex identity intersections such as ethnicity, gender, and sexual orientation. In addition, this study highlights the need for open, ongoing conversations about diversity within the college sector, particularly in the field of ESOL. From the findings it seems evident that currently, any changes are being implemented mainly by the 'other'; by opening up the conversation and offering opportunities for reflection, everyone involved in the profession could also become agents of change. This could involve facilitated workshops, reflective group discussions, or diversity task forces that encourage all staff to critically examine their roles in perpetuating or challenging exclusionary practices.

The study also suggests that while policies such as the Equality Act aim to create fair and inclusive hiring practices, blind hiring approaches may not fully address the complexities of systemic inequality. For instance, these practices often overlook structural barriers that make it difficult for individuals from underrepresented groups to even apply, such as the socio-economic challenges of obtaining the 'specialist' qualifications that appear to be essential for ESOL positions. Reevaluating these hiring practices may involve adopting more holistic recruitment strategies that consider lived experiences, alternative qualifications, and ways to support diverse candidates. This could also include expanding recruitment outreach to communities less represented in the current workforce and reassessing job criteria that might exclude qualified individuals from marginalized backgrounds. In conclusion, the practical implications of this research point to a need for continuous, context-sensitive training, the fostering of open, inclusive conversations about diversity, and the re-evaluation of hiring practices to address deeper systemic barriers. Together, these measures would contribute to a more equitable and representative ESOL workforce in Scottish colleges.

8.7.3 Personal implications

This study has also had personal implications for me as a researcher, as a former ESOL practitioner and as a professional who is currently involved in English language education in Scotland. These implications are multifaceted and focus particularly on power dynamics, social inequalities, and intersectionality within the context of ESOL education in Scotland.

Firstly, the study has increased my awareness of structural inequalities present at institutional and departmental level. Conducting this research deepened my understanding of how issues related to the perceptions of class, gender, ethnicity, sexual orientation, and migration status and their intersections facilitate or prevent access to employment opportunities in Scottish

Further Education institutions, and particularly in ESOL departments. Due to my own background, I experienced some of the issues discussed by the participants, but a deeper exploration of these issues has provided me with a wider understanding of power structures and mechanisms that support hegemonic structures in the sector.

In addition, the study enabled me to reflect on my own positionality as a researcher and as a former ESOL lecturer, and to consider how I have been affected by power structures, which have placed me in a position of either privilege or disadvantage depending on particular situations. For example, as a former ESOL lecturer I resonated with the experiences of Participant 2, who, being a younger member of staff, viewed himself as a driver of change. I have also experienced first-hand the ways in which curriculum managers, like Participant 7, are seeking ways to make the profession a more inclusive place. As a researcher who has experience in the sector, I could be considered to be in a privileged position as I was closer to the participants' context, and this enabled me to understand their discussions from an 'insider' perspective. At the same time, not being directly involved in ESOL currently gave me the opportunity to be more critical, as I was aware that I could not be negatively impacted by any perceived connection to it.

An additional personal implication of this study is that it has developed my sense of empathy and social justice advocacy. By understanding the 'barriers' to diversity faced by minority groups in the profession, I was inspired to start conversations in my own professional context, and challenge traditional ideas that support the status quo.

This study also has implications for my own professional practice as a lecturer. I have gained insights into the factors that might influence LTI negotiation, and the effects that this might have for professionals and for the students. As a result, I now include a deeper level of self-reflection in my practice in relation to my own identity negotiation and its potential impact on colleagues and students as I aim to foster a more inclusive and sensitive approach to different identities and experiences in the sector.

8.8 Future research and recommendations.

This study is a unique and original piece of research as it explores, from an intersectional framework, the identity of ESOL lecturers in the college sector in Scotland. As discussed in previous chapters of this study, the framework of intersectionality is relatively new in being used as a lens through which to explore the ELT industry, and particularly ESOL. Therefore, future research could focus on exploring different aspects of ESOL education in Scotland and beyond, from an intersectional lens. For example, it could examine classroom materials, the implementation of ESOL in Scotland and the background of ESOL students to gather evidence that can be used to inform guidelines and measures that support and encourage greater diversity in the departments. Further research on these aspects of Scottish ESOL education may help and encourage curriculum managers and human resources departments to reflect on and revise their recruitment criteria in order to attract people from more diverse backgrounds that can benefit the department and the students, and make ESOL a more welcoming profession.

In terms of the position of women in relation to power, this study has identified that although there are some women in senior roles in ESOL, such as curriculum managers and, what were previously known as senior lecturers, some do not feel comfortable in these positions, and some may prefer to work as ESOL lecturers in non-managerial positions (Participant 8). The study also explored the apparent lack of interest from women to apply for these kinds of positions. Such underrepresentation of women in positions of responsibility in the ELT field has been acknowledged by other scholars in different contexts and has also been noted by the Scottish Government (Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2019). The practices suggested by the Scottish Government as solutions to enhance gender parity in higher positions in the field of education could also be implemented in ESOL departments in the Scottish colleges. Such practices include the review of promotion criteria, targeted mentoring, women-only development events, as well as “consider[ing] the recommendations contained with the Universities and Colleges Employers Association” (Scottish Government and APS Group Scotland, 2019 p.127) to address and report the intersectional gender and ethnic gaps in higher and Further Education.

In terms of ensuring the FE ESOL sector becomes more LGBTQ+ friendly and more effective in tackling the perceived heteronormativity present in some departments, it would be advisable for Scottish colleges to provide more information to potential applicants regarding Equal Opportunity policies and how the information is handled to reduce the fear of rejection that some queer people feel when considering applying for these type of positions, as explained by Participant 2

In addition, in the first findings chapter, the study highlighted that there seems to be certain “uniformity” (Participant 5) in terms of the identity of ESOL staff in the colleges, as they seem to be predominantly white, heterosexual, middle aged, middle class and ‘native’ speakers. Participants compared the diversity in ESOL departments with other departments in the college highlighting the lack of diversity across the FE sector (Participant 5). Currently, the annual report from Colleges Scotland (2021) gives data on some aspects of identity of people working in Further Education in Scotland, such as, for example, their age and gender. While this information is interesting to show an overview of the FE sector, it does not show data on specific departments. For this reason, it would be interesting to explore and compare this data with data from similar studies in other fields, taking into account intersectionality in specific departments in order to identify any potential discriminatory practices, or barriers that may stop people from certain backgrounds working as FE lecturers across different fields in the college. In addition, following recommendations from other scholars in the field of LTI (Kennedy, 2020; Barkhuizen, 2021; Banegas, Beltrán-Palanques and Salas, 2023), it is advisable for language teacher education programmes to include an element on LTI. LTI should also be included as part of CPD at all stages of a teacher’s career. Lastly, it would be advisable for other scholars in the field to undertake a similar study on intersectionality in ESOL departments in Scotland and re-evaluate the situation in a decade or two in order to identify any changes and reflect on the effectiveness of any new measures introduced.

8.9 Conclusion

The aim of this last chapter was to encapsulate the main ideas of the study, and to offer a personal reflection on the process of completing this PhD, and on my own personal growth as a researcher, as an ESOL practitioner, as an academic and, above all, as a person. The framework of intersectionality is now the lens through which I see every aspect of my life, personal and professional, and it has changed my perception of my reality, helping me to acknowledge my own privileges as a white, European woman, and the implications that my identity may have for my own students and colleagues.

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Appendix 1 – Participant’s information sheet

Participant Information Sheet

Research Title: Intersectional discrimination in ESOL professionals and its impact on the profession: an exploration of the Scottish college context²⁵.

Invitation paragraph

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide it is important for you to understand why the research is being carried out and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and contact me if there is any further information you require. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to participate.

What is the purpose of the study?

The study aims to explore the unique identities of ESOL practitioners that are currently working within the Scottish ESOL context and to examine possible discriminatory practices that may occur within this context.

What will I have to do?

You will take part in an interview which will take between 45 and 60 minutes. You will be asked to talk about your role, and your experience and to reflect on aspects of identity and discrimination.

Why are you asking me?

The study focuses on the perspectives of ESOL practitioners working in Further Education institutions in Scotland. You are being asked to participate as you meet the criteria of participants needed for this study.

Do I have to take part?

No. Participating in this project is voluntary. If you decide after taking part in the interview/questionnaire that you would like to withdraw from the study, you can do so by emailing the researcher [REDACTED] and any data that you have given will be withdrawn.

Will my data be kept confidential?

Every individual is entitled to privacy and confidentiality. Information obtained from and about a participant should remain confidential unless otherwise agreed in advance. In reporting data therefore, individual participants should not be personally identifiable except under exceptional circumstances and with clear informed consent. Therefore,

²⁵ This was the working title of the study at the time of the data collection.

your name will not be used in the dissertation, nor in any other publications arising from the research. Your name will be replaced by a pseudonym and any detail that may put your privacy at risk will be omitted (e.g: the institution you work for). Electronic files and documents will be password protected and paper documents will be securely stored. The access, control and dissemination of data are also protected under the Data Protection Act¹³.

What will happen to the information I provide?

Your data and that from the other participants will be analysed using specialised software, in order to identify common themes. Those findings will be included in my PhD thesis.

On request, you will have full access to the final thesis and a summary of the data collected will be provided.

Who should I contact for more information?

If you have any more questions or would like additional information about the research, you can contact me by email on [b\[REDACTED\]](mailto:b[REDACTED])

What if I have a complaint about the research?

If you have a complaint about the research, please contact Margaret.allan@uws.ac.uk

Thank you for taking the time to read this information and I hope that you will be interested in taking part in the research.

Yours sincerely,

Paula Alcaraz Barrowcliffe.

I have read and understood the information in this document:
Participant's signature.

Appendix 2 – Interview schedule

Introductory Statement for Face-to-Face:

We are now recording. Thank you again for agreeing to participate in this individual interview. Please remember that anything you say will be made anonymous in the transcription process and that you are free to stop participating at any time, and without giving explanation. You can also decline to answer questions. There is no penalty for declining to participate. I've given you a Participation Information and this contains information about who to contact if you have any concerns or comments about today's interview.

Engagement

#	Questions:
1.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What's your current role in the college and how long have you been in this position?
2.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Can you tell me a little bit more about your background in ESOL education?
3.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How would you describe yourself in terms of identity? (e.g.: aspects of ethnicity, first language, gender and sexuality....)

Exploration

#	Questions:
4.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you think identity is considered either positively or negatively within practices in the profession? You can talk about your own experience or your perceptions of others.
5.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To your knowledge, does identity play a part in hiring practices of ESOL practitioners within the ESOL college context in Scotland? - <u>if yes</u>: in what way? -<u>if not</u>: what other aspects do you think are considered important in hiring practices?
6.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you perceive diversity within the Scottish ESOL college context? Do you think the teaching body is diverse?
7.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you think having a diverse teaching body in ESOL departments is important? Why?
8.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Do you think the diversity or lack of diversity in the teaching body affects the students learning development? Why?
9.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To your knowledge, is diversity within the teaching staff an important aspect for ESOL learners in the college?

	<p>-<u>if yes</u>: in, what ways do you think it is important for them?</p> <p>-<u>if not</u>: what things do you think the ESOL learners value about their teachers?</p>
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Exit

#	Question
10.	Do you think that people working in ESOL in colleges in Scotland value diversity within the teaching staff? Why?
11.	In your opinion, how do you think the profession will develop in terms of diversity within the teaching staff?

Appendix 3 – Letter to participants

May 2021

Participation in PhD study.

Dear Sir / Madam,

My name is Paula Alcaraz Barrowcliffe, and I am a PhD candidate at the University of the West of Scotland. I am currently at the stage of starting to collect data for my PhD study. My research is on the topic of discriminatory practices within the context of ESOL education in the Scottish college context and I would like to gain some insight of the current situation of ESOL professionals working within this context. In addition, I would like to better understand the views and perceptions of the ESOL practitioners in order to compare it with existing literature of the topic. Research which examines the perceptions of ESOL professionals working in Scottish colleges is important in order to understand diversity and contribute to the limited research in this context.

I am writing to ask if you would be willing to participate in my research.

The next page (please see attached) has more information about my PhD research study. It also outlines what I would be asking you to do as part of my study. I will contact you again in about a week to confirm if you would like to take part.

Many thanks for considering my request.

Best Regards,

Paula Alcaraz Barrowcliffe.

A handwritten signature in blue ink that reads "P.A. Barrowcliffe". The signature is written in a cursive style with a horizontal line underneath.

Appendix 4 - Permission Letter (Head of College)

This letter was sent to the Head of a Scottish college to grant consent to locate the research in a particular college. As permission was denied, participants had to be recruited independently using the methods explained in the methodology chapter.

March 2021

Participation in PhD study.

Dear Sir / Madam,

My name is Paula Alcaraz Barrowcliffe, and I am a PhD candidate at the University of the West of Scotland. I am currently at the stage of starting to collect data for my PhD study. My research is on the topic of discriminatory practices within the context of ESOL education in the Scottish college context and I would like to gain some insight of the current situation of ESOL professionals working within this context. In addition, I would like to better understand the views and perceptions of the ESOL practitioners in order to compare it with existing literature of the topic. Research which examines the perceptions of ESOL professionals working in Scottish colleges is important in order to understand diversity and contribute to the limited research in this context.

I am writing to ask for permission to locate my research within your college.

If permission is granted, I would like to interview 10 volunteer participants working in the ESOL department. The interviews will be around 45-60 minutes long, and participants will be asked to answer questions regarding their role and experience and to reflect on aspects of identity and discrimination.

Many thanks for considering my request.

Best Regards,

Paula Alcaraz Barrowcliffe.

Appendix 5 – Table of initial codes for Thematic Analysis.

This table shows the initial codes used for the thematic analysis, prior to NVivo. The final codes used in NVivo were lost after the analysis due technical failure and therefore, cannot be included.

<i>Participant</i>	<i>Theme</i>	<i>Sub-theme</i>	<i>Selected Quote</i>
P2	Diversity	Department's diversity	I think when you look at it, some departments are all very much similar, in their kind of identities. And when you- when you look across a broad spectrum, you don't see very much change, and you don't see diversity and working on it for a while now, it's been very static.
P2	Diversity	Department's diversity	We have a very small department. There's three of us. R= Okay, great. And it's no div... - P2 = No, so they are both women over the age of 45
P2	Diversity	Department's diversity	The total impact is until that person leaves that post there will be no diversity.
P2	Feeling of (non) belonging	Inclusion	I think they've accepted me, and they've welcomed me very well. And they've been....I think they've found it refreshing to have a new pair of eyes, overlook saying- not overlook things, but like, when it comes to, say, cross marking, or it comes to ehm... kind of peer... to peer observing. I think they kind of see something maybe that they haven't done before, or they maybe can adapt new teaching methods. So, I think it's quite good for them maybe to see what our younger audience is got to bring
P2	Future of the profession	Move to diversity	we need to break through as young professionals to make that change. And we need, We'll need to start getting into further education and more. And I know there's not jobs out there. And I know this does kind of struggle. But unless we start making the change then the change won't happen. Because the people who are in positions of power are years ahead of us. So that still going to be 15-20 years where there might be no impact.

P2	Hiring practices		I think the application process can sometimes be a barrier, because if you're having to tick, that you're a native speaker, if you're having to tick before that you're a gay man, or you're part of the LGBT community, I think that sometimes that is your first barrier, because maybe there's thought that their learners wouldn't want to be taught by someone like that. Or they want to be taught by a certain type of person. And that almost is filtering out their kind of people that they don't want to identify with and their departments.
P2	Hiring practices	Reluctance to change	I think, when you've got someone maybe who's in charge department, and has been there for a very long time, there are reluctant in order to have that change, and I think there's a worry about passing on and what the learners may react from it.
P2	Hiring practices	Important aspects	What aspects are important? I think - it's got to be based on the qualifications and experience of the person. I don't think - Identity is important, but that shouldn't be taken into account when applying for a job. I think, if you have people there, and they're the right person for the job, that should whatever based on they shouldn't be based on whether someone's a native speaker or not, it should be based on how good is that person for the profession? Do they have the experience? And I think ultimately, do they have the right connection to be with a learner?
P2	Lecturer's experience in ESOL		So before I went to the college, I was working for a local authority as an adult education tutor, delivering adult based education. And the service was then.... - everyone was let go in the service, and we're basically had to find new jobs. So, the option was to retrain or lose my job. So I then moved over to ESOL and focused on community based ESOL provision. R = 1:55 Okay, so you started working in ESOL in your other job? P2 = 1:59

			Yeah, yeah. As a as a community tutor, I was working in ESOL there for about a year and a half to two years.
<i>P2</i>	Diversity in the profession	Lack of diversity (uniformity)	R - So how do you perceive diversity within the Scottish ESOL college context? And do you think the teaching body is diverse? P2 = 8:45 No, no, not at all. That is a simple answer. I think even in terms of age, there's not a great kind of balance. Everyone that I know at the moment is probably above 40. I'm probably the youngest by far.
<i>P2</i>	Diversity in the profession	Lack of diversity (uniformity)	we're not a diverse profession yet. And I think that's... - that speaks for itself, although there may not - people may not be speaking out about it. I think the fact that diversity hasn't taken place, we don't have a balance of professionals so it pretty much answers for itself.
<i>P2</i>	Diversity in the profession	Lack of diversity (uniformity)	I think when you look at it, some departments are all very much similar, in their kind of identities. And when you- when you look across a broad spectrum, you don't see very much change, and you don't see diversity and working on it for a while now, it's been very static.
<i>P2</i>	Diversity in the profession	Lack of diversity (uniformity)	I think even in terms of age, there's not a great kind of balance. Everyone that I know at the moment is probably above 40. I'm probably the youngest by far.
<i>P2</i>	Diversity in the profession	Impact of diversity on the profession	if we don't bring different personalities, if we don't bring different identities, then we're not really doing the learners any service is by helping them integrate and if..and if we're the first point of contact with them. And we are- and we are kind of disengaging our equality and diversity in the profession, then it just carries on through and through. So that learner might be might never kind of be willing to change.
<i>P5</i>	Diversity in the profession	Lack of diversity (uniformity)	there's a uniformity. That is, you know, that is not good in terms of meeting meeting needs, you know,

			because you need you need to have, your teaching team has to be as diverse as maybe the people you teach.
P5	Department's diversity	Lack of diversity (uniformity)	So I would say, white, middle aged, middle class, and you do have a lot of women, but you also have quite a lot of men. And therefore, it's not as diverse as you know, and if I think of other departments where you've got more, you've got more diverse and more diverse base, you know? R 19:14 When you mean other departments, you mean of other disciplines? Yeah. P5 19:17 Yes, yes. Yeah.
P5	Diversity	Discussion of diversity in the classroom	I've experienced discrimination. We know what it's like, we know how it feels. And we can relate to our students, and we can discuss the topics and ways to deal you know, with some, some issues.
P5	Feeling of (non) belonging	Otherness	When I arrived in France as a refugee, I was the Other, but when I arrived in Scotland, I was a French woman, a typically French women, which would surprise people in France. Now I'm a bit, I'm not quite sure because I've lived in Scotland for 27 years. I'm married to a scott. So obviously my life is very different from my life would have been if I had married, you know, somebody from from somewhere else. English is not my first language, so, I had to learn English from scratch, but I was lucky because I learned English, in France at school, and then secondary school and university. So that makes a huge difference. What else can I say? So I think I've got.... the way I see my identity and the way other people see my identity, because they, they stereotype me as soon as, you know, in France, it was as soon as they heard my name, they stereotype the stereotype me. And now and in the UK, the stereotype me as well. But for, they don't know where my name comes from. So, they don't see, but it's more like my appearance and my

			accent. And my gender, also, I suppose. So, it's a bit difficult to say, you know, who I am. So I think I'm, I'm so fitting seat, but that that doesn't mean a lot.
<i>P5</i>	Feeling of (non) belonging	Otherness	I haven't been working in colleges for long enough, but obviously, it's not my culture. And I don't feel comfortable, I can say that, you know, I don't feel comfortable in a college environment, I will I much prefer teaching in community-based organisations, you know, the voluntary sector, and also council services. And I think that, in terms of identity, people are put in boxes.
<i>P5</i>	Feeling of (non) belonging	Otherness	I feel a bit like the, you know, the odd one out, because I... my ESOL career, I've done it in, in the UK, whereas all the other people they've the, you know, they taught in China, in Turkey and Latin America, you know, in the Middle East, and therefore, the it's, it's not what I would call ESOL,, you know, it's more like EFL. And therefore, you've got a completely different world, you know, the world of EFL, and the world of ESOL, and these are not the same, you know, not the same audience, not the same goals, not the, you know, not the same environment at all.
<i>P5</i>	Feeling of (non) belonging	Otherness	I feel like the odd one out because I'm not a native speaker, although in my team, we've got several people who are not native speakers, but you only have two people from East and West Africa. I'm from North Africa, but that's a bit different. And so it's like okay, so you I would say they are old middle aged, middle class with a teaching qualification like meaning like secondary teaching. So very different from my background. And, and there's a uniformity. That is, you know, that is not good in terms of meeting needs, you know, because you need you need to have, your teaching team has to be as diverse as maybe the people you teach.

P5	Feeling of (non) belonging	Otherness	I think that people like me are more likely to teach in community education than in college. I think as well that maybe it's a historical, maybe the, you know, a lot of my colleagues have been teaching ESOL for 20 - 25 years, you know, so obviously, it's, you know, historically they've been there for ages
P5	Feeling of (non) belonging	Otherness	for example, for me, not having people who look like me all the time is difficult. And I don't mean exactly the same background as me. But I'm from a mixed background. I've lived in different countries, and in my family, people speak different languages, and finding myself with colleagues who they don't speak any other language, they're white middle class, middle aged, and say, Well, apart from the middle age, you know well, we don't really have a lot in common. I can bring things like for example, what I discussed with my colleagues, they were when I arrived in Glasgow, I couldn't say the name of the streets, the name of the neighbourhoods, the name of the other cities in Scotland, the name of people, I couldn't pronounce first names or surnames, and it's something you need to teach. It's not something that you can learn fast. If you can't say the name of your doctor, and you've got an appointment, it's the first thing they ask you at reception. Therefore people need to be able to say things like that. Well, if you haven't been in my situation, you will not think about that.
P5	Future of the profession	Move to diversity	I think of all the newcomers people who have come from a diverse background, much more diverse than then, you know, the people who are well established. So it is possible, it is possible that the staff will be more diverse. I'm just thinking as well as will they be allowed to stay diverse? Will..and what I mean different. By that, I mean, different. Or will they have to fit in the mould, you know? R 33:28 Okay. So once they enter the department, they may need to just change completely who they are. Is that

			<p>what you mean? Yes. Okay. And why do you think that?</p> <p>P5 33:41 you have to fit in, you have to fit in.</p>
P5	Learner's identity	Not meeting needs.	<p>it's very difficult to see people as a whole, rather than just as a learner. And when I was teaching, like, even with for another college, when I was teaching community classes, I could see the same students who were in class in college. And then see them in a community class, which was a family learning class. So, they were we were working on ESOL and storytelling and being completely different. Because in college, it was so reductive, you know, the way they were seen your just a student, you don't know English, you're a woman, you wear a headscarf, or, you know, you come from Eritrea, and you've never had proper, I don't know, schooling or..... whereas when we were in, in the primary school with the children and we were doing.... we were still doing the same kind of activities, but in a different context and we were doing them differently. You could see people as whole or a whole person, rather than just as a learner. Okay. And for me, that was quite striking.</p>
P5	Lerner's identity	Not meeting needs.	<p>the fact that we cannot see students as a whole person, but just as somebody who comes to learn a language means that we don't match their needs. We don't they have perceived needs, and their perceived needs are different from what we think are their perceived needs. We never, you know, we're supposed to carry out surveys for the college in a language that is completely obscure for other students. Okay. About how the, you know, the student experience? Well, we we have to spend like three hours to explain the survey to an elementary student, and therefore, we will do</p>
P5	Diversity	Willingness to be diverse	<p>you need to have, your teaching team has to be as diverse as maybe the people you teach</p>

<i>P5</i>	Diversity	Willingness to be diverse	I think most colleagues enjoy the diversity. It's just that they're not helped into exploring different ways of doing,
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Department's diversity	It is a very small department in [XXX] College. I see identity of the people I work with to be very similar to me. So, they be of the same ethnicity and same first language as myself, there are only 3 of us, so is a very small..
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Department's diversity	All within the faculty are not particularly diverse, which tends to be mainly one gender, and mainly one ethnicity
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Department's diversity	the department is about 95% female about 90%, Scottish, or UK based
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Department's diversity	Predominantly 40 plus (referring to age)
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Profession's diversity	within that cohort of lectures, that is certainly lots of different ethnicities and different nationalities are there. So, I think my own experience, and is limited Paula. My own experience is that there is diversity, but there could be more.
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Profession's diversity	if you are an ESOL teacher, then you work with diversity every day. And you see the benefits of diversity coming through your classroom all the time. So therefore, I think any barriers to diversity, whether conscious or unconscious would not be as apparent as they would be with lecturers from another department.
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Willingness to be diverse	I think the ESOL lectures are ..- they have less barriers to - they have less barriers to diversity because of the nature of the environment they work in. Having more acceptance, more tolerance, more used to and enjoy the benefits of a diverse classroom.
<i>P3</i>	Diversity	Willingness to be diverse	I think so, looking to the future, I think they would welcome a more diverse staff base ESOL lecturers, certainly, would.
<i>P3</i>	Feeling of (non) belonging	Uniformity	It is a very small department in [XXX] College. I see identity of the people I work with to be very similar to me. So,

			they be of the same ethnicity and same first language as myself, there are only 3 of us, so is a very small...
<i>P3</i>	Future of the profession	Move to diversity	I think so, looking to the future, I think they would welcome a more diverse staff base ESOL lecturers, certainly, would.
<i>P3</i>	Future of the profession	Uncertainty	I think it's depending on how ESOL is going to develop and that becomes quite political. I think if Scotland continues to have be run by Westminster's government, then we will continue to become more of a closed nation. And that will affect ESOL and ESOL practices. If Scotland goes a different path, then I would see the company, the country opening up and everything changing. So how will it develop? I think, I don't know - There doesn't seem to be any guiding light on an overall body would look at nature of development within Scotland within Scottish ESOL. So, the development is going to be haphazard, it's going to be down to the individual curriculum managers qualities, and who they recruit. So the profile of curriculum managers will be important. And I guess the applicants more second language students who qualify for the continuing curriculum managers to make, but I genuinely don't know the answer to that. I don't see it being either positive or negative, because I think it's gonna be - it's gonna happen incrementally and in lots of different places.
<i>P3</i>	Future of the profession	Uncertainty	I think it's going to be haphazard and dependent on the quality of applications and then for individual recruiting managers and looking for and that can be - it can be difficult to predict because every college will have its needs. On the college development, for the college, have had a really good year for ESOL because online suits them and they think they're going to continue online with a lot of their provision so the lecturers they recruit will be recruited with that in mind. Glasgow, Clyde college slightly will be very

			different, because they will go back to face to face. So the recruitment wouldn't change from from the way it was before. I think different factors are going to implement that, and it's hard to find any commonality. So I'm not sure I could be as big as I think it is down to e too many different moving parts. The decisions of many individuals.
<i>P3</i>	Future of the profession	No change	<p>R = But then I wonder, because you said at the beginning, you said that people work in, for example, in your particular department, have very similar identity to yourself. So I wonder if that will continue to be... - Do you think it will continue to be the same in maybe 10 - 15 years time? Or do you think it will be like different identities there?</p> <p>P3 28:45 My, my, my feeling is it will be the same. Because the people doing the recruiting will probably be the same.</p>
<i>P3</i>	Future of the profession	Uncertainty	I think it's also related to the political situation. And if we do you have a kind of far right isolation as government the way that we have at the moment. If that continues, and there's nothing to say that it won't, then I think that the UK will become more closed in that diversity in many aspects will will reduce. So yeah, I think it may also be interesting to look at the profile of teachers and somewhere like a city, a more cosmopolitan city like London, to see how FE in London is managing the profile there, because that could be the path that Scotland may take unless we become independent. And we can encourage more people to come here and make this their home.
<i>P3</i>	Hiring practices		I mean that people hiring would be more likely to hire someone, they're perceived as a Native speaker. But I don't have any, I don't have any evidence to back that up
<i>P3</i>	Hiring practices		I mean that there is a combination of the qualifications and the personality of a person and think how they would fit into the role but into the wider staff.

<i>P3</i>	Learner's identity		I did a survey in class last year, and there were 31 nationalities and 39 first languages.
<i>P3</i>	Learner's identity		we had a lot of Syrian, and people from Middle East that because [**this area**] had a high proportion of Syrian refugees in the resettlement programme.
<i>P3</i>	Learner's identity		There are lots of Eastern Europeans predominantly and is a big area for the Polish community to come to live and work.
<i>P3</i>	Learner's identity		we have students from every continent from every, from every part of the world. And they've all made the move to Scotland, usually with -with family members. And we have a really big Venezuelan community
<i>P3</i>	Learner's identity		Two of them are fully qualified lawyers, but over here, they can't get work in anything but a shop one and works in McDonald's and selling things over the internet, I believe, to trade. So in all those wonderful little ESOL stories that you get, but yes, the the diversity that the students come from, from every background, and they all have personal stories to tell. And some of them have stories, which are not so nice.
<i>P3</i>	Lecturer's experience		I worked for for quite a long time in sales marketing. And then I career changed. And I studied CELTA, and then worked as an ESOL tutor with a refugee programme. And then I moved to - I joined the college to teach ESOL more formally. So, this is a new thing to me, something I haven't been doing for a long time.
<i>P4</i>	Lack of awareness		[Identity] is not discussed. That's not something that really prominent at all.